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JOBS RESEARCH

Evaluation of the Educational Project ‘JOBS’

A project to evaluate the effects of the JOBS teaching and learning materials in the educational instruction of JOBS

Report Part II, Version 2018

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Introduction

The project 'JOBS' in Romania, initiated by the Centre for *International Projects in Education* (IPE) of the Zurich University of Teacher Education (henceforth PH Zurich), comprises the cooperative development of teaching and learning materials on job orientation and career options for students in their last year of compulsory education (gymnasium) or at the start of their post-compulsory schooling (technical colleges). It also comprises corresponding professional development for teachers who implement the new cross-curricular education program during one scholastic year. The cooperation in this Swiss-Romanian project includes the *ministries of Romania and Switzerland* (the Romanian Ministry for Education, Research, Youth and Sport in Bucharest, Department Career Training and the directorate of the Swiss Agency for Development and Research (SDR) of the Swiss Foreign Ministry in Bern, DEZA) and two *development teams* (Switzerland, Romania), made up of teachers from all relevant school levels and types, specialists in school development, members of the Romanian school inspectorate and designers, illustrators and professionals in the development of teaching and learning materials for schools. The impact of the project is being evaluated in an accompanying research study, in collaboration between university fellows from both countries.

JOBS PROGRAM: In the initial project phase both development teams collaborated to write pilot versions of the teaching and learning materials (2010-2012) which in turn were proved in two Romanian schools (a technical school and a gymnasium in the town of Braşov), followed by a trial for the duration of two scholastic years (2013-2015), expanded to further regions. During this second period a further education program for teachers involved in the project was set up. This program, consisting of courses, long-distance-learning (e-learning) and coaching, was developed in collaboration between the Swiss developmental teams from Zurich University of Teacher Education and the University of Bucharest.

JOBS RESEARCH STUDY: To test effects of this implemented school subject, based on JOBS teaching and learning materials, the research study was initiated. The Swiss research team started with this evaluation (2012-2017), developing the questionnaire, run the first survey and search for a team of Romanian researchers to cooperate with. In the second year, two teams with researchers from Transilvania University of Braşov and from the Babes-Bolyai University of Cluj-Napoca were built up, cooperating with the Swiss research fellows from Zurich University of Teacher education, responsible for the study and, in parallel, for the capacity-building of the Romanian researcher as well. In addition, a team of teachers was found to contribute to the study, analyzing students' answers, captured by a test on JOBS-related knowledge.

Implementing JOBS as a school subject demands a shift in teaching framework, teaching structure, and lesson design. To master these new requirements on instructional design and teachers' acting, JOBS-teachers are promoted and supported in their professional development by courses and handbooks. JOBS-lessons emphasize on interactions among students, supported and coached by their teachers; through discussion during the lessons and experiences within the job market, students develop knowledge and awareness, useful for their career choices. The lessons, activating students through a cognitive and affective approach, are initiated by the tasks set in the teaching and learning materials. Three teachers from different subjects cooperate as an interdisciplinary team and conduct the JOBS-lessons in shared responsibility. In this setting, teachers' role comprises requirements to initiate task based learning processes and to support the students in their learning processes. The tasks aim on experiencing knowledge and skills as well as to reflect on individuals' perspective, shared in discussions and searching for solutions. In this process, the focus is not on right or wrong answers, but on logical argumentations, using different facts and experiences. Students learn to present their insights logically and comprehensibly and to discuss them within whole-class discussions. It is the teachers' job to stimulate students with encouraging and pertinent questions to promote further thinking. This method of teaching demands a change of traditional classroom roles of students and teachers.

The RESEARCH STUDY focus on *students* as well as on *teachers*, responsible for the lesson setting and the quality of the lessons. The evaluation study aims to trace effects and developments initiated by the JOBS program on both levels and to identify factors that facilitate or restrict these developments (see Report Part I, chapter 2).

Design of the study: The study is designed as an intervention-study in a pre- and post-design with control-group. Students and teachers from classes, who attend the JOBS-program, and others, who didn't, were collected by questionnaires (see Report Part I, chapter 3). Main questions of the study are:

- 1) What effects of JOBS-program on students and on teachers can be identified?
- 2) Which components contribute to the learning output?

Results on these two questions are presented in two reports.

Report Part I, September 2015, contains results on students' learning output, evaluated by the students themselves and by their teachers. It shows results on the learning output of JOBS-students compared with students, who didn't attend JOBS-program. The learning output was evaluated in three approaches: assessment of knowledge (1), based on tasked relying on the units of the program, self-assessed knowledge (2) and skills (3), based on the content of JOBS learning material. In addition, the relevance of this knowledge and skills were evaluated as well. Concerning the skills, students and teachers were also asked to assess students' pleasure and motivation working on the tasks of the JOBS-program. Students were asked as well as teachers to evaluate students' learning output.

Report Part II, July 2017, shows results of individual and contextual factors that contribute to the learning output of the students, evaluated by the students themselves and by their teachers.

The first chapter explains the goals of the second part of the report (chapter 1), followed by additional aspects of the theoretical background, the study is based on (chapter 2). The chapter on methods presents the instruments, used to gain the results of report part II. Information on statistical processes, used to analyze the data, focused on the research questions follow in chapter 3. Chapter 4 and 5 present results of both parts of the research study: Chapter 4 shows results on individual and contextual characteristics of the students and their effects of the learning output. Chapter 5 presents individual and contextual characteristics of the teachers and its effects on the learning output of the students, assessed from the point of view of the teachers. A final chapter (chapter 6) summarizes the results from Report 2017 Part II, amending results from Report 2015 Part I.

To understand individual students' experiences with the JOBS-program, in a second approach the learning of the students is investigated by an interview-study. The study is presented in chapter 7.

In addition, a list of dissemination activities is added (chapter 8).

We thank all the students and the teachers, who contributed to the study, as well as to all persons, who contributed to the JOBS-RESEARCH-study, with their cooperation or their interest.

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1 Aims of the second part of the report

In terms of the research and evaluation study, the expectations of the project commissioners are concerned primarily on the learning progress and the knowledge acquisition of the participating students. Through the project's cooperative approach, in which project members from both countries work together, further aims are set. This double assignment, coupled with additional professional development of the partners in Romania, led to a complex project organization of the study. The study is subdivided into multiple phases (see Report Part I).

The evaluation of JOBS program assesses the effects of the educational program 'JOBS' (teaching and learning materials as well as teachers' lessons) the learning output of the students evaluated by the students themselves and by their teachers. In addition, a test was developed to gather students' JOBS related knowledge. The study focuses not only on the learning output of the students, attending the program, but as well on the effect of individual and contextual preconditions on the learning output and on possible changes, effected by the program.

In addition to the explanations on the research study in the Report Part I (see p. 7f.), Part II focus on the following results:

Results on individual and contextual factors and its effects on the learning output of the students (Chapter 2 to 6)

Results of the interview study with focus on individual students' experiences (chapter 7).

Dissemination of results of the JOBS research study and the team members (chapter 8).

2 Additional explanations of the theoretical background and research questions of part II

Requirements of positioning themselves in the job market and taking primary responsibility for themselves and for a subsequent generation, young people are challenged to deal with their entry into adulthood (Havighurst, 1948; Dreher & Dreher, 1991; Krapp & Weidenmann, 2001; Albisser, Bieri & Keller-Schneider, 2011). To master these developmental task, students must be prepared to take a role in society and to contribute to society's development. The question of how an educational program may contribute to this developmental is the primary concern of the JOBS project.

2.1 The development of knowledge and competence

Knowledge is an important base to acquire competency to deal with demands and expectations of society and to master developmental tasks. Explicit knowledge can be taught, but explicit knowledge is not sufficient to acquire competence. Individuals' perception of requirements (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984), shaped by motives, goals and self-regulation, have an influence on individuals' competence development as well (Baumert & Kunter, 2006; Keller-Schneider, 2010).

Competence as a latent potential (Chomsky, 1981) means more than factual knowledge. Competence becomes manifest through dealing with requirements in specific situations (Weinert, 2001; Neuweg, 2014). To acquire knowledge and skills to deal with requirements in an appropriate way, tasks focused on goals on different levels of complexity are crucial. Knowledge and skills, fostered through JOBS program, are focused to learning objectives of varying complexity (Anderson & Krathwohl, 2001). To acquire knowledge and skills cognitive factors are not sufficient to boost the learning output; emotional, motivational and volitional factors are crucial as well (Weinert, 2001; Keller-Schneider, 2014, 2016).

The JOBS lessons, supported by teaching and learning materials, aim to equip teachers with an instrument to design interactive lessons. Even they haven't learned to plan and conduct lessons in an interactive way, JOBS-teachers can facilitate their students' exploration of the working world, the regional opportunities available to them and their own strengths and interests, using the suggestions and explanations of the teaching materials. Results on the learning output is explained in the Report Part I (Keller-Schneider & Albisser, 2015).

However, it is a point of interest, which individual characteristics of the students and the teachers support students' learning output concerning the knowledge and skills, JOBS-program aims to acquire. This will be explained in this second part of the Report on JOBS-RESEARCH-study.

2.2 The influence of individual and contextual factors on students' learning output

Figure 1 shows the model the study is based on. A learning setting gives opportunities to learn, but how students use these opportunities and in which extent they engage themselves in their learning process is influenced by different factors (Fend, 1998, 2006, Helmke, 2003; Keller-Schneider, 2014, 2016). Based on this approach, the quality of the *learning setting* as well as the professionalism and the personality of the *teachers* are important preconditions. In addition, the individual *students*, their use of the offered *learning opportunities* and their *individual characteristics* are crucial as well. The students' use of learning opportunities relies on their perception and task appraisals, embedded in the specific situation. So, the teaching style and teachers' personality, the complexity of the task and its fit to the students' preconditions as well as the learning surrounding and its atmosphere must fit to students' knowledge, motivation, beliefs and volition. These components of individual resources could have an influence on students' task appraisals. In addition, the *family background*, a student is embedded in, and the *school surrounding* are further preconditions effecting students task appraisal, the intensity of dealing with them and the learning output.

Fig. 1. The process of using learning situations in an interplay of learning opportunities, its use, family background and individual problem-solving behavior as predictors of possible learning outcomes (Keller-Schneider 2014, p. 149; adaptation to JOBS as a learning opportunity set in cursive).

Figure 1 shows the different components that contribute to a learning output: *learning opportunity* (program and teacher), *learning activities* (working on the tasks of JOBS-program) and *family background and context* (e.g. school type, area of the school). *Individuals perceptions of requirements* as the core element of the learning process is in the center, showing the cognitive, metacognitive or unconscious decision of the individual student to let themselves involve in a challenging and demanding process to work on a specific requirement. Individuals' resources and the use of social support are significant for task appraisals and the intensity of working on the tasks.

Tasks and stimuli in general are perceived with individual resources, such as knowledge, skills, beliefs and collective norms, goals and motives (Keller-Schneider, 2014, 2016). Based on an assessment of the extent to which they seem to be relevant and solvable, tasks are either accepted as challenges or are avoided as unsolvable or not significant. Based on the transactional model of stress and coping (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984) requirements were perceived by primary and secondary appraisals. Depending on the relevance of a requirement as well as on the individual and social resources, a task can be perceived as a challenge and leads into a process of dealing with it. From this process, a learning output will emerge, enlarging individuals' knowledge, insights and skills. If a task is perceived as not relevant or not challenging, dealing with it can be avoided, denied or refused. In addition, a task can also be mastered by routine. In all these cases dealing with the specific task does not promote individuals' capacity building and competence development (Keller-Schneider, 2010). So, to promote students' competency, challenging tasks, a discursive setting and motivating teachers are essential. Students must be ready to deal with them and search for solutions, promoted by a supporting surrounding.

To foster students' learning outcome by the JOBS program, the tasks of the program must fit students' precondition and motivate and involve them in searching for solutions. To fulfill basic needs of competence, relatedness and autonomy (Ryan & Deci, 2000) a possibility to show, appreciate and discuss their solutions is essential. The task-based learning JOBS-program in student-centered interactive settings provides a learning opportunity to foster students to acquire knowledge and skills concerning professions and work situations. In addition, the didactic approach of JOBS-program gives an opportunity to reinforce students' awareness of strength and interest (Jerusalem & Klein Hebling, 2009), by experiencing the basic needs of competence, autonomy and relatedness (Ryan & Deci, 2000).

2.3 Summary of the results of the report part I and further research questions

2.3.1 Summary of the result in the report part I

The study is designed as a longitudinal intervention-study with control-group, with focus on students and teachers. In the Report Part I (Keller-Schneider & Albisser, 2015) results on the learning output of the students were presented. This learning output was evaluated in three approaches, such as a knowledge test, a self-evaluation of acquired knowledge and self-evaluated skills, enriched with motivational factors relying on these tasks.

The results on the learning output of the *students* were summarized as follows:

- At the end of the year, JOBS-students dispose on more *knowledge*, evaluated by the knowledge test, than Non-JOBS-students. While JOBS-students show a significant increase of knowledge over the year attending JOBS-program, the knowledge of Non-JOBS-students is stable.
- The same effects are identified in the results on *self-assessed knowledge*: Knowledge of JOBS-students increase during the year of JOBS-classes significantly while the knowledge of the Non-JOBS-students stay on the same level. Concerning the *relevance of knowledge*, JOBS-program focus on, there is no difference between the groups and no development over time. All the students assess JOBS knowledge as important.
- JOBS students, after a year of JOBS-classes, show higher *skills* in dealing with requirements, JOBS-program focus on. Skills of the Non-JOBS-students remain on the same level. With focus

on the relevance of these skills and on the pleasure by using them, JOBS-students show higher marks than Non-JOBS-students, at the beginning of the year as well as at the end of the one-year intervention. Their first experiences within tasks of the JOBS-Program effect their attitudes.

From the perspective of the *teachers*, the learning output of the student can be summarized as follows:

- Teachers assess the *knowledge* of the students similar as the students' assessment, but on a lower level than the students do. From their point of view, JOBS-students' knowledge increases during the year as well, while the knowledge of Non-JOBS-students remain on the same level. JOBS- and Non-JOBS teachers assess the relevance of JOBS knowledge as relevant.
- Ratings on the *skills* of the students, JOBS-students' skills increased over the year, the one of the Non-JOBS-students increase slightly, but not significant. JOBS-teacher rate the pleasure students experience dealing with the tasks of JOBS-program as higher than Non-JOBS-teachers do. To experience the program contributes to an emotional perspective (valence) on the tasks.

→ All in all, from the point of view of the students and of the teachers, students attending JOBS-classes show an increase of knowledge and skills, while Non-Jobs-students remain on the same level, even they assess this knowledge and these skills as relevant. JOBS-program influences their development.

2.3.2 Research questions with results in the report part II

Based on the theory of the influence of individuals' task appraisal on the learning output, results to the following questions will be reported in this second part of the report on JOBS-RESEARCH. They focus on individual and contextual resources of students, their development and their effect on the learning output.

- 1) Which differences in their shaping of individual resources, such as self-concept, motives and beliefs, can be identified between JOBS- and Non-JOBS-students and over time? Are there distinctive developments of JOBS- and Non-JOBS-students?
- 2) Which differences can be identified between the two groups (JOBS and Non-JOBS students) and over time (at the beginning and at the end of the program) concerning social resources (context of family and school)?
- 3) To what extend do individual and contextual characteristics contribute to the learning output of JOBS-students?

Teachers contribute to the learning output of the students (Hattie, 2009). They are part of the learning opportunities for the students (see Fig. 1). In addition, JOBS-program and its didactical approach could influence JOBS-teachers' development. With focus on the JOBS-teachers the following questions will be investigated:

- 4) Which differences in their shaping of individual resources, such as self-concept, motives and beliefs, can be identified between JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers and over time? Are there distinctive developments of JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers?
- 5) Which differences can be identified between the two groups (JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers) and over time (at the beginning and at the end of the program) concerning factors of social resources (context of the schools)?
- 6) To what extend do individual and contextual characteristics contribute to the learning output of JOBS-students, assessed by their teachers?

3 Method – additional explanations

3.1 Design of the study

As explained in the first part of the report (Part I, 2015, chapter 3), the study follows a longitudinal design (pre- and post-test) with control-group. The possible effect of a repeated answer of a questionnaire was controlled by the Solomon four-group-design (Bortz & Döring, 2002).

A total of 796 JOS-students and 111 JOBS-teachers and a total of 1077 Non-JOBS-students and 190 Non-JOBS-teachers from Braşov County were included in the study. The data of a second wave, expanded to new regions, were not valid, so they couldn't be used for the study.

3.2 Instruments

The following instruments were applied in the questionnaire used in the research study, grouped by the areas shown in *Figure 1*. A general overview on the instruments used for students and teachers are listed synoptically in Report 2015, Part I.

Table 1 give an overview on the scales, used in the study with students, explained with item examples, number of items within a scale and the reliability of the scale (Cronbach's Alpha). *Table 2* shows the ones for teachers.

3.2.1 Instruments used for students

Tab. 1. Instruments used in the questionnaire for students

Instruments and scales (Number of Items)	Examples of items	Cronbach's Alpha			
		JOBS		Non-JOBS	
		t1	t2	t1	t2
Knowledge and skills, related to JOBS-program					
Knowledge on JOBS (17 sum) ⁴	How do you plan an interview?	-	-	-	-
Knowledge, self-assessed (ek 10) ¹	I know my professional interests.	.80	.86	.80	.79
Skills, self-assessed (spot 15) ¹	Presenting important information about a profession on a poster... I know how to do	.91	.92	.89	.89
Individual characteristics					
<i>Attitude</i>					
Relevance of knowledge (er 10) ¹	I find it important to know how to ask questions about professions	.82	.87	.85	.83
Relevance of skills (sim 15) ¹	Presenting important information about a profession on a poster... I find important	.93	.93	.92	.91
Enjoyment by using skills (spl 15) ¹	I like to analyze a workplace	.93	.93	.91	.90
<i>Self-concept</i>					
Subject competence (fk 11) ¹	In Chemistry, I am ... good	.79	.76	.76	.65
Subject interests (fv 11) ¹	I like Physics	.76	.73	.76	.69
Self-competence (es 5) ¹	I do my tasks reliably.	.87	.84	.86	.82
General self-efficacy (sw 8)	Whatever happens I will cope.	.91	.90	.90	.89
School-related self-efficacy (sw 5) ¹	When I put a lot of energy into it I can also solve difficult tasks in class.	.85	.81	.84	.84
Self-efficacy, social-related (sw 4) ¹	I can also cope well with difficult colleagues.	.77	.76	.77	.76

Motives					
Interest and importance					
Interest on professions (ev3 1) ¹	How big is your interest to know more about professions?	-	-	-	-
Interest on individual strength (ev4 1) ¹	How big is your interest to know more about your strength and interests?	-	-	-	-
Importance of learning at school (rele1 1) ¹	How important is it for you to learn a lot at school?	-	-	-	-
Importance of learning for future (rele4 1) ¹	How much will your future perspectives will be improved, if you learn a lot at school?	-	-	-	-
Motivation for learning at school					
• <i>Learning motivation</i> (mo 4) ²	In school, I like the tasks best when I must really think.	.84	.80	.83	.81
• <i>Social approval motivation</i> (mo 4) ²	I participate in class so the others do not think that I know less than them.	.75	.73	.70	.67
• <i>Avoidance motivation</i> (mo 3) ²	In school, it is important to me to invest as little as possible.	.51	.61	.60	.52
Work motives					
• <i>Autonomy</i> (wi 6) ¹	Plan my work very independently86	.86	.85	.82
• <i>Relatedness</i> (wi 5) ¹	Having a kind of work where colleagues can support each other,86	.87	.84	.84
• <i>Challenge</i> (wi 4) ¹	A work, which is challenging me60	.64	.70	.62
• <i>Meaningfulness</i> (wi 4) ¹	A socially important work77	.79	.80	.77
Beliefs					
Beliefs on teaching and learning					
• <i>Constructivist</i> (ltu 6) ¹	Students have to write down insights in their own words in order to remember the facts better.	.85	.86	.84	.82
• <i>Transmissive</i> (ltu 6) ¹	If students cannot solve a task the teacher has not explained it properly.	.77	.80	.80	.75
Achievement orientation towards different performance measurements					
• <i>Individual norm</i> (nor 3) ³	A good achievement is an achievement of a student that is better than the one before.	.63	.69	.62	.64
• <i>Social norm</i> (nor 3) ³	A good achievement is an achievement of a student that is better than the one of the other students.	.81	.85	.78	.80
• <i>Task based norm</i> (nor 3) ³	A good achievement is when I have understood something correctly.	.64	.68	.66	.64
Relevance of learning at school (rele 4) ¹	How much will your future perspectives be improved if you learn a lot in school?	.61	.57	.59	.54
Context					
Family context					
Parental support (par 4) ¹	My parents help me when I have problems.	.84	.83	.82	.81
School context (School as context for learning)					
Support of JOBS teachers (supT 4) ¹	My JOBS teacher helps me when I don't know how to go on with a certain task.	.85	.87	.80	.80
Importance for parents (re2) ¹	How important is it for your parents that you learn a lot at school?	-	-	-	-
Importance for teachers (re3 1) ¹	How important is it for your teachers that you learn a lot at school?	-	-	-	-
<i>Note:</i> The items were assessed on a Likert scale: ¹ 1=low to 6=high; ² 1=low to 5=high; ³ 1=low to 4=high; ⁴ = open questions, answers were analyzed by the method of content analyze (Mayring, 2015), points were added to a sum.					

3.2.2 Instruments used for teachers

Tab. 2. Instruments used in the questionnaire for teachers

Instruments and scales (Number of Items)	Examples of items	Cronbachs Alpha			
		JOBS		Non-JOBS	
		t1	t2	t1	t2
Knowledge and skills, related to JOBS-program, estimated by teachers					
Students' knowledge (ek 11) ¹	My knowledge about professions	.88	.92	.88	.90
Students' skills (spot 15) ¹	Occupying myself with the professional world... I know how to do (not well ... very well)	.95	.95	.94	.95
Individual characteristics					
<i>Attitudes</i>					
Relevance of knowledge (er 11) ¹	Knowing my professional interests, I find... (unimportant ...important)	.88	.86	.89	.90
Relevance of skills (sim 15) ¹	Analyzing a workplace... I find important (unimportant ...important)	.96	.94	.92	.95
Students' joy using skills (spl 15) ¹	Occupying myself with the professional world... I like to do (not at all... very much)	.94	.92	.92	.96
<i>Self-concept</i>					
Self-efficacy, general (8) ¹	I always succeed in solving difficult problems when I try hard.	.88	.90	.89	.90
Self-efficacy as teacher (10) ¹	I'm confident to communicate with demanding students, if I try hard	.76	.73	.75	.81
<i>Attitudes</i>					
Interest and importance					
Interest on professions (ev3 1) ¹	How big is the students' interest to know more about professions?	-	-	-	-
Interest on individual strength (ev4 1) ¹	How big is the students' interest to know more about your strength and interests?	-	-	-	-
Importance of learning at school (rele1 1) ¹	How important is it for you that students learn a lot at school?	-	-	-	-
Importance of learning for future (rele4 1) ¹	How much will students' future perspectives will be improved, if they learn a lot at school?	-	-	-	-
<i>Motives</i>					
Students' learning motives in school (mo 11)					
Learning (4) ²	I like the tasks best when I have to really think.	.76	.73	.84	.85
Social approval (4) ²	I pay a lot of attention that the others don't think I am stupid.	.75	.78	.80	.78
Avoidance (3) ²	It is important to me to invest as little as possible.	.62	.74	.61	.63
Motives for work and occupational career (19)					
• Autonomy (6) ¹	What is important for you? Plan my work very independently.	.79	.76	.83	.83
• Relatedness (5) ¹	A work, which expects a close collaboration with my colleagues.	.82	.83	.75	.91
• Challenge (4) ¹	A challenging work, which expects a lot of different skills.	.54	.42	.24	.39
• Meaningfulness (4) ¹	Having a kind of work where I can develop something together with colleagues.	.57	.69	.39	.64
<i>Beliefs</i>					
Beliefs on teaching and learning (ItUe 12)					
Constructivist orientation (6) ¹	The teacher shall encourage the students to find solutions themselves.	.62	.64	.70	.72
Transmissive orientation (6) ¹	The students have to copy down the given summaries so they can understand the facts well.	.52	.65	.37	.46
Orientation towards different reference standards of performance measurements					
Individual orientation (nor 3) ³	A good achievement is when I got more right answers than last time.	.39	.62	.61	.61
Social orientation (nor 3) ³	A good achievement is when I show better results than others in the class.	.77	.87	.78	.85
Task orientation (nor 3) ³	A good achievement is when I could achieve what was expected from me.	.56	.51	.49	.59

School context as a resource for teachers					
		JOBS		Non-J	
<i>Cooperation with teachers (only t2)</i>		im	fr	im	fr
within subject groups Importance (im) and frequencies (fr)					
Planning and preparation (5) ¹	We develop the quarterly planning together.	.72	.86	.83	.88
Discussion and reflection (11) ¹	We inform each other about the behavior and the levels of achievement of inconspicuous students.	.90	.94	.93	.96
with JOBS teachers					
Planning and preparation (5) ¹	We plan class together.	.84	.92	-	-
Discussion and reflection (11) ¹	We discuss our expectations towards the behavior of students in order to come to a joint idea.	.93	.94	-	-
<i>Team quality</i>					
Within Jobs-teams (J) and subject-teams (S)		J	S	-	S
Shared aims and values (tq 4) ¹	There is consensus about the commitment of team decisions.	.83	.85	-	.81
Teach as a team (tq 4) ¹	We discuss and compare requirements that we give our students.	.85	.85	-	.81
Cooperation as a team (tq 5) ¹	We work well as a team.	.88	.87	-	.87
Solve problems together (tq 4) ¹	Conflicts are dealt with openly and constructively.	.73	.76	-	.73
<i>Note: The items were assessed on a Likert scale: ¹ 1=low to 6=high; ² 1=low to 5=high; ³ 1=low to 4=high.</i>					

3.3 Data processing and analysis

Qualitative data (open questions on JOBS-knowledge):

The answers of the open questions from the knowledge test were analyzed by content analyzes, based on a coding guide, carried out by the team of JOBS-teachers with *Dana Felegean, Alina Gavrilă and Dorina Drahici*, trained to do this task.

Quantitative data

In the *first phase* of the evaluation (2013-2015) the collected data were revised: latent structures were verified by factor analysis, reliability was tested (Cronbach's alpha test). Differences of means between the intervention and the control group were tested by variance analyzes (compared between two groups and two times). In the *second phase* of the evaluation (2015-2017), effects of individual and contextual factors on the learning output was examined. The data were analyzed by scientists of the Transilvania University of Braşov, Department of Psychology, Dr. Laura Teodora David, Dr. Ana-Maria Cazan and Dr. Camelia Truta, in cooperation with the project leadership team of JOBS-RESEARCH, Prof. Dr. Manuela Keller-Schneider and Prof. Dr. Stefan Albisser. The following steps has been carried out:

- Data cleaning and verification of distribution, computing scales after factor analysis (principal component analysis (oblime method), extraction of factors following the Kaiser criteria).
- Variance analyses per instrument: Compare intervention and control groups (JOBS – Non-JOBS) per time of measurement t1 and t2 (ANOVA; ANCOVA, if the difference in time 1 is significant). Multifactorial variance analyses with repeated measurement (GLM) to investigate on longitudinal effects.
- Tests to prove learning effects, caused by a repeated use of the survey, controlled by Solomon design: variance analyses on the four Solomon groups time 2: JOBS with pretest, JOBS without pretest, NON-JOBS with pretest, NON-JOBS without pretest.
- Regression analyses to investigate the effects of individual and contextual factors on the learning output of the students.

4 Results of study A – Students

After a short introduction into the meaning of the constructs, results are shown in figures and tables with short comments and interpretations, marked with arrows (→). The *first subchapters* present results on means and the comparison between the intervention- and the control-group (JOBS and Non-JOBS students) as well as in their development over a period of the school year of the intervention. The *second subchapters* contain tables on its effect on the learning output, evaluated in three different approaches: knowledge (test), self-assessed knowledge and self-assessed skills.

Chapter 4 contains results from students, chapter 5 results on teachers, followed by a summary and conclusions in chapter 6.

4.1 Learning output and the effect of attitudes on JOBS knowledge and skills

4.1.1 Attitudes on JOBS knowledge and skills and their differences between the groups and over time

Performed JOBS-knowledge (tested with open questions)

The knowledge and skills of the students were assessed in three different approaches (see report 2015, part I). First by a knowledge test with open questions (Fig. 2), second by self-evaluated knowledge (Fig. 3). The third approach focus on self-evaluated skills (Fig. 4).

Results on knowledge and its development are shown in Figure 2 and in Table 3 (for further explanations see report 2015, chapter 4.2).

JOBS program has a significant effect on the learning output of the students (see *Tab. 3*). The expected effect that students participating in JOBS program would have distinctly more JOBS-related knowledge than those who did not take part is statistically significant, but the difference between the groups is small. It can be assumed, that they were not challenged by the open questions or not used to write all they know about they were asked to. The differences between the sums of the points, scored over all 17 questions, are shown in *Figure 2*.

Fig. 2. Content knowledge JOBS by intervention and control groups: sums over all questions, with results of variance analysis (between the groups JOBS and Non-JOBS, times and development)

Tab. 3. Knowledge (test), differences between the groups and over time

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1 – Time 2	
	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANOVA	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANCOVA	J GLM	NJ GLM
Knowledge	23.96 (6.74)	20.41 (6.95)	J>NJ***	24.52 (6.79)	20.58 (6.68)	J>NJ***	n.s.	n.s.
Knowledge time 1 J > NJ *** F(815) = 54.65, p < .001 $\eta^2 = .06$; time 2 J > NJ *** F(668) = 54.65, p < .001 $\eta^2 = .18$;								
Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M = mean, SD = standard deviation, level of significance p: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; η^2 = Eta square								

Knowledge and its relevance (self-assessment)

In the second approach, *knowledge* was assessed by self-evaluation. In addition, the *attitude* on this knowledge was asked as well. Results on the knowledge and its relevance in the opinion of the students are shown in Fig. 3, results of the mean comparisons (variance-analyzes) are shown in Table 4.

Attitudes are the dispositions of persons towards a specific situation or demand. As a framework for decision making upon coping with requirements, they were influenced by underlying values, beliefs and feelings. The attitude of the *relevance* of JOBS-knowledge and JOBS-skills on professions and individual strength and interests reflect the cognitive approach, *emotions* by experiencing the specific skills gives information on the valence of experiencing the skills. Attitudes, fitting to the demands (Blömeke, Kaiser & Lehmann, 2008), are preconditions for acquisition of knowledge and skills.

Results on the attitude towards the relevance of JOBS-knowledge are shown in *Figure 3* and *Table 4*, the results on the attitudes towards the relevance of the skills and its valence of emotions (such as pleasant or not pleasant) were shown in *Figure 4* and *Table 5*.

Fig. 3. Ratings of content knowledge JOBS and the relevance of this knowledge, by means of JOBS and Non-JOBS students

At the beginning of the school year JOBS-students and Non-JOBS-students rate their knowledge as adequate. The means are in the upper part of the scale. There is no difference between the intervention and the control group. At the end of the school year, JOBS-students rate their knowledge significantly higher than the students from the control group do (see Fig. 3 and Table 4).

Concerning the *relevance of knowledge*, both groups show high values both at the beginning and at the end of the school year. There is no significant difference between the two groups. At the beginning as well as at the end of the school year, students rate this knowledge as very useful and meaningful.

Tab. 4. Ratings of content knowledge JOBS and its relevance; mean (M) and standard deviations (SD), variance analysis on time t1, t2 and on the development (t1-t2), per intervention group (J) and control group (NJ)

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1 – Time 2	
	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{GLM}	NJ _{GLM}
Knowledge ¹	4.32/ 84	4.31/ 89	n.s.	4.80/ .75	4.36/ .78	J > NJ ***	t1 < t2 ***	n.s.
Relevance ²	5.15/ 68	5.06/ .75	n.s.	5.04/ .82	5.08/ .72	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.

¹ Main effect of knowledge J > NJ ***, F(1,1619) = 30.46, p < .001, $\eta^2 = .03$;
² Main effect of relevance of knowledge J/NJ, F(1,1654) = 3.04, p = .08, $\eta^2 = .002$

Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance p: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; η^2 = Eta square

Skills, its relevance and its valence (self-assessment)

Skills to be acquired during the JOBS program were evaluated from multiple perspectives: extent of its competence, its relevance and its valence (pleasure). Students were asked to evaluate every single skill (15 in total) by the perspectives: ‘I can ...’ (competence), ‘I find it important’ (relevance) and ‘I like doing...’ (valence). The results of the ratings of these three perspectives are shown in Figure 4 and Table 5.

Fig. 4. Skills, relevance and valence of JOBS-based skills, by intervention (JOBS) and control group (Non-JOBS)

A highly significant increase of *skills* of the JOBS-students during the period of the intervention by JOBS is visible. From their perspective, JOBS-students are much more able to show the skills, trained on through JOBS program.

A comparison of the *relevance* and the *valence* of these skills between the intervention group JOBS and the control group Non-JOBS, significant differences are visible at the beginning and at the end of the school year. JOBS-students rate the relevance of the skills and their enjoyment in experiencing these skills higher than Non-JOBS students do. The survey took place in the second and third week of the program, therefore JOBS-students experienced the new subject already, their evaluations seem to be effected by the first experience, but their attitudes towards JOBS-program remains stable during the year.

Tab. 5. Ratings of the attitudes on the importance of knowledge, the importance of skills and the pleasure in practicing the skills. Mean (M) and standard deviations (SD), results of the variance analysis, time t1 and t2 and repeated measurement (t1-t2), by intervention (J) and control group (NJ)

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1–Time 2	
	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANOVA	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANCOVA	J GLM	NJ GLM
Skills ¹	4.39/ .98	4.24/ .94	n.s.	4.57/ .89	4.43/ .91	NJ < J***	t1 < t2***	n.s.
Relevance ²	4.62/1.03	4.43/1.03	NJ < J***	4.67/ .93	4.49/ .99	NJ < J**	n.s.	n.s.
Valence ³	4.48/1.07	4.24/1.03	NJ < J**	4.43/1.02	4.26/1.05	N < J***	n.s.	n.s.

¹ Main effect of skills: J > NJ*** F(1,1552) = 35.919, p < .000, η² = .023; ² Main effect of relevance of skills: F(1,1581) = 23.923, p < .001, η² = .015; Solomon n.s.; ³ Main effect of valence of skills: F(1,1578) = 12.913, p < .001, η² = .008; Solomon n.s.; level of significance: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance p: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; η²= Eta square

4.1.2 Effects on the learning output

Results of the different models (M4, M5, M6) on the effects of attitudes on the knowledge and the skills of the students at the end of the school-year are shown in the following table. Table 6 contains the results on the attitudes at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) and at the end of the year (*time 2*) on the tested knowledge at the end of the year. Table 7 shows the results on the self-assessed knowledge, Table 8 the ones on the self-evaluated skills.

Tab. 6. Effects of students' attitudes on their tested knowledge (knowledge questions)

Model	Time 1				Time 2			
	M4 er	M5 sim	M6 spl	M4,5,6	M4 er	M5 sim	M6 spl	M4,5,6
Relevance knowledge M4 er	.150*			.114	.357***			.159*
Relevance of skills M5 sim		.131*		.049		.423***		.315**
Valence of skills M6 spl			.149*	.022			.331***	-.003
R ²	.022	.017	.022	.027	.128	.179	.109	.184
F	7.381***	5.430***	6.914***	2.479	47.79***	69.13***	37.55***	21.30***

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

Results show, that the attitudes toward JOBS content knowledge (see Table 6) at the beginning of the intervention has a very weak effect on the learning output, measured at the end of the intervention program by tested knowledge. Only about 3% of the learning output can be explained by the prior attitudes.

Attitudes at the end of the intervention explains 18% of the learning output. Attitudes on the relevance of the skills shows the biggest effect (Beta .423***), relevance of the knowledge (Beta .357**) and the

valence of the skills (Beta .331***) are significant as well. Proved all together, the attitudes on relevance show higher effects than valence does.

Tab. 7. Effects of students' attitudes on their learning output (self-assessed knowledge)

Model	Time 1				Time 2			
	M4 er	M5 sim	M6 spl	M4,5,6	M4 er	M5 sim	M6 spl	M4, 5,6
Relevance knowledge er	.396***			.264***	.667***			.409***
Relevance of skills sim		.426***		.207		.653***		.244**
Valence of skills spl			.409***	.111			.617***	.200
R ²	.157	.181	.168	.255	.445	.426	.381	.554
F	58.30***	66.62***	59.41***	30.06***	256.81***	231.01***	184.73***	115.94***

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

Results on effects of attitudes towards JOBS content knowledge (M4,5,6, see Table 7) at the beginning of the intervention (*time 1*) on self-evaluated knowledge at the end of the intervention (*time 2*) explains 25% of the variance of the relevance of knowledge. The effects on the relevance of the skills is higher than the one of the valence of the skills. Investigated separately, relevance of knowledge (M4, Beta .40***) and skills (M5, Beta .43***) as well as the valence of the skills (M6, Beta .41***) contribute to an explained variance of 16%-18%.

At the end of the school year (*time 2*), the effects of relevance and valence are even higher (relevance of knowledge with Beta .67***), skills with Beta .65***), valence of the skills (Beta .62***) with explained variance of 38%-45%. Effects of the predictors investigated all together (M4,5,6), explain 55% of the self-evaluated knowledge of the students at the end of the year. From the point of view of the students it is important, that students' attitudes fit to demand to acquire specific knowledge and skills.

Tab. 8. Effects of students' attitudes on their learning output (self-assessed skills)

Model	Time 1				Time 2			
	M4 er	M5 sim	M6 spl	M4,5,6	M4 er	M5 sim	M6 spl	M4,5,6
Relevance of knowledge M4 er	.420***			.212**	.602***			.120**
Relevance of skills M5 sim		.473***		.209		.862***		.512***
Valence of skills M6 spl			.511***	.203			.891***	.326***
R ²	.177	.224	.261	.300	.363	.743	.670	.780
F	64.63***	84.27***	101.1***	36.66***	175.3***	880.9***	597.5***	324.4***

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

Attitudes (see Table 8) towards JOBS-knowledge and JOBS-skills at the beginning of the year (*time 1*), as predictors from the beginning of the intervention, explain 30% of the skills at the end of the year. Each predictor is significant (relevance of knowledge with Beta .42***, skills with Beta .47***, valence of the skills (Beta .51***); proved all together, each of them contribute (with Beta around .20) to the learning output.

Attitudes at the end of the program (*time 2*) contribute with very high effects (relevance of knowledge with Beta .60***, skills with Beta .86***, valence of the skills with Beta .89***) to the learning output concerning skills. Tested all together(m4,5,6), 78% of the variance of the skills at the end of the year is explained; relevance of the skills shows the highest effect (Beta .51***), followed by the valence of the skills (Beta .33***) ant the relevance of the knowledge (Beta .12**).

4.2 Individual characteristics as resources for learning

Individuals' characteristics, such as beliefs, achievement values, goals, motives, and interests as well as knowledge and skills and individuals' self-concept influence learning and achievement (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002; Pintrich, 2003; Weiner, 1992). Individual characteristics shape individuals' perception of requirements (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984) and the unconscious decision to deal with them (Keller-Schneider, 2010, 2014). Based on the model of the process of demand appraisal for learning activities and learning output (Keller-Schneider, 2014) in a formal context of school, individuals' characteristics are essential for dealing with requirements. The following results focus on extensions of individual characteristics, its differences between the intervention group of JOBS-students and the control-group of Non-JOBS-students and their development during the school year, when the intervention took place. In the second part of every chapter, effects of these characteristics are shown twice: at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) on the learning output by the end of the intervention (*time 2*) and at the end of the year (*time 2*) on the learning output by the end of the intervention (*time 2*). The learning output of JOBS-related competencies is measured by performed knowledge, self-assessed knowledge and self-assessed skills.

First, different aspects of the self-concept and of individuals' preferences will be shown (4.2.1), followed by several components of motivation (4.2.2) and beliefs (4.2.3).

4.2.1 Self-concept

Self-concept as a *stable perception* of abilities, describes individuals' perception on their own academic performance and personal identity (Hannover et al., 2005), built up during the whole life. Based on experiences, feedback and the attribution of reasons for success or failing (Heckhausen & Heckhausen, 2007) individuals' self-concept may change very slowly. It is distinctive from self-awareness, as a capacity for introspection and the ability to recognize oneself as an individual separate from the environment and others (Rochat, 2003).

Self-efficacy as a dynamic component of individuals' self-concept or belief system focus on people's beliefs about their capabilities to deal with requirements arising in the future (Bandura, 1977). It emerges from experiences as well, but it stands for a dynamic component of individuals' resources.

Evaluations on self-concept and self-efficacy were gathered in various approaches:

- (1) a general self-concept on learning competencies the self-concept on skills like concentration, persistence, attention and cooperation were evaluated.
- (2) the subject specific academic self-concept) on performance within specific subjects
- (3) in addition, the preferences of the subjects as individuals' preferences.
- (4), self-efficacy in general
- (5) school-related self-efficacy
- (6) social-related self-efficacy.

4.2.1.1 Components of self-concept and their differences between the groups and over time

Self-Competence

Self-competence describes the ability of a student to learn in an effective way, evaluated by the components of concentration, reliability, persistence, cooperation and performance.

Results show a difference between JOBS- and Non-JOBS-students; JOBS-students show higher averages than Non-JOBS-students (see *Figure 5* and *Table 9*), but based on the weak effect.

Fig. 5. Self-competence (Means of JOBS- and Non-JOBS-students)

Tab. 9. Results of the variance analyzes, proving the differences between the groups and over time

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1 – Time 2	
	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANCOVA	J _{GLM}	NJ _{GLM}
Self-competence es	4.64/1.10	4.47/1.10	NJ < J*	4.69/.95	4.48/.98	NJ < J*	n.s.	n.s.
Self-competence t1: $F(1,776) = 4.48, p = .05, \eta^2 = .006$; t2: $F(1,776) = 5.01, p = .05, \eta^2 = .009$								
Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance $p^* < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; \eta^2 =$ Eta square								

JOBS-students seem to dispose of better preconditions to learn at the beginning (*time 1*) as well as at the end of the school year (*time 2*). JOBS-program focus not only on knowledge and skills on professions and career choice but also on fostering learning conditions and competencies to learn. The classes attending the JOBS-program, were not selected by random, but dependent on the initiative of their teachers. It might be, that teachers, interested in participating this program, kept an eye on students' competences to learn, already before the program started.

Academic Self-Concept within specific subjects

To control the possible effect of students' academic self-concept ('I'm good in ...') and the valence ('I like to deal with ...') of specific subjects were evaluated. Academic self-concept refers to the individuals' perception about their academic abilities or skills (Trautwein et al., 2009). The development of academic self-concept starts in the early childhood, influenced by parents and other educators. Entering school, comparisons within peers and feedback of teachers and parents influence the academic self-concept significantly (Freund et al., 2012). Preferences in specific subjects shows the emotional component.

JOBS- and Non-JOBS-students don't differ in their subject specific academic self-concept (see *Figure 6* and *Table 10*) with few exceptions, but due to their very weak effect the differences are not relevant.

Fig. 6. Self-Concept in school subjects (1= I'm bad in ..., 6=I'm very good in ...)

Tab. 10. Subject-specific academic self-concept (between JOBS- and Non-JOBS-students and over time)

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1 – Time 2	
	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANOVA	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANCOVA	J GLM	NJGLM
Mathemat.	3.20/1.37	2.89/1.44	NJ < J*	3.39/1.43	3.23/ 1.47	NJ < J*	n.s.	n.s.
Romanian	4.07/1,03	3.90/1.27	n.s.	4.09/1.12	3.96/1.20	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
German	1.73/1.27	1.84/1.35	n.s.	1.86/1.48	1.99/1.55	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
English	3.45/ 1.47	3.58/ 1.56	n.s.	3.59/1.50	3.68/ 1.47	n.s.	t1 < t2*	n.s.
French	2.72/1.50	2.62/1.57	n.s.	2.87/1.50	2.63/ 1.51	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
History	3.75/1.30	3.70/1.28	n.s.	3.75/1.20	3.86/1.20	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Biology	3.82/1.24	4.00/1.29	n.s.	4.04/1.30	3.91/1.20	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Physics	2.82/1.42	2.95/1.45	n.s.	3.30/1.40	3.08/1.40	n.s.	t1 < t2*	n.s.
Chemistry	3.23/1.49	3.13/1.55	n.s.	3.36/1.50	3.20/1.50	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Music	4.05/1.89	4.24/1.17	n.s.	3.80/2.00	4.17/1.80	J < NJ*	t1 > t2*	n.s.
JOBS	4.84/1.32	-	-	4.94/1.29	-	-	t1 < t2***	

Mathematics t1: $F(1,413) = 4.94, p = .04, \eta^2 = .012$; Music t2: $F(1,436) = 4.02, p = .04, \eta^2 = .009$

Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance $p^* < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; \eta^2 = \text{Eta square}$

Preferences in specific subjects

Figure 7 shows the averages of preferences in specific subjects, differentiated between JOBS and Non-JOBS-students, Table 11 contains the results from comparisons between the two groups and over time.

Results show quite low preferences in Mathematics, higher ones in the languages Romanian and English. Preferences in the subject JOBS are at the beginning of the school year very high, at the end of the year a bit lower, but still high. They stay stable during the year (time 1 and time 2). The large spread of the values (standard deviation) points out big differences between the students. In relation to the evaluated subjects, JOBS-students seem to like JOBS-lessons most.

Comparing the means, no relevant differences between the groups of JOBS- and Non-JOBS-students and related to the development of preferences over time were identified. Related to the preferences in the subject JOBS, JOBS-students' attitudes changes during the year. At the end of the intervention (*time 2*) JOBS-students' preferences are significantly lower than they were at the beginning of the intervention (*time 1*), but still higher than on the other subjects.

Fig. 7. Preference in specific subjects (I like ..., 1= not at all, 6= very much)

Tab. 11. Preference in specific subjects (Results from variance analyzes between the groups and over time)

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1 – Time 2	
	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANCOVA	J _{GLM}	NJ _{GLM}
Mathematics	3.01/1.70	3.10/1.70	n.s.	2.95/1.64	3.01/1.77	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Romanian	3.99/1.43	3.98/1.48	n.s.	4.08/1.41	4.04/1.51	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
German	2.11/1.65	2.36/1.81	n.s.	2.09/1.67	2.26/1.76	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
English	3.93/1.61	4.22/1.70	n.s.	3.96/1.75	4.24/1.70	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
French	2.84/1.64	2.87/1.75	n.s.	2.71/1.70	2.80/1.77	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
History	3.68/1.54	3.86/1.60	n.s.	3.82/1.66	3.79/1.61	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Biology	3.92/1.56	4.00/1.60	n.s.	3.75/1.53	4.18/1.46	J < N ^{***j}	n.s.	n.s.
Physics	3.07/1.59	2.95/1.45	n.s.	2.80/1.56	2.91/1.67	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Chemistry	3.36/1.63	3.11/1.70	n.s.	3.33/1.73	3.21/1.75	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Music	4.00/2.07	4.41/1.85	J > NJ [*]	4.12/1.92	4.38/1.87	n.s.	t1 < t2 ^{**}	n.s.
JOBS	5.17/1.40	-	-	4.70/1.64	-	-	t1 ^{***} > t2	

Music t1: $F(1,436) = 4.65, p = .03, \eta^2 = .010$

Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance $p^* < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; \eta^2$ = Eta square

Self-efficacy

Self-efficacy as the self-concept on own ability to master upcoming requirements was evaluated in three different approaches (Schwarzer & Jerusalem, 2002): Self-efficacy in general tells about this ability in an unspecific way, school-related self-efficacy give an insight in students' concept of their abilities to deal with requirements at school and social-related self-efficacy shows the ability to deal with requirements within social contexts.

Results show similar evaluations concerning own ability to deal with requirements in the three dimensions (see Fig. 8 and Table 12). There are no differences between JOBS- and Non-JOBS-students and over time.

Fig. 8. Self-efficacy in three approaches (1 = low, 6 = high)

Tab. 12. Self-efficacy (Results from variance analyzes between the groups and over time)

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1-Time 2	
	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANOVA	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANOVA	J _{GLM}	NJ _{GLM}
General self-efficacy SE	4.34/1.11	4.31/1.10	n.s.	4.36/.97	4.30/1.04	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
School-related SE	4.43/1.12	4.37/1.09	n.s.	4.42/.96	4.36/1.10	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Social related SE	4.30/1.15	4.25/1.14	n.s.	4.30/ 1.03	4.25/1.07	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.

Note: J = JOBS-students, NJ = Non-JOBS-students, M = mean, SD = standard deviation, level of significance p* < .05, ** < .01, *** < .0011; η² = Eta square

4.2.1.2 Effects of components of self-concept on the learning output of JOBS-program

Effects of self-concept on performed JOBS knowledge

Results in Table 13 show that several components of the *self-concept* and *preferences* at the beginning of the intervention (*time 1*) have significant effects on the amount of knowledge at the end of the intervention by the JOBS program (*time 2*). Still, the explained variance is quite small for all models; less than 10% of students' knowledge can be explained by predictors related to self-concept and preferences at the beginning of the intervention, either in simple or multiple models. Preferences in English at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) show a significant effect (Beta .25**) on the tested knowledge at the end of the year (*time 2*).

Tab. 13. Effects of components of self-concept on learning output of performed knowledge (tested with open questions)

	Time 1					Time 2				
Model	M13 es	M15 fk	M17 fv	M13, 15,17	M21 sw	M13 es	M15 fk	M17 fv	M13, 15,17	M21 sw
Self-competence M13 es	.116*			.022		.358***			.237***	
Self-concept of specific subject M15 fk										
Math		.107		.167			.117*		.162*	
Romanian		.038		.045			.093		.048	
English		-.037		-.167			.071		-.023	
Jobs		.138*		.076			.226***		.173*	
Preferences on subjects M17 fv										
Math			.140	-.084				.029	-.111	
Romanian			.156*	-.030				.075	-.009	
English			.115	.245***				.138*	.059	
Jobs			.195***	.040*				.156**	.006	
Self-efficacy M21 sw										
General SE					-.127					.174
School-related					.253**					.186*
Social-related					.028					-.019
R²	.013	.039	.039	.079	.026	.128	.119	.058	.173	.107
F	4.341*	3.177*	15.59***	3.042***	2.688*	47.92***	10.75***	6.041***	7.065***	12.48***
<i>Note:</i> R ² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: p * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001										

Components of self-concept at the end of the intervention (*time 2*) explain 17% of the knowledge at the end of the year. High self-competences in learning (Beta .24***), high self-concept in Math (Beta .16*) and JOBS (Beta .17*) show significant effects on the emerged knowledge at the end of the year (*time 2*); subject-specific preferences are not significant.

Components of *self-efficacy* at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) explain 3% of the knowledge at the end of the year, high school-related self-efficacy is significant (Beta .25**). Self-efficacy at the end of the year (*time 2*) explain 11% of the learning output, school related self-efficacy is significant as well (Beta .19*).

→ For the effects of JOBS-program this finding shows, that the individual preconditions of *self-concept* and *self-efficacy* do not change during the time the program is running, but they have a low impact on the learning output of the program, evaluated by a knowledge test. Most probably, other factors play a more significant role in prediction the performance of knowledge acquired through JOBS-program, shown in the answers to the open questions.

Effects of self-concept on self-assessed JOB-knowledge

Self-concept, preferences and self-efficacy are significant for the learning output of self-assessed knowledge. All computed regression models are significant (Tab. 14).

Components for *self-concept* and *preferences* at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) explain 23% of the self-assessed knowledge at the end of the year (*time 2*). High self-competences in learning (Beta .29***), Romanian language (Beta .18*) and English (Beta .19*) are significant predictors for the learning output. At the end of the year (*time 2*), components of the self-concept and preferences explain 43% of the

learning output, evaluated as self-assessed knowledge of the students. High self-competencies in learning have a strong effect on the learning output (Beta .44*), a high self-concept in Romanian have a positive but weaker effect (Beta .16**).

Of importance is a high *self-competence in learning* at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) as well as at the end of the year (*time 2*) on the self-assessed knowledge at the end of the year (*time 2*), as a single predictor (M13) or in combination with subject competence (M13, 15) or subject preferences (M13, 15, 17); more than 20% of the self-assessed knowledge at the end of the year (*time 2*) is explained. The effect of the self-concept related to JOBS is quite small as at the beginning of the year (*time 1*), when students knew very little about the program and had no prior experience to the type of learning activities JOBS-program promotes. At the end of the year (*time 2*), self-competence proves to be a significant predictor for self-assessed knowledge, explaining 33% of the variance when tested as a single predictor (M13), and higher when tested in a multiple predictors models (M13, 15, 17). As expected, the self-competence related to JOBS-knowledge is a very strong predictor (M15). More than 41% of students' self-assessed knowledge is explained by their general self-competence and JOBS specific self-concept.

→ Self-competences in learning, subject-specific self-concept and preferences/interests in different subjects are important predictors for high self-assessed knowledge; self-competences in learning show the highest effect.

→ To foster students in their competences to learn is an important task of school in general.

Tab. 14. Effects of components of self-concept on learning outcomes (self-assessed knowledge)

Model	Time 1					Time 2				
	M13 es	M15 fk	M17 fv	M13,15,17	M21 sw	M13 es	M15 fk	M17 fv	M 13,15,17	M21 sw
Self-competence M13 es	.417***			.293***		.580***			.444***	
Self-concept in specific subject M15 fk										
Math		.104		-.035			.158**		.081	
Romanian		.154*		.175*			.149**		.163**	
English		.049		-.066			.209***		.067	
Jobs		.214***		.117			.292***		.105	
Preferences in specific subjects M17 fv										
Math			.117*	.067				.141**	-.006	
Romanian			.093	-.110				.046	-.119*	
English			.152**	.189*				.253**	.054	
Jobs			.134**	.000				.270**	.082	
Self-efficacy M21 sw										
General					.047					.283**
School-related					.187					.255**
Social-related					.185*					.108
R ²	.174	.137	.024	.226	.153	.336	.287	.418	.429	.354
F	65.034*	12.061*	14.709*	8.904**	17.776*	161.518***	31.074*	43.099*	24.748*	55.892***
Note: R ² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: p * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001										

Self-efficacy at the beginning of the intervention (*time 1*) explains 15% of the learning output of knowledge, assessed by the students. At the end of the intervention (*time 2*) it explains 35% of the learning output; general self-efficacy (Beta .28**) and school-related self-efficacy (Beta .26**) show significant effects.

→ Based on the fact, that self-efficacy didn't grow during the intervention, it can be assumed, that students experience their efficacy and abilities by working on the tasks of JOBS-program and by presenting their results. Experience of competence, autonomy and relatedness as basic needs (Deci & Ryan, 1993; Ryan & Deci, 2000), given by JOBS-program, are essential for students' ability to *recognize* their knowledge.

Effects of self-concept on JOBS skills (self-assessed)

Regarding the effects of different components of the self-concept (*time 1*) on self-assessed skills, at the end of the year (*time 2*), all tested regression models are significant, with self-competence of learning as a strong predictor, either as a single predictor (M13 Beta .51***) or in combination with subject-related competence (M15) and subject-related interest (M17) (Beta .40***) (see *Table 15*).

At the end of the year (*time 2*), the same pattern is found. Self-competence is a very strong predictor (M13, Beta .71***) and explains 51% of the learning output. Testing subject-related self-concept, JOBS-related self-concept is the strongest single predictor (Beta .37***), followed by the other subjects of English, Romanian and Math; they explain 41% of the skills.

The explained variance of several models is very high, especially for the combined sets of predictors: self-competence, subject-related self-concept and preferences explaining 62% of the variance of the skills at the end of the intervention.

Tab. 15. Effects of self-concept on the learning output (measured as self-assessed skills)

Model	Time 1					Time 2				
	M13 es	M15 fk	M17 fv	M 13, 15,17	M21 sw	M13 es	M15 fk	M17 fv	M 13, 15,17	M21 sw
Self-competence M13 es	.505***			.399***		.713**			.545***	
Self-concept of specific subject M15 fk										
Math		.140		.013			.173***		.051	
Romanian		.156*		.165*			.199***		.200***	
English		.115		.013			.210***		.012	
JOBS		.195***		.076			.365***		.081	
Preferences in specific subjects M17 fv										
Math			.127*	.068				.162***	.003	
Romanian			.123*	.104				.100**	-.089	
English			.173**	.118				.288***	.108	
JOBS			.140**	.015				.338***	.160**	
Self-efficacy M21 sw										
General					.095					.403***
School-related					.373					.225**
Social-related					.271					.137**
R ²	.255	.175	.130	.301	.432	.508	.406	.329	.627	.502
F	101.99***	15.585***	12.700***	12.737***	4.816*	320.21***	51.284***	36.970***	53.950***	101.17***
<i>Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: p * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001</i>										

Self-efficacy at the beginning (*time 1*) and at the end of the year (*time 2*) explains 50% of the variance of the learning output of skills, worked on during the JOBS intervention.

Summary on the three approaches of the learning output

Self-efficacy has a significant effect on the learning output, evaluated as knowledge, as self-assessed knowledge and as self-assessed skills, at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) and at the end of it (*time 2*). For the JOBS-students, self-efficacy explains only 2% of the variance of knowledge (*time 1*), 15% of the variance of self-assessment of knowledge (*time 1*) and 35% at the end of the year (*time 2*), and more than 50% of the variance of self-assessed skills in both time 1 and time 2.

→ Self-efficacy is important to recognize own abilities.

4.2.2 Motives

Motivation is defined as the process that initiates, guides, and maintains goal-oriented behaviors. Motivation is what causes us to act to fulfill basic needs (Ryan & Deci, 2000). Motives are relevant to reach goals or to avoid specific situations. So, push and pull factors can drive to act. Intrinsic and extrinsic components influence motivation.

To assess dynamic components that may have an influence on the learning output of JOBS-program, motivation is investigated by several approaches: The importance of learning in general and its influence on future possibilities (1) may drive students to deal with task of the JOBS program. Motives for learning at school (2) focus on interests to learn, on the desire of social approval or on the motive to avoid or minimalize requirements and stress.

4.2.2.1 Components of motives and their differences between the groups and over time

Importance of learning for school and for future

Fig. 9. Importance of learning for school and for future (from 1 = low to 6 =high)

JOBS- and Non-JOBS-students evaluate the learning for school and for the future as very important – a good precondition to engage oneself to work on tasks seriously. There are no differences between the two groups of students and no significant development over time (Fig. 9 and Tab. 16).

The lower means in time 2 for both JOBS and Non-JOBS students could be explained by the fact that at the end of the school year the students' answers might have been contextual.

Tab. 16. Importance of learning for school and for future (differences between the groups and over time)

Importance	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1 – Time 2	
	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANOVA	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANOVA	J GLM	NJ GLM
For school	5.02/1.12	5.07/1.22	n.s.	4.84/1.17	4.95/1.17	n.s.	t1 > t2**	n.s.
For future	5.55/.87	5.49/.96	n.s.	5.41/.96	5.51/.86	n.s.	t1 > t2**	n.s.

JOBS: Importance of learning for school: $F(1,335) = 11.423$, $p = .001$, $\eta^2 = .033$; Importance of learning for future: $F(1,335) = 9.032$, $p = .003$, $\eta^2 = .026$

Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance $p^* < .05$, $** < .01$, $*** < .001$; η^2 = Eta square

Interest to learn about professional world and about own strength

Fig. 10. Interests on goals of the JOBS-program (1=low, 6 = high)

JOBS-students show higher interests to learn about professions and about own strength than Non-JOBS-students. During the year of the intervention, JOBS-students' interests to learn about their own strength decreases.

Tab. 17. Interests in learning about professions and own strength

Interests	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1 – Time 2	
	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANOVA	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANCOVA	JOBS _{GLM}	NJ _{GLM}
Professions	4.47/1.63	4.06/1.75	J>NJ***	4.41/1.50	4.08/1.71	J > NJ**	n.s.	n.s.
Individ.strength	5.47/.099	5.43/ 1.1	n.s.	4.95/1.21	5.39/1.05	J<NJ***	t1 > t2***	n.s.

F professions t1: $F(1, 335) = 14.202$, $p = .001$, $\eta^2 = .041$; professions t2: $F(1, 413) = 5.237$, $p = .003$, $\eta^2 = .016$; individual strength t2: $F(1, 413) = 31.448$, $p = .001$, $\eta^2 = .031$

Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance $p^* < .05$, $** < .01$, $*** < .001$; η^2 = Eta square

Motivation for learning in school

This instrument (see Keller-Schneider, 2013) is based on the theory of learning and achievement of Elliot (1999) with dimension of approach and avoidance. The data of this study didn't allow to differentiate between avoidance of learning and avoidance of achievement; these dimensions are joint in the scale of avoidance of learning and achievement. The questions on achievement point out the social benefit of achievements, so this scale is called social approval of achievement.

The motivation for learning at school shows quite high averages (*Fig. 11*) in learning orientation as well as in the motivation for social approval of achievement and on avoidance of learning and achievement. The quite large spread point out individual differences. There are no differences between JOBS and Non-JOBS-groups and their development over time (*Tab. 18*).

Fig. 11. Motivation for learning in school (from 1 = low to 6= high)

→ The JOBS-interventions program has no effect on students' learning motivation in school. Students of the intervention and of control-group don't differ, neither at the beginning of the school-year (*time 1*) nor at the end of it (*time 2*). Even the JOBS-program fosters the students in their knowledge and skills on professions and individual strength, it has no effect on the underlying motivation to learn in school.

Tab. 18. Motivation for learning in school

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1 – Time 2	
	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{GLM}	NJ _{GLM}
Learning	3.80/ .96	3.69/ .95	n.s.	3.70/ .86	3.69/ .92	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Social approval	3.48/ 1.00	3.49/ .94	n.s.	3.45/ .92	3.45/ .90	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Avoidance	3.33/ .93	3.34/ .98	n.s.	3.22/ .95	3.23/ .94	n.s.	n.s.	t1>*t2

Note: J = JOBS-students, NJ = Non-JOBS-students, M = mean, SD = standard deviation, level of significance p* < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; η² = Eta square

Work Motives

Motives to fulfill basic need by work show quite high averages (*Fig. 12*) with large inter-individual differences (*Tab. 19*). There are small but significant differences between the two groups. But because of the low effects, the differences are not relevant.

Fig. 12. Work motive (from 1= low to 6=high)

→ Even JOBS-program has effects on the learning output concerning knowledge and skills on professions and individual strength and preferences, it doesn't influence the deeper motivation of goals through affiliate in work. JOBS- and Non-JOBS-students don't differ in their motivation as expectations on work.

Tab. 19. Work motives: Differences between JOBS- and Non-JOBS groups and over time

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1–Time 2	
	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANCOVA	J _{GLM}	NJ _{GLM}
Autonomy	4.66/1.08	4.47/1.09	NJ < J*	4.57/ .96	4.42/1.00	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Relatedness	4.68/1.12	4.50/1.11	NJ < J*	4.57/1.04	4.51/1.04	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Challenge	4.38/1.00	4.25/1.11	n.s.	4.27/ .93	4.19/1.00	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Meaningfulness	4.82/1.03	4.72/1.08	n.s.	4.75/ .95	4.71/1.02	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Autonomy t1: $F(1,761) = 5.29, p = .02, \eta^2 = .006$; Relatedness t1: $F(1,761) = 4.90, p = .02, \eta^2 = .007$								
<i>Note:</i> J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance $p^* < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; \eta^2 =$ Eta square								

4.2.2.2 Effects of motives on the learning output of JOBS-students

Effects of motives on the performed knowledge

Tab. 20. Effects of motives on learning outcome: performed knowledge

Model	Time 1					Time 2				
	M7 imp	M10 int	M11 mo	M12 wi	M11, 12	M7 imp	M10 int	M11 mo	M12 wi	M11, 12
Importance of learning M7 re										
school	.169**					.268***				
future	-.009					.103				
Interest in professions and in own strengths M10 ev										
professions		.133*				.148**				
strength		.083				.218***				
Learning motives M11 mo										
Learning			.211***		.245**			.317***		.230**
Social approval			.032		.040			.008		.010
Avoidance			-.152		-.128			-.223***		-.200**
Work motives M12 wi										
Autonomy				.030	.085				.225**	.203
Relatedness				.099	.012				.111	.069
Challenge					-.227**				-.266**	
Meaningfulness				.232*	.169				.228**	.181
R²	.027	.032	.054	.058	.102	.109	.104	.115	.144	.198
F	4.703*	5.549***	5.99***	4.55***	4.61***	20.33***	19.32***	13.65***	12.96***	10.35***

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance p * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

Even though all models are significant, the explained variance of motives at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) is very low ($\approx 10\%$). Proving the effects (*Tab. 20*) of all motives at the beginning on the intervention (*time 1*) on the knowledge at the end of the year (*time 2*), learning orientation shows a high effect (Beta .25**). The work motive of having a challenging work effects the performed knowledge at the end of the year negative (Beta -.30**). It might be that the questions on the knowledge, acquired during the JOBS-program, were not perceived as challenging.

Effects of motives at the end of the year (*time 2*) explain 20% of the variance of performed knowledge, showing a similar pattern. Learning motivation shows a strong effect on the learning output (Beta .23**), avoidance orientation a negative on (Beta -.20**) and the desire to have a challenging work contributes with a negative effect (Beta -.26**).

→ Several components of motivation to drive someone's acting have all in all a small effect on knowledge performance, tested by open question asking for written answers. If students are not used to answer open questions by telling everything they know about, or if their motivation does not fit to the task they should fulfill, is not clear.

Effects of motives on self-assessed JOBS knowledge

Table 21 contains the results of the regressions analyzes of motives as predictors of the self-assessed knowledge at the end of the intervention by JOBS-program.

Importance of learning for school and for future (M7) at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) explains only a small percentage (4%) of the self-assessed knowledge at the end of the year (*time 2*); the effect of learning for school is significant (Beta t1 .22**). At the end of the year (*time 2*) the explained variance is higher (22%) with a strong effect of the importance of learning for school (Beta .41***). In students' perception learning for school drives the learning output of JOBS-knowledge, but the effect of learning for future is not significant.

Interests in professions and *in own strengths* at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) as well as at the end of the year (*time 2*) are significant predictors of self-assessed JOBS knowledge (M10). They explain with 13% and 39% a significant part of the JOBS-knowledge at the end of the intervention.

Motives for learning at school (M11) at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) predict 14% of the learning output at the end of the year (*time 2*), the effects of learning motivation at the end of the year (*time 2*) explain 25%. In both times, motivation for learning is the strongest predictor (Beta t1 .36***, Beta t2 .46***).

Motives for work during occupational career (M12) at the beginning of the intervention (*time 1*) explain 19%, at the end of the intervention (*time 2*) 32% of the emerged knowledge at the end of the program. Autonomy is the strongest predictor (Beta t1 .22*, t2 .25**), in addition at the end of the program the motive of relatedness shows a significant effect (Beta t2 .19**) as well.

Tab. 21. Effects of motives on knowledge as a learning output (self-assessed knowledge)

Model	Time 1					Time 2				
	M7 imp	M10 int	M11 mo	M12 wi	M11, 12	M7 imp	M10 int	M11 mo	M12 wi	M11, 12
Importance of learning M7 re										
school	.216***					.404***				
future	.001					.108				
Interest in professions and in own strengths M10 ev										
professions		.194***					.300***			
strength		.253***					.410***			
Learning motives M11 mo										
Learning			.363***		.241**			.459***		.276***
Social approval			.054		-.038			.092		.068
Avoidance			-.074		-.115			-.037		-.100
Work motives M12 wi										
Autonomy				.177	.217*				.253**	.236**
Relatedness				.075	.014				.194**	.108
Challenge				.083	.053				.102	.033
Meaningfulness				.152	.103				.093	.053
R²	.047	.136	.142	.186	.229	.217	.389	.249	.318	.360
F	7.911***	23.32***	17.06***	16.55***	11.69***	44.67***	103.0***	34.07***	35.15***	23.16***
<i>Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance p * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001</i>										

In the combined model the explained variance is higher (t1 23%, t2 36%). Both components on motivation contributes to the self-assessed learning output of JOBS-knowledge by the end of the intervention.

→ Considering that the models have higher explained variance at the end of the intervention (*time 2*) than at the beginning of it (*time 1*), on behalf of students' perspective, the relations between motivation and success are stronger. Students experience on an unconscious level, that their motivation and their success in building up JOBS-knowledge are related.

Effects of motives on JOBS skills (self-assessed)

Motives (Table 22) at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) explain a small part of the learning output, measured as skills focused on during the JOBS program. *Importance to learn* (M7) and *interests about professions and own strength* (M10) explain less than 16% of the variance of the skills at the end of the intervention. At the end of the year (*time 2*) their impact is much stronger, importance to learn and interest to learn on professions and own strength explain 31% or 39% of the JOBS-skills by the end of the year.

The effects of *motivation to learn at school* and *to learn for future* as predictors from the beginning of the year (*time 1*) explain a variance of about 25% and 22%. In the combined model the explained variance is higher (29%) with the strongest positive effects of the learning motivation (Beta .29***). At the end of the year the explained variance of 39% and 53% is higher, combined in one model, the explained variance is even higher (58%), with significant effects of the learning orientation motive and the work motive of experiencing autonomy and meaningfulness.

Tab. 22. Effects of motives on learning outcome (measured as self-assessment of acquired skills)

Model	Time 1					Time 2				
	M7 imp	M10 int	M11 mo	M12 wi	M11, 12	M7 imp	M10 int	M11 mo	M12 wi	M11, 12
Importance of learning M7 re										
school	.330***					.462***				
future	.014					.164***				
Interest in professions and in own strengths M10 ev										
professions		.164**					.291***			
strength		.305***					.418***			
Learning motives M11 mo										
Learning			.147***		.290***			.547***		.290***
Social approval			.167*		.073			.144*		.100
Avoidance			.098		-.112			-.032		-.056
Work motives M12 wi										
Autonomy				.081	.122				.252***	.233**
Relatedness				.188*	.083				.256***	.160**
Challenge				.160*	.083				.120**	.028
Meaningfulness				.116	.046				.196**	.151*
R²	.113	.158	.247	.224	.288	.314	.389	.386	.527	.579
F	19.81***	29.27***	32.49***	20.25***	15.45***	70.91***	99.15***	62.84***	81.46***	55.12***

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance p* < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

→ Students' motivation with focus on the dynamic components of work motivation to fulfill basic needs, such as challenge, autonomy, relatedness and meaningfulness is significant for their learning output of JOBS skills.

→ Motivation at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) is an important predictor, but the influence on the learning output at the end of the year, measured by experienced skills, grows through the year, attending JOBS program. At the end of the year (*time 2*) the impact of different characteristics of motivation on the learning output is higher.

→ Even the motivation doesn't grow within the year, the effects of motivation are stronger at the end of the year. JOBS-students experience the interaction between motivation and learning output (skills) and their motivation as a predictor of success.

Summary on motives

→ Motives are important predictors for the learning output of the students. Its' explained variance changes, depending on the way the learning output is measured and on the time of measurement.

→ Effects on self-assessed skills explain the largest part of the learning output, effects on self-assessed knowledge is lower; the lowest one is the one on the performed knowledge. Effects over time (*time 1 and time 2*) are lower than effects at the same time. Motives do not change through the JOBS-program, but they effect students' sense of competence.

4.2.3 Beliefs on learning and achievement

Beliefs can be described as individuals' reference frame to understand situations and the likelihood of processes, referring to the past and to the future. Concepts of beliefs of a person contains assumptions on facts and conditions as true, according to individuals' logic as a belief system. As a part of individuals' identity, they are based on factual knowledge as well as on affective ones.

But beliefs as well may persist independent of facts. Acquisition of knowledge may effect a slow change of beliefs, but if specific knowledge of skills expected to acquire do not fit within individuals' belief system, the requirement to deal with it will be refused, avoided or denied (see model of development in *Figure 1*). To foster students' internalization of acquired knowledge, experiencing factual knowledge is essential (Keller-Schneider, 2014, 2016), like the JOBS-program aims to. Individuals' beliefs as well as goals and interests, influence their learning output (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002; Pintrich, 2003; Weiner, 1992).

4.2.3.1 Beliefs on learning and achievement and differences between the groups and over time

Beliefs on transmissive and constructivist teaching and learning styles

Beliefs on teaching and learning can be categorized in two dimensions: With focus on a clear and effective instruction, *transmissive* beliefs of teaching and learning emphasize on teachers' role to make students understand, what they should learn. *Constructivist* orientations focus on students' thinking and understanding of facts and their relatedness to other facts, building up synergies of a deep understanding. The interplay and the intensity of these two dimensions leads to different profiles of beliefs on teaching and learning, representing individuals' judgment on the assumption of 'what works'.

Fig. 13. Beliefs of students on teaching and learning (from 1= low to 6=high)

Beliefs on teaching and learning of JOBS- and Non-JOBS-students show high values in both dimensions (*Fig. 13*). JOBS- and Non-JOBS-students don't differ in their beliefs on teaching and learning as well as they don't change over time (*Tab. 23*). JOBS-program has no effect on JOBS-students' beliefs on the effects of transmissive and constructivist teaching and learning styles.

→ JOBS-program has no effect on students' beliefs on teaching and learning. Even they experience a constructivist approach during a program on three lessons weekly, their belief-system will not change through this experience.

Tab. 23. Beliefs on teaching and learning, differences between JOBS- and Non-JOBS groups and over time

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1–Time 2	
	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANOVA	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANOVA	J _{GLM}	NJ _{GLM}
Constructivist	4.67/ 1.02	4.46/ 1.05	n.s.	4.69/ .93	4.68/.90	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Transmissive	4.58/ .95	4.54/ 1.01	n.s.	4.45/.95	4.51/ .94	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.

Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation

Beliefs on reference norms of performed achievement

Achievement can be measured related to different norms. In the past, rates on achievement emerged from the comparison of an individual achievement with the average of the class as reference norm. In our days, this approach to evaluate students' achievement is not appropriate to foster their learning and achievement, independent on the achievement level of the surrounding. To reach a more objective judgment on the achievement of a student, the importance of the task-based criteria-oriented norm grew. But to foster students and to recognize their progress, individual oriented norm is important as well (Rheinberg, 2006).

Individuals' belief (of students and of teachers, see 5.2.3.1) on the reference-norm to evaluate achievement may rely on all the three dimensions and have an effect on students' learning and achievement (Dickhäuser & Rheinberg, 2003). To assess students' belief on what a good achievement relies on, focus on the three dimensions and asks about their opinion on measurements of achievement (Schöne et al., 2004).

Results on students' belief on reference norm of achievement are shown in *Fig. 14*, differences between the two groups and their development during the period JOBS-program is running in *Tab. 24*.

The averages show (*Fig. 14*), that students' beliefs rely on all three dimension of reference norm for achievement. In their perspective, a good achievement is characterized by a comparison with their own ones, with the criteria of the tasks as well in comparison with their peer.

For JOBS-students the reference of social oriented norm to compare own achievement with the achievement of the others decrease during the year. Concerning the other norms, there are no significant differences over time and between JOBS and Non-JOBS-students (*Tab.24*).

Fig. 14. Orientation towards different reference norm of performed achievement (1=low, 4 = high)

Tab. 24. Beliefs on norms as references of performed achievement

Norm	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1 – Time 2	
	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{GLM}	NJ _{GLM}
Individ. oriented	3.22/ .76	3.18/ .75	n.s.	3.32/ .58	3.31/ .61	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Social oriented	3.22/ .59	3.18/ .76	n.s.	3.10/ .79	3.18/ .75	n.s.	t1 > t2***	n.s.
Task oriented	3.48/ .59	3.38/ .75	n.s.	3.43/ .57	3.40/ .72	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.

Social oriented norm JOBS: $F(1,329) = 8.874, p = .003, \eta^2 = .026$;

Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance $p^* < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; \eta^2 = \text{Eta square}$

4.2.3.2 Effects of students' beliefs on learning and achievement on students' learning output

Effects of students' beliefs on learning and achievement on performed JOBS-knowledge

Tab. 25. Effects of beliefs on learning and achievement on the learning output (performed JOBS-knowledge)

Model	Time 1			Time 2		
	M8 ltu	M9 nor	M8,9	M8 ltu	M9 nor	M8,9
Beliefs on teaching and learning M8 ltu						
Constructivist	.130		.005	.270**		.162
Transmissive	.013		.009	.045		.013
Beliefs on norms as references of performed achievement M9 nor						
Individual oriented norm		.239***	.257***		.192**	.133
Social oriented norm		.017	.000		-.014	-.031
Task oriented norm		-.003	.013		.148*	.133
R²	.020	.060	.074	.093	.094	.126
F	3.069**	6.729***	4.629***	16.314***	11.331***	8.932***

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance $p^* < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001$

Beliefs on teaching and learning and on norms of performed achievement contribute to the learning output, measured as performed knowledge (Tab. 25). Less than 10% of the variance of performed knowledge can be explained by beliefs about learning and performance. Again, knowledge measured in an objective manner, shows independency of individual characteristics.

Effects of students' beliefs on learning and achievement on self-assessed JOBS-knowledge

Students' beliefs about learning and achievement have significant effects on self-assessed knowledge in both times (Tab. 26); Beliefs on teaching and learning at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) explain about 13% to 15% of the learning output, beliefs at the end of the year (*time 2*) about 30% respectively 37%. Beliefs on achievement, recognized based on different norms, contribute to the self-assessed knowledge at the end of the year with an explained variance of 10% at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) and 30% at the end of the year (*time 2*). Individual oriented and task oriented norms show significant effects.

Tab. 26. Effects of beliefs on learning and achievement on the learning output (self-assessed JOBS knowledge)

Model	Time 1			Time 2		
	M8 ltu	M9 nor	M8,9	M8 ltu	M9 nor	M8,9
Beliefs on teaching and learning M8 ltu						
Constructivist	.313 ^{***}		.245 ^{**}	.480 ^{***}		.317 ^{***}
Transmissive	.067		.068	.298 ^{***}		.000
Beliefs on norms as references of performed achievement M9 nor						
Individual oriented norm		.203 ^{**}	.137		.334 ^{***}	.193 ^{**}
Social oriented norm		-.019	-.059		-.038	-.049
Task oriented norm		.170 ^{**}	.074		.279 ^{***}	.237 ^{***}
R²	.132	.100	.166	.268	.301	.369
F	22.698 ^{***}	11.411 ^{***}	11.169 ^{***}	57.259 ^{***}	45.878 ^{***}	35.681 ^{***}

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: p * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

→ From all the beliefs-related predictors, constructivist beliefs about teaching and learning have the strongest positive effect in both times as well as in the simple (M8 Beta t1 .31^{***}, t2 .48^{***}) and in the combined models (M8,9, Beta t1 .25^{***}, t2 .32^{***}).

→ Individual oriented and task-oriented norms effect the learning output in a positive and significant way as well and contributes to the learning output.

Effects of students' beliefs on learning and achievement on self-assessed JOBS-skills

Tab. 27. Effects of beliefs on learning and achievement on the learning output (self-assessed JOBS skills), differences between JOBS- and Non-JOBS groups and over time

Model	Time 1			Time 2		
	M8 Ltu	M9 nor	M8,9	M8 Ltu	M9 nor	M8,9
Beliefs on teaching and learning M8 Ltu						
Constructivist	.412 ^{***}		.267 ^{***}	.618 ^{***}		.433 ^{***}
Transmissive	.048		.054	.040		-.026
Beliefs on norms as references of performed achievement M9 nor						
Individual oriented norm		.246 ^{***}	.164 [*]		.384 ^{***}	.220 ^{***}
Social Oriented		.091	.061		.099 [*]	.070
Task based norm		.142 [*]	.045		.254 ^{***}	.186 ^{***}
R²	.199	.156	.229	.420	.404	.525
F	35.700 ^{***}	18.444 ^{***}	16.201 ^{***}	110.505 ^{***}	69.621 ^{***}	65.648 ^{***}

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: p * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

Students' beliefs about learning and achievement predict students' self-assessed skills (*Tab. 27*) with an explained variance of 23% at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) and 53% at the end of the year (*time 2*). Constructivist beliefs has the strongest positive effects (M8 Beta t1 .41***; t2 .62***) on the learning output as skills. Beliefs on reference norm of achievement, individual and task oriented norm contribute significantly to the learning output (explained variance time 1 16%, time 2 40%).

Summary of results of beliefs

→ Beliefs contribute to the self-assessed learning output of JOBS learning-activities. The explained variance of the performed knowledge is lower than the ones based on self-assessment of knowledge and skills. Beliefs shape individuals' perception on learning output.

→ Even the mean of the beliefs didn't change during the year of the intervention, they influence the learning output, especially the self-assessed knowledge and skills. The explained variance at the end of the year is bigger than at the beginning of it. Students' beliefs are more related to their learning output.

→ Beliefs fitting to the didactic approach of JOBS, such as constructivist beliefs on teaching and learning and such as individual oriented reference frame for achievement, contribute with strong effects; beliefs that does not fit, do not restrain the learning.

4.2.4 Effects of individual characteristics as resources for a high learning output during JOBS-program

According the theoretical approach, that individuals' perception based on individual characteristics as resources, shapes the intensity of dealing with requirements (see explanations chapter 1 and *Fig. 1*) we prove the effects of self-concept, motives and beliefs in combined models on the performed JOBS-knowledge, on the self-assessed knowledge and the self-assessed skills (*Tab. 28*).

Individual characteristics all in all contribute with 26% (*time 1*) and 32% (*time 2*) to the *performed JOBS-knowledge* at the end of the intervention. Of special interest is, that in relation to the investigated factors, the motive to have a challenging job in the future has a negative effect on the performed JOBS-knowledge, captured with open questions on JOBS-knowledge.

→ It seems, that this kind of knowledge test in school didn't challenge students who like to be challenged in life.

Individual characteristics influence the amount of *self-assessed knowledge and skills*, both, at the beginning (*time 1*) and at the end (*time 2*) of the intervention. The explained variance at the end of the year is higher, even they didn't change their motives and beliefs over the time of JOBS-intervention program.

→ Upon students' perception their beliefs and motives, fitting to the didactic approach of JOBS-program, rely stronger on the learning output at the end of the year. It seems that they feel more competent to reach goals and to contribute to their learning output on their own.

Tab. 28. Effects of self-concept, motives and beliefs on the learning output as performed JOBS-knowledge

Effects on	Performed knowledge t1	Performed knowledge t2	Knowledge self-ass. t1	Knowledge self-ass. t2	Skills self-assessed t1	Skills self-assessed t2
Self-concept						
self-competence M13 es	.013	.074	.131	.138	.195	.219***
Self-concept subject competence M15 fk						
In Math	.106	.169*	-.042	.088	.015	.038
In Romanian	-.027	-.030	.127	.136*	.081	.168***
In English	-.0162	-.045	-.051	.059	.086	-.011
In Jobs	.097	.181*	.063	.061	-.017	.097
Self-concept subject interest M17 fv						
In Math	-.143	-.127	.020	-.021	-.032	.005
In Romanian	-.032	-.023	-.135	-.178**	-.129	-.124**
In English	.196	.043	.146	-.009	.056	.048
In Jobs	.114	-.095	-.008	-.017	.018	.006
Self-efficacy M21 sw						
General	-.150	.220	.043	.105	.171	.162**
School-related	.099	-.074	.152	-.090	-.120	-.106
Social-related	-.103	-.016	-.118	.030	-.102	-.006
Motives						
Importance of learning M7 re01, 04						
for school	.079	.117	-.060	.013	.046	.010
for future	-.085	-.035	-.175**	-.059	-.103	-.042
Interest in working world/ Interest in own strengths M10 ev02,03						
on professions	.055	.094	.055	.215***	.003	.170***
on indiv. strength	-.076	.143	.177*	.198**	.048	.087
Learning motives M11 mo						
Learning	.269**	.079	.137	.104	.290**	.102
Social approval	.022	-.010	.009	.050	-.004	.047
Avoidance	-.112	-.160*	-.069	-.007	-.013	.037
Work motives M12 wi						
Autonomy	.001	.098	.162	.054	.024	.055
Relatedness	.001	-.029	-.023	.039	.002	.085
Challenge	-.294**	-.345***	-.055	-.057	.017	-.050
Meaningfulness	.216	.088	.035	-.036	.014	.004
Beliefs						
Beliefs on teaching and learning M8 ltu						
Constructivist	-.061	-.030	-.029	.077	.033	.097
Transmissive	.150	.098	.138	.011	.114	-.056
Reference norm of achievement M9 nor						
Individual oriented	.271**	-.033	.007	.114	.029	.112*
Social oriented	-.021	-.007	-.019	-.083	.044	.032
Task oriented	-.095	.082	-.012	.055	-.051	.078
R ²	.256	.318	.324	.571	.363	.772
F	2.464***	3.892***	3.292***	10.868***	3.786***	27.206***
<i>Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: p * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001</i>						

4.3 Family and school context as resources for the learning output

4.3.1 Characteristics of family context

4.3.1.1 Family composition

The participants were asked to specify how many members of their family are living with them and who these people are. The results are summarized in *Tab. 29*, for both groups JOBS and Non-JOBS.

Tab. 29. The present and numbers of family members, split into the groups of JOBS/Non-JOBS students

	JOBS		Non-JOBS	
	quantity	percent	quantity	percent
without father	52	15.2	48	14.2
without mother	21	6.2	37	9.4
with grandfather	53	15.5	47	13.9
with grandmother	85	24.9	87	25.7
another person	25	7.3	18	5.3
siblings 1	114	33.4	115	34
2	78	22.9	62	18.3
3	30	8.8	27	8
4	8	2.3	18	5.3
5	9	2.6	12	3.6
6 to 11	10	3	12	3.6
family total 1	1	0.3	3	0.9
2	15	4.4	20	5.9
3	81	23.8	75	22.2
4	111	32.6	111	32.8
5	64	18.8	55	16.3
6	25	7.3	26	7.7
7 to 12	28	8.2	34	10.1

The sample groups of JOBS and Non-JOBS neither differ in terms of family composition nor in terms of family size and number of siblings.

→ There are no contextual differences between the intervention and the control-group. So, the composition of the families does not influence the learning output of JOBS-students.

4.3.1.2 Family background: parental education, profession and occupation

Results on the students' information on their parents' level of education (*Tab. 30* and *Fig. 15*), profession (*Tab. 31*) and occupation (*Tab. 32*) are shown in the following tables.

Parents' Education

Tab. 30. Parents education, split into the categories JOBS/NON-JOBS

Level of education	JOBS		Non-JOBS	
	quantity	percent	quantity	percent
gymnasium	97	28.3	164	25.4
vocational school	33	9.6	70	10.9
high school	179	52.2	341	52.9
college	2	.6	2	.3
post university education	9	2.6	33	5.1
I don't know	23	6.7	35	5.4
Distribution of parents' education: Chi2 after Pearson (1, N=988)= 5.344, p= .375				

Fig. 15. Level of parents' education for students in JOBS and Non-JOBS classes

In both groups, parents' education is finished at a high school level (about 50%), followed by the gymnasium (about 28%) and the vocational school (about 10%). College and post university studies are rarely. There are no differences concerning the distribution on the education between the parents of JOBS- and Non-JOBS students.

Parents' professions

Tab. 31. Parents profession in time 1 and time 2, split into categories JOBS/Non-JOBS

Profession	JOBS time 1		JOBS time 2		Non-JOBS time 1		Non-JOBS time 2	
	number	percent	number	percent	number	percent	number	percent
father								
agriculture	16	6.0	9	3.0	13	4.7	9	1.6
industry	187	69.8	160	52.6	193	69.9	299	52.4
services	51	19.0	35	11.5	48	17.4	82	14.4
knowledge (research, IT)	1	.4	0	0	2	.7	2	.4
State administration	9	3.4	9	3.0	14	5.1	23	4.0
I don't know	4	1.5	91	29.9	6	2.2	156	27.3
mother								
agriculture	4	1.8	3	1.1	1	.5	8	1.6
industry	62	28.6	47	17.4	61	28.9	83	16.1
services	145	66.8	112	41.5	139	65.9	219	42.5
knowledge (research, IT)	1	.5	0	0	1	.5	3	.6
State administration	5	2.3	0	0	2	.9	3	.6
I don't know	4	1.8	108	40.0	7	3.3	199	38.6
Occupation father: time 1, $\chi^2 = (1, N = 544) = 2.199, p = .821$, time 2, $(1, N = 875) = 5.217, p = .390$								
Occupation mother: time 1, $\chi^2 = (1, N = 428) = 4.185, p = .523$; time 2, $\chi^2(1, N = 785) = 3.701, p = .593$.								

Most of the professions of fathers correspond to industry domain (70%) followed by service domain (19%), while those of mothers are in services domain (67%), followed by the industry domains (29%). There are no significant differences concerning the distribution on the professions between the parents of JOBS and Non-JOBS students.

→ Of specific interest is the finding on the percentage of the respondents, declaring, that they do not know the profession of their parents: The part of students in both groups at the end of the year (*time 2*), who don't know, is much higher than at the beginning of the year (*time 1*). It could be, that students realize the profession is not very easy to identify, that is more to it that just a job and they were not so sure any more if they know their parents' profession correctly.

→ The acquired knowledge enlarges their sensitivity toward professions, but JOBS-program emphasize on understanding professions and its requirements more than on categorizing them according to a system.

Parents' occupation

As *Tab. 32* shows, more than three quarters of fathers have an occupation in an execution position, while around half of the mothers have such a position. One quarters of mothers are housewife. Management position or self-employment is reported by around five percent of the students, for both fathers and mothers.

Tab. 32. Parents occupation in time 1 and time 2, split into categories JOBS/Non-JOBS

	JOBS time 1		JOBS time 2		Non-JOBS time 1		Non-JOBS time 2	
	number	percent	number	percent	number	percent	number	percent
Father								
employee- execution function	256	79.3	218	69.9	281	81.4	445	74.4
employee- management function	12	3.7	16	5.1	13	3.8	23	3.8
employee- support function	0	0	2	.6	0	0	0	0
self employed	20	6.2	14	4.5	19	5.5	14	2.3
unemployed	25	7.1	16	5.1	25	7.2	29	4.8
socially assisted	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
pensioner	8	2.5	4	1.3	5	1.4	13	2.2
without occupation	2	.6	3	1.0	2	.6	6	1.0
pupil, student	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
I don't know	2	.6	39	12.5	0	0	68	11.4
Mother								
employee- execution function	188	55.1	169	52.6	186	53.4	314	53.1
employee- management function	19	5.6	10	3.1	19	5.5	31	5.2
employee- support function	14	4.1	18	5.6	10	2.9	14	2.4
self employed	2	.6	0	0	1	.3	0	0
unemployed	5	1.5	4	1.2	3	.9	7	1.2
socially assisted	4	1.2	1	.3	4	1.1	1	.2
housewife	81	23.8	84	26.2	104	29.9	138	23.4
pensioner	4	1.2	6	1.9	2	.6	9	1.5
without occupation	21	6.2	4	1.2	12	3.4	3	.5
pupil, student	1	.3	0	0	5	1.4	1	.2
I don't know	2	.6	25	7.8	2	.6	73	12.4
Fathers: time 1, $\chi^2=$ time 1 (1, N= 668)= 3.550, p= .830; time 2, $\chi^2=$ 2 (1, N= 910)= 9.881, p= .273								
Mothers: time 1, $\chi^2=$ (1, N= 689)= 10.088, p= .433, time 2, χ^2 (1, N= 912)= 15.409, p= .080								

Distribution according to parents' occupation: The intervention and the control groups do not differ in the distribution according to parents' occupation.

4.3.1.3 Support and expectations

Parental support

Family context is not limited on the composition of the family or their background concerning education, occupation and profession. Of similar importance is how students perceive the support they get from their parents. The parental support was measured by items such as: *My parents are proud of me*, or *My parents help me when I have problems*.

As shown in *Fig. 16* and *Tab. 33*, students experience parents' support on a quite high level (M), but with a quite large spread (SD > 1).

Fig. 16. Belief about parents' support 1 = not true (low support) 6 = very true (high support)

Tab. 33. Perceived parental support, differences between JOBS- and Non-JOBS groups and over time

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1 – Time 2	
	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANOVA	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANCOVA	J GLM	NJ GLM
Parental sup	5.14/ 1.03	4.87/ 1.13	NJ < J***	5.13/ .94	4.84/ 1.11	NJ < J**	n.s.	n.s.
Parental support t1: $F(1,792) = 12.34, p = .001, \eta^2 = .015$, t2: $F(1,635) = 5.95, p = .01, \eta^2 = .009$								
<i>Note:</i> J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance p: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; η^2 = Eta square								

The JOBS-students perceive parental support on a higher level than Non-JOBS-students do.

→ It might be, that attending the program could also be of interest for the parents.

Perceived relevance of students' learning for parents

Students were asked to rate their perception of parents' attitude towards the importance of their learning at school (on a scale from 1= low to 6= high): *How important is it for your parents that you learn a lot in school?* (see *Tab. 2*). The answer (*Fig. 17* and *Tab. 34*) can be seen as a form of parents' sensitivity to their children's learning.

Students of both group perceive parents' expectations on their learning at school as high. There is no difference concerning students' perception of the relevance of school learning for their parents of JOBS-students compared with Non-JOBS-students. The decrease of this expectation by the end of the year is very small, statistically significant but not of relevance (weak effect/power).

Fig. 17. Students' perception on the relevance of school education for their parents (from 1= very unimportant to 6 = very important)

Tab. 34. Students perception of parents' attitudes towards the relevance of students' learning, differences between JOBS- and Non-JOBS groups and over time

Students perception of parents' attitude towards their child's learning	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1 – Time 2	
	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{GLM}	NJ _{GLM}
	5.82/ .60	5.82/ .63	n.s.	5.76/ .64	5.74/ .74	n.s.	t1>***t2	t1>***t2
Perception of parent' attitude towards students' learning: JOBS F(1,324) =13.484, p =000, η ² = .039, t2: F(1,326) =22.027, p = .000 η ² = .063								
Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance p * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; η ² = Eta square								

4.3.2 Effects of family context on learning outcomes

Effects of parents on JOBS-students' performed knowledge

Parents support and expectation on students' learning in school has a very small effect on students performed JOBS-knowledge (Tab. 35), even lower at the beginning of the year (12%, time 1) than at the end of the intervention year (16%, time 2). Students perception of parents expectation at the end of the year (time 2) has a positive effect on the performed knowledge (Beta .20***).

The degree of education shows a negative effect (Beta -.22***), that means, the lower the education of the parents the higher students' perception on their expectations on their child's learning.

Tab. 35. Effects of parents on JOBS-students' learning output (performed knowledge)

Parents support, attitude and expectation	Time 1				Time 2			
	M28 sup _p	M30 imp _p	M35 ed _p	M28-35	M28 sup _p	M30 imp _p	M35 ed _p	M28-35
Family support M28 sup _p	.088			.075	.287***			.266***
Importance of learning M30 imp _p		.043		.068		.203***		.115*
Education of parents M34 ed _p			-.233***	-.247***			-.223***	-.175**
R ² explained variance	.008	.002	.054	.067	.083	.041	.036	.116
F	2.508	.612	18.854***	11.439***	29.235***	14.373***	16.013***	21.573***

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; Level of significance: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

Effects of parents on JOBS-students' self-assessed knowledge

Characteristics of the family influence the learning output of the students, measured by self-assessed knowledge (Tab. 36). Students' perception of *parents' support* (M28) at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) explains 15% of the learning output of the students, at the end of the year (*time 2*) 20%. Perceived *parents' expectation* on students' learning (M30) has an impact on students' learning output at the end of the year (*time 2*).

The level of *parents' education* (M35) shows negative effects (the lower their education the higher their child's level of self-assessed knowledge).

All investigated factors together contribute with about 20% to the learning output as self-assessed knowledge of the students.

Tab. 36. Effects of parents on JOBS-students' learning output (self-assessed knowledge)

Parents support, attitude and expectation	Time 1				Time 2			
	M28 sup _p	M30 imp _p	M35 ed _p	M28-35	M28 sup _p	M30 imp _p	M35 ed _p	M 28-35
Family support M28 sup _p	.393***			.388***	.429***			.415***
Importance of learning M30 imp _p		.018		.036		.182**		.117*
Education of parents M34 ed _p			-.19**	-.208**			-.19**	-.11**
R ² explained variance	.152	.166	.004	.194	.184	.033	.036	.201
F	57.606***	10.065***	.449	37.069***	71.803***	11.149**	11.869***	40.001***

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; Level of significance: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

Effects of parents on JOBS-students' self-assessed skills

Results on effects of family characteristics on students self-assessed skills (Tab. 37) contribute with an explained variance of 22% at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) and 29% at the end of the year (*time 2*); level of parents' education has a negative effect on students self-assessed skills.

→ The education level of the parents (M35) correlates negatively with the learning output of the students; as lower the education level of the parents as higher students' perception of their skills.

Tab. 37. Effects of parents on JOBS-students' learning output (self-assessed skills)

Parents support, attitude and expectation	Time 1				Time 2			
	M28 sup _p	M30 imp _p	M35 ed _p	M28-35	M28 sup _p	M30 imp _p	M35 ed _p	M28-35
Family support M28 sup _p	.385***			.374***	.505***			.473***
Importance of learning M30 imp _p		.058		.035		.143*		.082
Education of parents M34 ed _p			-.229***	-.269***			-.229***	-.182***
R ² explained variance	.148	.003	.052	.219	.255	.021	.052	.285
F	52.657***	1.07	49.563***	41.376***	106.25**	6.563*	49.563***	61.930***

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

Summary of results on effects of parents on the learning output of the students:

→ Perceived support and expectations of parents have a positive influence on JOBS-students' learning output.

→ Parents' education correlates negatively, that means, as lower parents' education the higher the learning output of the students. So, students of parents with low education feel themselves more competent and perform their knowledge on a higher level than students of parent of higher education level.

→ The effect on performed knowledge is lower than the one on self-assessed knowledge and on self-assessed skill.

→ The effects over time are lower than the effects at the end of the year, measured at the same time as the learning output.

4.3.3 School context – School and Teachers

The following informations on school context was collected:

- *School type*: Gymnasium and vocational college
- *Location of the school*: village, small town and city
- Students' *perceived support from their teachers* was measured by a four items scale, with answer in a six points scale (1=not true, 6 = very true), on questions like: *Teacher realises immediately when I have not understood something correctly.* (see Tab. 2).
- In addition, students were asked on their *perception on teachers attitudes towards the importance of their learning*, asked by the question: *How important is it to your teachers that you learn a lot in school*, on a scale from 1= very unimportant to 6= very important (see Tab. 2).

4.3.3.1 School and Teachers – differences between JOBS- and Non-JOBS-groups

Students' perceived support of their teachers

JOBS-students' perception of teachers' support is higher than the one of Non-JOBS-students (Fig. 18 and Tab. 38). The differences are of high significance, but with a low effect. There are no changes over time.

Fig. 18. Students perception on their teachers' support (from 1= low to 6 = high)

Tab. 38. Students' perception of teachers' support, differences between JOBS- and Non-JOBS groups and over time

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1–Time 2	
	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANCOVA	J _{GLM}	NJ _{GLM}
Perceived support	4.85/1.16	4.50/1.18	NJ < J***	4.87/1.13	4.37/1.15	NJ < J***	n.s.	n.s.
Students perception of teachers support t1 F(1,792)= 17.27, p = .001, $\eta^2 = .021$, t2 F(1,635)= 8.47, p=.004, $\eta^2 = .013$								
<i>Note:</i> J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance p: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; η^2 = Eta square								

Students' perception on teachers' attitude on the relevance of their learning

There are no differences between the two groups regarding the perception of the importance teachers place on learning (Fig. 19 and Tab. 39). Non-JOBS students perceived a decrease of the importance of their learning for their teachers during the school year.

Fig. 19. Students' perception of teachers' attitudes towards the relevance of school education (1= very unimportant, 6 = very important)

Tab. 39. Students' perception of teachers attitudes towards the relevance of students' learning, differences between JOBS- and Non-JOBS groups and over time

Teachers' relevance of students' learning	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1–Time 2	
	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{GLM}	NJ _{GLM}
	5.17/1.24	5.23/1.24	n.s.	5.07/1.35	4.91/1.40	n.s.	n.s.	t1>***t2

Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance p: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; η^2 = Eta square

4.3.3.2 Effects of characteristics of school context on students' learning output

Effects on performed knowledge

Tab. 40. Effects of school context on learning output as performed knowledge

Model	School		Time 1			Time 2		
	M 26 type	M27 loc	M24 sup _t	M25 im _t	M24,25	M24 sup _t	M25 im _t	M24,25
Type of school M26 type	.106*							
School location M27 loc		.061**						
Teachers support M24 sup _t			.108*		.107*	.213***		.088
Importance of learning M25 im _t				.019	.007		.125*	.049
R ²	.011	.117	.012	.000	.011	.046	.016	.059
F	3.782*	10.044***	3.774*	.125	1.846	33.946***	5.352*	10.242***

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

School-type (M26) has no significant effect on the performed knowledge of JOBS-students (*Tab. 40*); the *location of the school* (village, small town, city, M27) explains 11% of the performed knowledge. Perceived teacher support and expectations at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) have no effect on students' performed knowledge, those at the beginning of the year contributes with 5% to the amount of performed knowledge.

→ School type show no effect on students' performed knowledge.

→ Location of the school shows an effect on students' performed knowledge.

Effects on self-assessed knowledge

Tab. 41. Effects of school context on learning output as self-assessment of knowledge

Model	School		Time 1			Time 2		
	M 26 type	M27 loc	M24 supT	M25 Rele03	M24,25	M24 SupT	M25 Rele03	M24,25
Type of school M26 type	.206***							
School location M27 loc		.036						
Teachers support M24 SupT			.288***		.046	.362***		.149**
Importance of learning M25				.112*	.284***		.207***	.332***
R ² explained variance	.042	.001	.083	.012	.089	.131	.043	.150
F	14.483***	.923	28.119***	4.105*	14.359***	48.271***	14.564***	28.018***

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: p * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

Concerning self-assessed knowledge (*Tab. 41*), school type (M26) contributes with 4% to the self-assessed knowledge, location of the school (M27) has no effect.

Students' perception on teachers' support (M24) at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) explains 8% of the learning output; at the end of the year (*time 2*), the explained variance is more or less the same, in combination with teachers' expectations the effect arises to an extent of 15% (M24,25).

→ Teacher support and teachers' interest on their learning is a motivation factor for students; it effects their experiencing of competence and contributes to their learning output.

→ School type and location of the school has no effect on students' self-assessed knowledge

Effects on self-assessed skills

School type (M26) explains 4% of the learning output (*Tab. 42*), measured by students' self-assessed skills, location of the school (M27) contributes with 2%. The influence of teacher support (M24) on experienced skills is even higher than the on the self-assessed knowledge; experienced teacher support at the beginning of the year explains 12% of the learning output, at the end of the year 23%. Teachers' expectation contributes with about 3%.

→ Perceived teacher support matters!

→ School type and location of the school has no effect on students' self-assessed knowledge

Tab. 42. Effects of school context on learning output as self-assessed skills

Model	School		Time 1			Time 2		
	M 26 type	M27 loc	M24 SupT	M25 impT	M24,25	M24 supT	M25 impT	M24,25
Type of school	.197***							
School location		.125***						
Support			.341***		.33***	.482***		.095*
Importance of learning				.16**	.08		.188***	.462***
R ² explained variance	.039	.016	.116	.023	.123	.232	.035	.241
F	12.76***	10.659***	36.69***	8.34**	21.06***	94.504***	11.426***	49.04***

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; evel of significance: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

Summary on influences of school context:

- School location has an effect on students' performed knowledge, but not on the self-assessed one.
- School type contributes to the self-assessed learning output of the students; students from gymnasium assess their knowledge and skills higher than students form vocational school.
- Students' teacher support show the strongest effect on students' self- assessed skills, followed by self-assessed knowledge and performed knowledge. Teacher support and interest on students learning is a fostering precondition for students experiencing their competencies.

5 Study B – Teachers

5.1 Learning output and its importance, from the perspectives of the teachers

5.1.1 Knowledge and skills

Results on knowledge and skills, evaluated by the teachers, were presented already in the report part I (see report part I). I will be recapitulated briefly.

JOBS-knowledge and its' relevance

Fig. 20. JOBS-related knowledge of students, from the perspective of their teachers, separated into JOBS and Non-JOBS classes

According to the ratings of the teachers, there was a significant increase in *knowledge* amongst students of the intervention group. There is no noticeable development in the control group (see Figure 20 and Table 43).

The ratings of *relevance of knowledge* from the perspective of the teachers show no difference over time. The mean values are very high with no significant differences.

→ The JOBS and Non-JOBS teachers evaluate the JOBS-based knowledge as very important.

Tab. 43. Ratings of students' knowledge and its relevance from the teachers' perspective, differences between JOBS- and Non-JOBS teachers and over time

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1-Time2	
	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}
Knowledge ¹	3.04/.77	3.22/.81	n.s.	4.18/.81	3.19/.90	J > NJ***	t1 < t2***	3.04/.77
Relevance ²	5.43/.50	5.40/.52	n.s.	5.48/.50	5.46/.57	n.s.	n.s.	5.43/.50

¹Main effect J > NJ*** F(1, 264) = 30.46, p < .001, $\eta^2 = .104$; ²Main effect J / NJ F(1, 264) = .052, p = .820, $\eta^2 = .000$
 Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance p: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; η^2 = Eta square

Skills: Competence, Relevance and Valence

Fig. 21. Ratings of the students' skills by the teachers: Skills and the relevance of this skills and the students' enjoyment in using these skills

According to the rating of teachers (Fig. 21 and Tab. 44), the *skills* of the JOBS-students increased significant, assessed by their teachers. An increase can also be seen in the *valence (enjoyment)* of using these skills. Concerning the relevance of JOBS-skills, there are no significant differences between JOBS- and Non-JOBS teachers. No significant changes can be seen amongst the Non-JOBS-students. No significant changes can be identified in the rating of relevance.

Tab. 44. Ratings of students' skills: Competence, its relevance and the valence of carrying out activities based on the teaching and learning materials, differences between JOBS- and Non-JOBS teachers and over time

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1-Time2	
	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}
Skills	3.22/ .96	3.20/ 1.06	n.s.	4.30/ .90	3.66/ 1.22	J > NJ ***	t1 < t2***	n.s.
Relevance	5.25/ .78	5.27/ .66	n.s.	5.47/ .58	5.27/ .66	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Valence	4.12/ .94	3.71/ .89	n.s.	4.59/ .73	3.91/ 1.16	J > ** NJ	t1 < *** t2	n.s.
Competence: F(1, 258) = 17.52, p < .001, η ² = .064, Pleasure: F(1, 254) = 12.19, p = .001, η ² = .046								
Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance p * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; η ² = Eta square								

→ JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers assess JOBS-knowledge and skills as very important.

→ JOBS-teachers evaluate an increase of their students' JOBS-knowledge and JOBS-skills.

→ JOBS-teachers assess an increasing enjoyment of their student working on the tasks presented in the learning material of JOBS-program.

5.1.2 Effects on the learning output of the students, assessed by the teachers

Tab. 45. Effects of the relevance and the valence of JOBS-knowledge and skills on the emerging *knowledge* at the end of the intervention, assessed by the teachers

Model	Time 1				Time 2			
	M4 er	M5 sim	M6 spla	M4, 5,6	M4 er	M5 sim	M6 spla	M4, 5,6
Relevance of knowledge M4 er	.140			.078	.424***			.307*
Relevance of skills M5 sim		.170		.048		.295*		-.201
Valence of skills M6 spla			.269*	.245			.536***	.499***
R ²	.020	.029	.068	.087	.180	.087	.288	.337
F	1.47	2.120	5.140*	2.153	15.77***	6.59***	28.69***	11.186***

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; Level of significance: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

Tab. 46. Effects of the relevance and the valence of JOBS-knowledge and skills on the emerging *skills* at the end of the intervention, assessed by the teachers

Model	Time 1				Time 2			
	M4 er	M5 sim	M6 spla	M4, 5,6	M4 er	M5 sim	M6 spla	M4, 5,6
Relevance of knowledge M4er	.125			.030	.475***			.083
Relevance of skills M5 sim		.269*		.131		.511***		-.001
Valence of skills M6 spla			.369**	.326			.816***	.791***
R ²	.020	.036	.136	.165	.225	.261	.666	.696
F	1.47	1.311	11.193**	4.476**	20.95***	24.33***	141.79***	50.30***

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: p * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

Teachers attitude towards the relevance of JOBS-knowledge and skills influence the learning output of their students (Tab. 45 and Tab. 46).

Relevance of knowledge and *relevance* of skills effect the learning output – the effects of *relevance* at the beginning of the year (*tieme 1*) are less than at the end of the year (*time 2*). The *valence* of working on the tasks, that means the pleasure students experience using their skills by dealing with the requirements of JOBS-program, show the strongest effect, especially at the end of the year (*time 2*). The effect is bigger on skills that the effect on knowledge.

→ Teachers attitude towards knowledge and skills they teach are important for the progress of their students.

→ In addition, in the perception of JOBS-teachers, pleasure while learning and motivation to deal with tasks boost the learning output of their students, at least during JOBS-lessons.

5.2 Individual characteristics

5.2.1 Self-concept as self-efficacy

Self-efficacy represents somebody's self-concept of being capable to deal with requirements, based on their capacity and their effort. Self-efficacy is measured with a general approach and a professions specific approach (Schwarzer & Jerusalem, 1999; Schmitz & Schwarzer, 2000)

5.2.1.1 Self-efficacy and their differences between the groups and over time

General and teacher related self-efficacy

Fig. 22. General self-efficacy of teachers (from 1=low, 6 = high)

Tab. 47. Self-efficacy of teachers, differences between JOBS- and Non-JOBS teachers and over time

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1-Time2	
	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{GLM}	NJ _{GLM}
General self-efficacy sw	4.94/.62	4.83/.66	n.s.	4.93/.58	4.98/.57	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Teacher self-efficacy lws	5.01/.47	4.91/.51	n.s.	5.01/.49	4.86/.60	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.

Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; η^2 = Eta square

The results on self-efficacy (Fig. 22 and Tab. 47) show no significant differences between JOBS and Non-JOBS teachers regarding general and teacher related self-efficacy. Attending the JOBS program has no effect on self-efficacy, identified as a stable personality trait.

→ JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers do not differ in their individual characteristics of self-efficacy. Concerning this characteristic, all of them could attend JOBS-program as a JOBS-teacher.

5.2.1.2 Effects of teachers' self-efficacy on students learning output, evaluated by the teachers

Tab. 48. Effects of teachers' self-efficacy on students' learning output as knowledge, assessed by the teachers

Model	Time 1		Time 2	
	M21A sw	M21B lsw	M21A sw	M21B lsw
General self-efficacy swsM21a	.240*		.175	
Teachers self-efficacy lsw M21b		.080		.068
R ²	.057	.006	.031	.005
F	4.146*	.468	2.143	.338

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: p * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

Tab. 49. Effects of teachers' self-efficacy on students' learning output as skills, assessed by the teachers

Model	Time 1		Time 2	
	M21A sw	M21B lsw	M21A sw	M21B lsw
General self-efficacy sw M21A	.175		.185	
Teachers self-efficacy lsw M21B		.068		.234*
R ²	.034	.055	.034	.055
F	2.566	4.154*	2.566	4.154*

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: p * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

Regarding general self-efficacy (Tab. 48 and Tab. 49), the results show that self-efficacy of teachers contributes not significantly to the learning output of the students, assessed by their teachers.

→ Self-efficacy of JOBS-teachers is not a precondition to foster students' learning output.

5.2.2 Motives

5.2.2.1 Motives and their differences between the groups and over time

Job Motives of teachers

Fig. 23. Job motives to fulfill psychological basic needs, JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers compares

Tab. 50. Job motives to fulfill psychological basic needs, JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers compares, differences between JOBS- and Non-JOBS teachers and over time

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1-Time2	
	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANOVA	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANOVA	J GLM	NJ GLM
Autonomy	5.29/.66	5.22/.71	n.s.	5.21/.7	5.15/.72	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Relatedness	5.49/.55	5.35/.54	n.s.	5.21/.70	5.15/.72	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Challenge	4.34/.64	4.40/.55	n.s.	.21/.70	5.15/.72	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Meaningfulness	5.40/.54	.29/.49	n.s.	5.21/.70	5.15/.72	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.

Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance p: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; η^2 = Eta square

Job motives of teachers seem to be quite stable (see Fig. 23 and Table 50). There are no significant and relevant differences between the two groups of teachers and over time.

→ JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers don't differ in their profile of work motives.

5.2.2.2 Effects of teachers Motivation to work on students' knowledge assessed by the teachers at the end of the intervention

Tab. 51. Effects of work motives on students' learning output as *knowledge*, assessed by the teachers

	Time 1	Time 2
Motives for work M12 wi	M12 wi	M12 wi
Autonomy	.273*	.262*
Relatedness	.153	.172
Challenge	-.105	.105
Meaningfulness	-.005	-.254*
R ²	.113	.166
F	2.140	3.274**

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: p * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

Teachers job motivation (Table 51) at the beginning of the intervention (time 1) explain 11% of the learning output of their students, measured as knowledge, assessed by the teachers; motivation for work at the end of the intervention (time 2) explains students' JOBS-related knowledge with 17%.

Tab. 52. Effects of work motives on students' learning output as *skills*, assessed by the teachers

	Time 1	Time 2
Motives for work M12 wi	M12 wi	M12 wi
Autonomy	.118	.164
Relatedness	.154	.392*
Challenge	.106	.035
Meaningfulness	.048	-.228
R ²	.085	.204
F	1.559*	4.236**

Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: p * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001

Teachers job motivation (Tab. 52) at the beginning of the intervention (time 1) explain 9% of the learning output of their students, measured as skills, assessed by the teachers; motivation for work at the end of the intervention (time 2) explains students' JOBS-related knowledge with 20%.

→ Teacher's job motivation explains 9-20% of students' learning. So, teachers' motivation matters!

5.2.3 Beliefs

5.2.3.1 Beliefs and their differences between the groups and over time

Beliefs on Students' Motivation to Learn

Fig. 24. Teachers beliefs on students' motivation to learn

Avoidance to learn and achieve in school is the strongest motive of students to learn in school, according to their teachers' perspective. In the group of the Non-JOBS-teachers this belief even grows during the school-year. *Social approval* as a learning motive for students shows the second highest extension according teachers perspective, beliefs on *learning orientation* shown the lowest one (Fig. 24).

→ Teacher beliefs on students' motivation to learn in school show a negative expectation concerning students' learning motivation.

Non-JOBS-teachers' belief on students' avoidance of learning and achievement increases during the school year; the one of JOBS-teachers stays on the same level (Tab. 53).

→ As an effect of JOBS-program, JOBS-teachers change their expectations on their students within less than one year – it can be assumed, that the task based students-centered didactic approach of JOBS-program gives them the chance to experience their students' activity and interests.

Tab. 53. Teachers beliefs on students' motivation to learn, differences between JOBS- and Non-JOBS teachers and over time

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1-Time2	
	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANOVA	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANOVA	J GLM	NJ GLM
Learning	3.28/.73	3.18/.80	n.s.	3.33/.67	3.25/.91	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Social approval	3.64/.81	3.85/.81	n.s.	3.86/.78	3.77/.79	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Avoidance	4.02/.74	4.14/.68	n.s.	3.97/.89	4.16/.80	n.s.	n.s.	t1 <*** t2
Non-JOBS t1-t2: $F(1,68) = 4.32, p = **, \eta^2 = .060$								
Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance p: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; η^2 = Eta square								

Beliefs on teaching and learning

JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers differ in their beliefs on teaching and learning (Fig. 25 and Table 54). JOBS-teachers show higher marks concerning constructivist orientation and lower in transmissive ones than Non-JOBS-teachers.

→ It seems that teachers with fitting orientations towards the didactic approach were interested to join the JOBS-project and learn more in student-focused, task-based approaches.

Over time, JOBS-teachers' constructivist orientation even increases, their transmissive orientation decreases, while Non-JOBS-teachers' orientation stays stable.

→ Experiencing the didactic approach of JOBS-program JOBS-teachers change their beliefs on effective teaching and learning beliefs towards a more student-centered approach.

Fig. 25. Beliefs of teachers on teaching and learning

Tab. 54. Beliefs of teachers on teaching and learning, differences between JOBS- and Non-JOBS teachers and over time

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1-Time2	
	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANCOVA	J _{GLM}	NJ _{GLM}
Constructivist	5.13/.50	4.95/.67	n.s.	5.33/.54	5.04/.63	J>NJ*	t1<t2*	n.s.
Transmissive	4.48/.70	4.78/.58	J<NJ*	4.18/.79	4.81/.57	J<NJ***	t1>t2***	n.s.
Constructivist t1: F(1,127) = 5.74, p=n.s., $\eta^2 = .04$; t2: F(1,127) = 5.74, p=**, $\eta^2 = .04$, t1-t2 JOBS-teachers : F(1,72) = 6.24 p=**, $\eta^2 = .08$; t1-t2 NJ n.s. Transmissive t1: F(1,168) = 9.71, p=*, $\eta^2 = .055$; t2: F(1,128) = 19.71, p=**, $\eta^2 = .13$; t1-t2 JOBS-teachers: F(1,72) = 3.36 p=**, $\eta^2 = .089$; t1-t2 Non-JOBS-teachers n.s.								
Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance p: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; η^2 = Eta square								

Norms of reference to evaluate achievement

Teachers reference frame to evaluate achievement (Fig. 26 and Tab. 55) shows higher marks concerning the norm the criteria of a task and concerning individual learning processes of the students than in relation to the average of the class. JOBS- and Non-JOBS don't differ statistically significant and relevant.

→ Attending JOBS-project has no effect on teachers' norms of reference to evaluate students' achievement.

Fig. 26. Norms of reference to evaluate achievement

Tab. 55. Norms of reference to evaluate achievement, differences between JOBS- and Non-JOBS teachers and over time

Norm	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1-Time 2	
	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	J _{GLM}	NJ _{GLM}
Individual oriented	3.43/.46	3.39/.57	n.s.	3.52/.47	3.48/.50	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Social oriented	2.86/.65	2.84/.73	n.s.	2.70/.76	2.96/.77	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
Task based	3.48/.56	3.41/.52	n.s.	3.32/.60	3.45/.53	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.

Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance p: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; η^2 = Eta square

Teachers' beliefs on the relevance of students' learning in school

Teachers' beliefs on the importance of students' learning for school and for their future (Fig. 27 and Tab. 56) don't differ between JOBS- and Non-JOBS teachers, in addition, these beliefs are stable over time.

→ Attending JOBS-project has no effect on teachers' beliefs on the importance to learn. JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers' belief in this importance very strongly.

Fig. 27. Teachers beliefs on the importance of students learning for school and for future

Tab. 56. Teachers' beliefs of students' learning for school and for future

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1-Time 2	
	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANOVA	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANOVA	J	NJ
for school	5.28/.92	5.27/.99	n.s.	5.28/.94	5.36/.87	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.
for future	5.29/.89	5.54/.73	n.s.	5.23/.97	5.48/.76	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.

Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance p: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; η^2 = Eta square

Teachers beliefs on students' interest to learn about professions and own strength

JOBS and Non-JOBS-teachers differ in their beliefs on students' interest in learning about professions and their own strength (Fig. 28 and Table 57). JOBS-teachers expect students' interest as higher than Non-JOBS-teacher do. At the end of the year the belief on students' interest even grew higher.

→ Teachers attending the program have higher expectations on students' interest towards subject knowledge and skills JOBS program aims to facilitate.

→ It seems that JOBS-teachers are more sensitive to possible interests of students on the goals the program is aiming on.

→ Attending the program JOBS-teachers' belief in students' interest even grew.

→ JOBS-program effects JOBS-teachers' belief-system on students' interest according to the goals, the program focus on.

Fig. 28. Teachers' beliefs on students' interests to learn about professions and about their strength (1=low, 6= high)

Tab. 57. Teachers' belief on students' interests to learn about professions and about their own strength, differences between JOBS- and Non-JOBS teachers and over time

	Time 1			Time 2			Time 1-Time 2	
	J M/SD	N-J M/SD	ANOVA	J M/SD	N-J M/SD	ANCOVA	J	NJ
Professions	3.99/1.27	3.41/1.20	J>NJ**	4.83/.88	3.38/1.23	J>NJ***	t1<t2***	n.s.
Strength	4.38/1.12	3.81/1.23	J>NJ**	5.09/.91	3.63/1.38	J>NJ***	t1 <t2***	n.s.
<i>Students' interests on learning about professions: t1 t1 F(1,169) = 9.090**, $\eta^2 = .052$; t2 F(1,169) = 84.939***, n.s., $\eta^2 = .341$; t1-t2 JOBS-teachers: F(1,73) = 24.03***, $\eta^2 = .248$; Non-JOBS-teachers F(1,59) = .278, n.s., $\eta^2 = .001$</i>								
<i>Students' interests on learning about their own strength: t1 F(1,169) = 9.819, p = .002, $\eta^2 = .056$; t2 F(1,169) = 65.53***, p < .001, $\eta^2 = .241$; t1-t2 JOBS-teachers F(1,133) = 22.94***, $\eta^2 = .239$; Non-JOBS-teachers F(1,58) = .025, n.s., $\eta^2 < .001$</i>								
<i>Note: J= JOBS-students, NJ= Non-JOBS-students, M= mean, SD= standard deviation, level of significance p: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001; η^2 = Eta square</i>								

JOBS-teachers perceive a significant increase of their students' interest on professions and on their own strength during the JOBS-intervention program.

→ To work on specific tasks and to deal with arising difficulties and requirements has a positive impact on their interest in the specific subject matter they are dealing with.

5.2.3.2 Effects on learning output, evaluated by teachers

Effects of teachers' beliefs on students' knowledge, assessed by teachers

Beliefs of teachers have an effect on students' knowledge and skills at the end of the year (Table 58 and Table 59). Specially students' interest on professions and on own strengths – the specific focus of JOBS-program – explains 34% of the learning output, evaluated by the teachers. Beliefs on constructivist learning orientation shows a significant effect on students' learning output, perceived by their teachers.

→ Beliefs, fitting to the didactic approach of the program and focused on the subject matter of JOBS-program contributes to a higher learning output of the students, perceived by the teachers.

Tab. 58. Effects of teachers' beliefs at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) on the students' knowledge at the end of the year (*time 2*)

Teachers' beliefs on	Time 1				
	M7 re	M8 ltu	M9 nor	M10 ev	M11mos
Importance of learning M7 re					
for school	.047				
for future	-.099				
Beliefs on teaching and learning M8 ltu					
Constructivist		.039			
Transmissive		-.217			
Norms of reference to evaluate achievement M9 nor					
Individual oriented norm			.230		
Social oriented			-.234		
Task oriented norm			.200		
Interest in professions (eval 03) and in own strengths M10 eval 04					
Professions				.172	
own strength				.028	
Learning motives (mos)					
Learning					.218
Social approval					.056
Avoidance					.182
R ²	.007	.050	.103	.037	.092
F	.244	1.848	2.611	1.363	2.252
<i>Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001</i>					

Tab. 59. Effects of teachers' beliefs at the end of the year (*time 2*) on the students' knowledge at the end of the year (*time 2*)

Teachers' beliefs on	Time 2				
	M7 re	M8 ltu	M9 nor	M10 ev	M11 mos
Importance of learning M7 re					
for school	.039				
for future	.011				
Beliefs on teaching and learning M8 ltu					
Constructivist		.264*			
Transmissive		-.073			
Orientation towards reference standards M9 nor					
Individual oriented norm			.234		
Social oriented			.018		
Task based norm			-.050		
Interest in working world M10 ev3 and in own strengths ev4					
Professions				.306*	
own strength				.318**	
Learning motives M11 mos					
Learning					.144
Social approval					.277*
Avoidance					-.133
R ²	.002	.066	.049	.337	.130
F	.075	2.484	1.092	18.038***	3.335*
<i>Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001</i>					

Effects of teachers' beliefs on students' skills, assessed by the teachers

Tab. 60. Effects of teachers' beliefs at the beginning of the year (*time 1*) on their evaluation of the students' skills at the end of the year (*time 2*)

	Time 1				
Teachers' beliefs on	M7 re	M8 ltu	M9 nor	M10 eval	M11 mos
Importance of learning M7 re					
for school	-.024				
for future	-.016				
Beliefs on teaching and learning M8 ltu					
Constructivist		.187			
Transmissive		-.118			
Norms of reference to evaluate achievement M9 nor					
Individual oriented norm			.180		
Social oriented			-.314		
Task oriented norm			.126		
Interest in professions (eval 03) and in own strengths M10 eval 04					
Professions				.053	
own strength				.030	
Learning motives (mos)					
Learning					.238*
Social approval					.263*
Avoidance					-.001
R²	.001	.053	.091	.006	.173
F	.044	1.967	2.268	.210	4.685**
<i>Note: R² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001</i>					

Teachers' beliefs effect the students' learning output of skills as well (*Table 60* and *Table 61*). Interest on professions, individual oriented norm of reference of teachers on the perception of learning orientation of the students contribute to the explained variance of students' learning output.

Tab. 61. Effects of teachers' beliefs at the end of the year (*time 2*) on their evaluation of the students' skills at the end of the year (*time 2*)

	Time 2				
Teachers' beliefs on	M7 re	M8 ltu	M9 nor	M10 ev	M11 mos
Importance of learning M7 re					
for school	.139				
for future	-.119				
Beliefs on teaching and learning M8 ltu					
Constructivist		.191			
Transmissive		.026			
Orientation towards reference standards M9 nor					
Individual oriented norm			.365*		
Social oriented			-.201		
Task based norm			-.027		
Interest in working world M10 ev3 and in own strengths ev4					
Professions				.465***	
own strength				.168	
Learning motives M11 mos					
Learning					.357**
Social approval					.359**
Avoidance					-.140
R²	.015	.040	.113	.359	.354
F	.545	1.441	2.671	19.845***	.354***

→ All in all, teachers' beliefs influence the learning output of the students, but it is not clear, if teachers' beliefs explain the learning output or teachers' perception of it.

5.3 Context – team conditions

During the process of the evaluation-study, instruments on school conditions of teachers as collective resources to deal with requirements were added to the survey. Teachers' attitudes towards cooperation, the frequencies of cooperation and the perceived quality of the teams they are part of it were added to the questionnaire at the end of the year (*time2*).

5.3.1 Cooperation within groups of subject teachers and of JOBS-teachers

Teachers were asked about their *attitudes on cooperation* and on the *frequency of their cooperation*. All teachers were asked about this within their groups of subject-teachers. In addition, JOBS-teachers were asked about their attitudes and frequencies of cooperation within the JOBS-groups. While the Non-JOBS teachers were asked only about their cooperation within the subject-groups, JOBS-teachers were asked about their cooperation within both groups, subject-group and JOBS-groups.

5.3.1.1 Cooperation of teachers and their differences between the groups

Fig. 29 shows the result on cooperation of JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers within their subject-groups, *Fig 30* shows the results of JOBS-teachers cooperation within the groups of JOBS-teachers and within the groups of subject-teachers.

Fig. 29. Cooperation of teachers within subject groups

Cooperation of teachers within their subject groups, comparison between JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers: There are no differences (*Tab. 62*) between JOBS and Non-JOBS teachers regarding the *frequency* of cooperation in planning and preparation as well as discussion and reflection within the subject group. JOBS teachers consider planning and preparation more *important* than Non-JOBS teachers within the same subject group. There are no differences for cooperation by discussion and reflection.

→ JOBS-teachers attitudes on cooperation show a higher relevance of cooperation.

Cooperation of JOBS-teachers within the subject- and JOBS-group they are part of (Fig. 30): JOBS-teachers evaluate the importance of planning and preparing as important within the JOBS-groups as within the subject-groups. Concerning the importance, they assess discussion and reflection with JOBS-teachers more important that with subject teachers. They cooperate with JOBS-teachers more often than they do within the group of subject-teachers.

→ JOBS-teachers cooperate more often within their groups with JOBS-teachers.

Fig. 30. Cooperation of JOBS-teachers within the teams of JOBS-teachers and within their group of subject-teachers

In both dimensions, such as planning and preparing as well as discussion and reflection, JOBS-teachers cooperate more often within their JOBS-groups than within subject-groups (Fig. 30 and Tab. 62). Concerning the importance of cooperation, there are no differences.

→ Relying on the didactic approach of JOBS-program and its expectations on teachers, JOBS-teachers cooperate more within their JOBS-groups than they do with other teachers, teaching the same subject.

Tab. 62. Cooperation of JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers within their subject-groups and cooperation of JOBS-teachers within their JOBS-groups and subject-groups

	J and NJ-teachers within Subject Groups			JOBS Teachers within JG and SG		
	J M/SD	NJ M/SD	ANOVA	JG M/SD	SG M/SD	ANOVA
Importance of cooperation						
Planning and preparation	5.21/.61	4.83/.96	J> NJ **	5.29/.71	5.215/.61	n.s.
Discussion and reflection	5.35/.58	5.20/.74	n.s.	5.51/.60	5.366/.58	JG > SG ***
Frequency of cooperation						
Planning and preparation	3.93/1.16	3.73/.33	n.s.	5.09/1.06	3.93/1.16	JG >SG ***
Discussion and reflection	4.69/.92	4.57/1.17	n.s.	5.44/.66	4.69/.92	JG > SG ***
<i>Note: J= JOBS-teachers, NJ= Non-JOBS-teachers, JG= group of JOBS-teachers, SG= groups of subject teachers</i>						
<i>Attitude on importance of cooperation of J and NJ teachers within their subject-groups:</i>						
Planning and preparation: F(1,204) = 10.015, p=**, $\eta^2 = .046$						
<i>JOBS-teachers' attitude on importance of cooperation within JOBS-groups and subject-groups:</i>						
Discussion and reflection t2: F(1,76)=8.64, p=**, $\eta^2 = .10$						
<i>JOBS-teachers' frequency of cooperation within JOBS-groups and subject-groups</i>						
Planning and preparation F(1,76)=64.28, p=***, $\eta^2 = .45$; Discussion and reflection F(1,76)=56.75, p=***, $\eta^2 = .43$						

→ Cooperation within the team of JOBS-teachers is a core element of the didactic approach. Differences concerning the frequency of cooperation are expected. But concerning planning and preparing, JOBS-teachers don't cooperate more often with JOBS-teachers than they do with subject teacher. The well-prepared teaching and learning material of the JOBS-program can contribute to this.

→ JOBS-teachers' higher frequency in cooperation and their attitude concerning the importance of it could be a helpful precondition to attend the project successful.

5.3.1.2 Effects of cooperation of JOBS-teacher cooperation on the learning output of the students, evaluated by the teachers

Tab. 63. Effects of cooperation on the learning output as knowledge of the students at the end of the year (time 2), assessed by the teachers

Cooperation of JOBS-teachers	Time 2			
	M50 imSG	M51 frSG	M52 imJG	M53 frJG
Importance of cooperation within the subject-group				
Planning and preparation (important)	n.s.			
Discussion, reflection (important)	n.s.			
Frequency of cooperation within the subject-group				
Planning and preparation (often)		.064		
Discussion, reflection (often)		.341		
Cooperation of Jobs teachers – importance within the JOBS group				
Planning and preparation (important)			n.s.	
Discussion, reflection (important)			n.s.	
Cooperation of Jobs teachers – frequency within the JOBS group				
Planning and preparation (often)				-.13
Discussion, reflection (often)				.543***
R²	.006	.152*	.065	.20
F	n.s.	5.927*	n.s.	8.75***
<i>Note:</i> im= Importance, fr= frequency, JG= JOBD groups, SG= subject groups, R ² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001				

Teachers cooperating frequently within the subject group and especially within the JOBS-group, evaluate students' learning on a higher level (Tab. 63 and Tab. 64). Cooperation with other teachers through discussion and reflection contributes to a higher level of learning output of their students' knowledge and skills.

→ Teachers attitudes on discussion and reflection and their cooperating activities contributes to a higher learning output of their students, evaluated as skills.

→ Cooperation on planning is not as effective on students learning output than discuss and reflect their learning processes.

Tab. 64. Effects of cooperation on learning output as *skills* at the end of the year (*time 2*), assessed by the teachers

	Time 2			
	M50 imSG	M51 frSG	M52 imJG	M53 frJG
Importance of cooperation of Jobs teachers – importance within the subject group (kltiF)				
Planning and preparation (important)	-.051			
Discussion, reflection (important)	.242			
Cooperation of Jobs teachers – frequency within the subject group (kltiF)				
Planning and preparation (often)		-.008		
Discussion, reflection (often)		.360*		
Perceptions of OBS-teachers: Importance of cooperation within the JOBS-groups and within the subject-group (kltiJ)				
Planning and preparation (important)			-.024	
Discussion, reflection (important)			.4134***	
Cooperation of Jobs teachers – frequency within the Jobs subject group (kltiJ)				
Planning and preparation (often)				-.016
Discussion, reflection (often)				.502**
R²	.095	.125	.157	.242
F	3.634*	4.727*	6.330***	10.666***
<i>Note:</i> im= Importance, fr= frequency, JG= JOBD groups, SG= subject groups R ² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001				

5.3.2 Team quality

Team quality as a collective resource supports teachers in dealing with professional requirements (Purkey & Smith, 1983; Bonsen, 2005; Terhart & Klieme, 2006; Townsend, 2007; Fend, 2008; Keller-Schneider & Albißer, 2013; Fussangel & Gräsel, 2014). Team quality is evaluated according the four characteristics, such as shared aims, cooperate and teach as a team as well as solve problems together.

5.3.2.1 Cooperation of teachers and their differences between the groups

Fig. 31. Team-quality within the subject-groups, comparison between JOBS- and Non-JOBS teachers

Results (Fig. 31 and Tab. 65) show no significant differences between the teams of JOBS-teachers and the subject-teachers in comparison between JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers.

But JOBS-teachers perceive the team quality within the JOBS-groups as higher than they perceive it within the subject-group (Fig. 32 and Tab. 65).

Fig. 32. Team-quality, evaluated by JOBS-teachers, within the subject-groups and the JOBS-groups

→ Compared with other teams, JOBS-teachers evaluate the team quality of their JOBS-teams as higher. So, experiencing team-quality based on active interaction and cooperation, changes the frames of references on behalf of expectations on team quality.

→ JOBS-program has an effect on the team-quality of teams of teachers.

Tab. 65. Team quality within subject- and JOBS-groups

	t2 TeaS			tqJ - tqS Jobs teachers		
	J _{M/SD}	NJ _{M/SD}	ANOVA	tqJ _{M/SD}	tqS _{M/SD}	ANOVA
Shared aims and values	5.26/.71	5.25/.73	n.s.	5.63/.60	5.26/.71	tqS <*** tqJ
Teaching as a team	5.16/.77	5.10/.80	n.s.	5.61/.55	5.16/.77	tqS <*** tqJ
Cooperation as a team	5.28/.71	5.18/.81	n.s.	5.36/.63	5.28/.71	tqS <** tqJ
Solving problems together	5.10/.79	5.10/.78	n.s.	5.38/.71	5.10/.79	tqS <** tqJ
<i>Comparison of JOBS-teachers between JOBS- and subject-groups:</i>						
Shared aims and values t2: $F(1,97) = 26.26^{***}$, $\eta^2 = .21$; Teaching as a team t2: $F(1,97) = 31.51^{***}$, $\eta^2 = .24$						
Cooperation as a team t2: $F(1,97) = 11.56^{**}$, $\eta^2 = .11$; Solving problems together t2: $F(1,97) = 13.01^{**}$, $\eta^2 = .12$						
<i>Note:</i> tqJ= Team quality of JOBS-group; tqS= Team quality of subject-group						

5.3.2.2 Effects of team quality on the learning output of students, evaluated by teachers

→ A high team quality among teams of teachers contributes to a high learning output of their students (Tab. 66 and Tab. 67).

Tab. 66. Effects of quality of team on students' learning output as *knowledge* at the end of the year (time 2)

	Time 2		
	M55 tqSG	M56 tqJG	M55,56
Quality of team work within the same subject (teaF)			
Shared aims	n.s.		.089
Teach as a team	n.s.		-.355
Cooperation	n.s.		.595
Problem solving	n.s.		-.238
Quality of team work within Jobs subject (teaJ)			
Shared aims		-.006	.050
Teach as a team		.285	.147
Cooperation		-.134	-.218
Problem solving		.216	.278
R ²	.094	.121	.152
F	n.s.	2.277	1.39
<i>Note:</i> tqJ= Team quality of JOBS-group; tqS= Team quality of subject-group; R ² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; Level of significance: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001			

Tab. 67. Effects of quality of team on students' learning output as *skills* at the end of the year (time 2)

	Time 2		
	M55 tqSG	M56 tqJG	M55,56
Quality of team work within the same subject (teaF)			
Shared aims	.519*		.448
Teach as a team	-.507		-.606
Cooperation	.619		.569
Problem solving	-.341		-.464
Quality of team work within Jobs subject (teaJ)			
Shared aims		.252	.322
Teach as a team		.403	.322
Cooperation		-.311	-.489
Problem solving		.199	.358
R ²	.163	.283	.351
F	3.352*	6.527***	4.194***
<i>Note:</i> SG= subject group, JG= JOBS groups; R ² = explained variance by the predictors together, F=F-Value of the regression analyze and the level of its significance; level of significance: * < .05, ** < .01, *** < .001			

6 Summary

6.1 Study A: students, in addition to the results in Report 2015 Part I

6.1.1 JOBS-knowledge and JOBS-skills

The learning output of the students was evaluated in three approaches, such as a performed knowledge by a test with open questions, as well as knowledge and skills by self-assessed, enriched with motivational factors relying on these knowledge and skills. The results on the learning output of the students were summarized as follows.

- At the end of the year, JOBS-students *perform more knowledge*, evaluated by a knowledge test, than Non-JOBS-students. While JOBS-students show a significant increase of knowledge over the year attending JOBS-program, the knowledge of Non-JOBS-students remains stable.
- The same effects are identified within the results on *self-assessed knowledge*: Knowledge of JOBS-students increase during the year of JOBS-classes significantly while the knowledge of the Non-JOBS-students stay on the same range.
- JOBS students, after one year of JOBS-classes, show higher *skills* in dealing with requirements, JOBS-program focus on. Skills of the Non-JOBS-students remain on the same level.
- The amount of knowledge and skills at the beginning of the school year has a stronger impact on the knowledge and skills at the end of the year in the group of Non-JOBS-students than in the group of JOBS-students.
- The JOBS-program has an impact on the learning output of the JOBS-students, independent of the amount of knowledge they already bring in.

→ The JOBS program matters, JOBS knowledge and skills are teachable.

→ The JOBS-intervention program has an impact on the learning output of the students attending the program. JOBS-students know more about the professional world and about their own interests and strengths.

6.1.2 Attitudes on the relevance of knowledge and skills

- Concerning the *relevance of knowledge*, JOBS-program focus on, there is no difference between the groups and no development over time. All the students assess JOBS knowledge as important.
- With focus on the *relevance of these skills* and on the *pleasure by using them* (valence), JOBS-students show higher marks than Non-JOBS-students, at the beginning of the year as well as at the end of the one-year intervention. Their first experiences with tasks of the JOBS-program effect their attitudes.
- This attitude on the *relevance* of JOBS-knowledge and skills influence the learning output, especially on the self-assessed knowledge and the self-assessed skills.
- The pleasure in using JOBS-skills shows a boosting effect on the learning output.
- *Positive attitudes* towards JOBS-knowledge and skills are effective predictors of a high learning output of the student.

→ JOBS- and Non-JOBS-students consider the knowledge and the skills, taught by JOBS-program, as very important. There are no differences between the two groups, neither at the beginning nor at the end of the intervention. The JOBS theme is held as very relevant for all, independent of attending the program as a student or as a teacher or not.

→ This attitude influences the learning output of the JOBS-students. Requirements, fitting to individuals' belief system are important preconditions for the learning output of the students. To discuss with students on the meaning of requirements for their development contributes to a higher learning output, not only concerning JOBS-knowledge and JOBS-skills, we suppose.

→ The interest in and the relevance of JOBS-program is high, both from the perspective of the participating and the non-participating students, as well as from the perspective of their teachers (see chapter 6.2).

6.1.3 Self-concept:

- JOBS- and Non-JOBS-students don't differ in their subject specific academic self-concept. In addition, they don't differ neither in their preferences nor in their self-efficacy.
- In relation to the subject Mathematics, Romanian and English languages, JOBS-students' self-concept is higher in their JOBS-competences than in the other subjects.
- JOBS-students like the JOBS-lessons more than the other subjects; their preferences are very high.
- Students' *self-concept* and *self-efficacy* do not change during the time the program is running, but both have an impact on the learning output of the program.
- Self-competence to learn is a significant predictor of the learning output.

→ To foster students in their abilities to learn and to deal with tasks is an effective goal of JOBS-program, aimed on by the didactic approach of JOBS-program. To foster students in their competences to learn is an important task of school in general as well; JOBS-program may contribute to.

→ JOBS-program has no effect on students' subject-specific self-concept, but it gives the chance to all of them, to succeed in this specific subject, independent of their achievements in the other subjects.

6.1.4 Motivation

- JOBS- and Non-JOBS-students evaluate their learning for school and for the future as very important – a good precondition to work on tasks seriously. There are no differences between the two groups of students and no significant development over time.
- Students of both groups are motivated to learn. Their motivation is an important predictor for their learning output. But the JOBS-intervention program has no effect on students' learning motivation, their acting and learning is based on. The profile of their learning motivation stays stable during the year of JOBS-intervention program.
- Even motives have an impact on the learning output concerning JOBS-knowledge and JOBS-skills, JOBS-program doesn't influence the deeper motivation of learning. JOBS- and Non-JOBS-students don't differ in their motivation as expectations on their work.

→ Motives are important predictors for students learning output, but they do not change through the program.

→ To talk about students' motives for learning and for work could help to strengthen their focus on learning and achievement.

6.1.5 Beliefs

- JOBS- and Non-JOBS-students don't differ in their beliefs, such as on teaching and learning or on the reference norms to evaluate achievement.
- Beliefs contribute to the self-assessed learning output of JOBS learning-activities. Constructivist beliefs on teaching and learning as well as individual oriented and task-oriented norms of references for achievement have the strongest positive effect on the learning output.
- JOBS-program has no effect on students' beliefs on teaching and learning. Even they experience a constructivist approach during the task based student-centered program, their belief-system doesn't change through this experience.

→ Even the beliefs didn't change during the year of the intervention, beliefs influence the learning output.

→ Beliefs fitting to the didactic approach of JOBS, such as constructivist beliefs on teaching and learning and such as individual oriented reference frame for achievement, contribute with strong effects; beliefs that doesn't fit to the didactic approach, do not restrain the learning.

→ To foster students' awareness concerning their beliefs on learning through elements of JOBS-program might contribute to the learning output.

6.1.6 Family context

- The groups of JOBS and Non-JOBS-students don't differ in terms of family composition nor in terms of family size and number of siblings.
- The composition of the families doesn't affect the learning output of JOBS-students.
- Perceived support and high expectations of parents have a positive influence on JOBS-students' learning output.
- Parents' education correlates negatively with JOBS-students' learning output; that means, as lower parents' education the higher the learning output of the students. So, students of parents with low education feel themselves more competent and perform their knowledge on a higher level than students of parent of higher education level.

→ Perceived parents support is a positive precondition, but not essential for students' learning output.

→ JOBS-program succeed to foster all of the students.

6.1.7 School context

- JOBS-students feel more supported by their teachers than Non-JOBS-students.
- All students perceive high expectations of their teachers concerning the relevance of their learning at school.
- Teacher support and teachers' interest motivates students; it effects their learning output.

→ Teacher support and interest on students learning is a fostering precondition for students experiencing their competencies. Perceived teacher support matters!

Summary:

JOBS-program foster students to acquire knowledge and skills. Attitudes, such as the relevance of these knowledge and skills, as well as high motivation and beliefs, fitting to the learning activities of the

program, contribute to the learning output of JOBS-program. But JOBS-program in its duration of one school-year doesn't change students' motivation and beliefs.

A positive school surrounding with teachers supporting the students and showing high expectations contribute to students' learning output.

A positive family background contributes as well, but JOBS-program works independent on students' family background.

6.2 Study B teachers

6.2.1 Students learning output

From the perspective of the teachers, the learning output of the student can be summarized as follows:

- Teachers assess the *knowledge* of the students similar as the students' assessment, but on a lower level than the students do.
- From teachers' point of view, JOBS-students' knowledge increases during the year as well, while the knowledge of Non-JOBS-students remain on the same level.
- Ratings on the *skills* of the students, JOBS-students' knowledge increased over the year, the one of the Non-JOBS-students increase slightly, but not significant.

→ From the point of view of teachers, students attending JOBS-classes show an increase of knowledge and skills, while Non-JOBS-students remain on the same level,

6.2.2 Relevance of JOBS-knowledge and JOBS-skills

- JOBS- and Non-JOBS teachers assess JOBS-knowledge and JOBS-skills as relevant.
- JOBS-teachers rate the pleasure students experience dealing with the tasks of JOBS-program as higher than Non-JOBS-teachers do. To experience the program contributes to emotional perspective (valence) on the tasks.
- JOBS-teachers assess an increasing enjoyment of their student working on the tasks presented in the learning material of JOBS-program.
- Teachers attitude towards knowledge and skills they teach are important for the progress of their students.

→ JOBS teachers attitude towards the relevance of JOBS-knowledge and JOBS-skills contribute to the learning output of their students. In addition, from teachers' point of view, students' pleasure in dealing with JOBS-tasks contribute to the learning output as well.

6.2.3 Self-concept of teachers

- JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers do not differ in their individual characteristics of self-efficacy. Concerning this characteristic, all of them have the same disposition to attend JOBS-program as a JOBS-teacher.
- Self-efficacy of JOBS-teachers is not a precondition to foster students' learning output.

→ JOBS-teaching and learning material enables JOBS-teachers to foster their students, independent of their self-efficacy as a teacher.

6.2.4 Motives

- JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers don't differ in their profile of job motivation.
- Teachers' job motivation contributes to their students' learning output.

→ Teachers' motivation matters!

6.2.5 Beliefs

- JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers don't differ in their beliefs on students' motivation to learn in school. But their belief in students' avoidance orientation is the strongest motives, followed by the motive of social approval of their achievement.
- JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers differ in their beliefs on teaching and learning. JOBS-teachers show higher marks concerning constructivist orientation and lower in transmissive ones than Non-JOBS-teachers. Over time, JOBS-teachers' constructivist orientation even increases, their transmissive orientation decreases, while Non-JOBS-teachers' orientation stays stable.
- JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers don't differ in their reference norms to evaluate achievement.
- JOBS and Non-JOBS-teachers differ in their beliefs on students' interest in learning about professions and their own strength. JOBS-teachers perceive students' interest as higher than Non-JOBS-teacher do. At the end of the year the belief on students' interest even grew higher.
- JOBS-teachers' beliefs have an impact on their assessment of students' learning output. Especially their perception of students' interests in professions and in their own strength has an impact on the learning output.

→ It seems that teachers with fitting beliefs on teaching and learning orientations are more interested in attending JOBS-program as a JOBS-teacher than the other teachers. High constructivist learning orientations fits to the teaching and learning approach of JOBS-program.

→ Experiencing the didactic approach of JOBS-program JOBS-teachers change their beliefs on effective teaching and learning beliefs towards a more student-centered approach. Constructivist beliefs on teaching and learning become stronger, transmissive ones diminish.

→ Experiencing JOBS-program let arise students' interest visible. To judge about students' interests, experiences within this subject are necessary. Teachers (JOBS- and Non-JOBS-teachers) attitude on students' motivation to learn in school differ from the one of the students. While students' motivation in learning shows the highest marks, followed by achievement orientation and avoidance orientation, teachers perceive avoidance orientation as the highest and learning orientation as the lowest.

→ To reflect own beliefs on students and expectations, based on these beliefs, would be an important task for teachers. Program of further education for JOBS-teachers could focus on it.

6.2.6 School context: cooperation and team quality

- JOBS-teachers' attitudes on the relevance of cooperation is higher than the one of Non-JOBS-teachers (subject teachers). JOBS-teachers cooperate more often within their groups with JOBS-teachers than they do within their groups of subject teachers.
- Cooperation with other teachers through planning, discussion and reflection contributes to a higher level of learning output of their students.
- Compared with other teams, JOBS-teachers evaluate the team quality of their JOBS-teams as higher. So, experiencing team-quality based on active interaction and cooperation, has an impact on the growth of team quality.

→ JOBS-teachers' higher frequency in cooperation and their attitude concerning the importance of cooperation is a positive predictor for students' learning output.

→ JOBS-program has a positive effect on the team-quality within the groups of JOBS-teachers.

6.3 Conclusion

JOBS-program matters! JOBS-students increase their knowledge and skills on professions and on their own strength and interests. This effect is identified through a knowledge test of performed knowledge, through a self-evaluation of knowledge and skills and through teachers' evaluation of students' knowledge and skills.

All of them are convinced of a high relevance of this knowledge and skills. The gained experiences are important.

Individual resources contribute to a high learning output. To motivate students and to make them experienced their influence on their own learning is essential.

Teachers, who attend to JOBS-project affiliate to it by choice. Their motivation to follow the didactic approach of JOBS-teaching and learning material is higher, their belief system fits better to it. To gain more teachers willing to involve in JOBS-program, it might be important to foster their awareness of their beliefs and attitudes as well as their competencies to teach in a student-centered approach.

A questionnaire is limited on the quality of answers, persons are giving. It is not clear, how they did understand the questions and how intensively they were thinking about their answers. To answer a questionnaire, self-awareness and metacognitive abilities are essential. In addition, social desirability as a tendency to answer the question can't be excluded.

Competence and skills to master career decisions and to find a way for the next step in professional education can't be measured by an assessment of knowledge and skills. A high learning output of JOBS-students is identified by this research study, the learning outcome is still open.

7 Interview-Study

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7.1 Introduction

The rationale for conducting the interview study was to approach, at a deeper level, the perception students have on their experiences in JOBS-program. The main focus was on the significance and utility students give to their experiences several years after they ended the JOBS program in their compulsory school time, in the light of subsequent life events and academic experiences. By conducting a qualitative study, the individual meaning can be approached in depth and placed in a much larger context of professional orientation.

We would like to express our gratitude to all those involved in the interview study, namely: the students for their availability, the teachers who facilitated our contact and meetings with the students, and to *Mihaela Potocianu* and *Mihaela Stelea* (Masters students at *Transilvania University of Braşov*), who transcribed the audio files.

7.2 Questions of the study

The main questions of the interview study were:

- Q1. What is the students' perception on their experiences in JOBS-program, few years after completing the program?
- Q2. What is students' educational and/or professional path after completing JOBS-program?
- Q3. What are the benefits students considered to have obtained as a result of participating in JOBS-program?
- Q4. What meaning do students place on learning and education about professions?

7.3 Method

7.3.1 Design and approach

To address the above-mentioned questions, *semi-structured interviews* were conducted with students who were enrolled in JOBS-program. The circular model of research process was followed in designing the interview study. This model states that theories should not be applied to the subject being studied. Theories are "discovered" and formulated in working with the field and the empirical data to be found in it. People to be studied are selected according to their relevance to the research topic. The aim of the interview study is to increase complexity by including context (Flick, 2009).

7.3.2 Sample and sampling procedure

The participants were selected from the students' database of the JOBS-RESEARCH-study. From the entire sample of 1875 students included in JOBS-RESEARCH-study (wave 1) 24 participants were selected according to their scores of the JOBS-knowledge (self-assessed). The scores were divided into three categories (high/medium/low); from each category four boys and four girls were randomly selected, two with high scores within the category and two with low scores within the category (for example, from the category medium scores of self-assessed knowledge four students were randomly selected, one boy and one girl with the highest medium scores, and one boy and one girl with the lowest medium scores). This procedure was applied to select JOBS- and Non-JOBS-students, resulting a total of 24 participants.

From the 24 students selected only nine students were included in the interview study. The rest of the students were either unreachable (contact information of some of them were valid no longer or the students had moved to a different city) or unwilling to participate in the interview study. The sample characteristics are presented in *Table 68*. All participants are from urban area.

Tab. 68. Sample description for the interview study

Code	Gender	Year of birth	School	JOBS/ Non-JOBS	Education of father	Education of mother	Occupation of father	Occupation of mother
1	M	1999	Aprily Lajos National College	JOBS	university	university	entrepreneur	controller
2	M	1997	Technical College Transporturi	JOBS	vocational school	university	car mechanic	housewife
3	M	1997	Technical College Transporturi	JOBS	highschool	highschool	n.s.	receptionist
4	F	2000	Aprily Lajos National College	JOBS	highschool	highschool	machinist	nurse
5	F	1999	Aprily Lajos National College	JOBS	not spec.	highschool	n.s.	cashier
6	M	2000	Aprily Lajos National College	Non-JOBS	highschool	highschool	engineer	housewife
7	M	2000	Aprily Lajos National College	JOBS	university	university	cashier	maseur
8	M	2000	Aprily Lajos National College	JOBS	university	university	engineer	not spec.
9	F	1996	Transilvania Technical College	JOBS	not spec.	not spec.	not spec.	not spec.

Note: not spec.=not specified

7.3.3 Data collection

All selected students were contacted by phone and asked to participate in the interview study (phone number were provided by schools' principals). During the phone calls, they were informed about: the name and role of the interviewer in the Jobs program, the topic of the interview, the duration and the place of the interview, the fact that participation is voluntary and does not include any benefits or risks for the participant. The date and hour of the interview were agreed over the phone with participants giving consent.

At the beginning of each interview, informed consent for audio-recording was obtained from participants. Eight participants gave consent for audio recording, and only one participant gave consent for video recording. Recording of the interviews started after the participants told their names. Interviews took place in two locations: *Transilvania* University of Braşov, Building K and Colegiul Tehnic de

Transporturi Braşov. All interviews were conducted by the same interviewer. Interviews lasted between 15 and 35 minutes.

The *interview guide* (see Annex 1) includes a set of 15 open-ended questions, organized in the following order: introductory questions (example of question: *Describe me a past or present experience you would like to remember, an aspect of your life that you consider to be important.*); perception on JOBS program (example of question: *Let's assume you meet a friend who tells you "I heard you participated in JOBS programs. What is JOBS?" What would you tell him?*); importance of JOBS (example of question: *Taking into consideration all your experiences from the past year and how you stand now, what do you think NOW about JOBS?*); learning outcome (example of question: *What did you learn in JOBS?*); benefits (example of question: *From what you learned in Jobs, what did help you?*); satisfaction with JOBS (example of questions: *What would you recommend to further keep in JOBS?*); importance of learning about professions (example of question: *How can one learn something about the world of jobs in schools?*); and closing questions.

7.3.4 Data transcript and transformation

Audio files were transcript by two masters' students. Audio files and transcripts were named using participants' codes (numbers). The lines in each transcript file were numbered and the number of the questions from the interview guide were added to the transcripts.

Data analysis was made in Romanian language for each case. In description of cases, anchor examples were chosen and translated into English. In translating the anchor examples close attention was given to ensuring equivalence of content. Idiomatic expressions and slang in Romanian were translated into English language so that their meaning to be similar, but it was not always possible to make a literally translation. The anchor examples presented in description of cases have references to the code of the interview and the lines from the transcripts corresponding to the fragment included.

7.3.5 Data analysis

Data obtained from the interviews were analyzed using *case-oriented strategy of data analysis* (Huberman & Miles, 1998), which is best suited for identifying invariant patterns common to relatively small sets of cases (Ragin, 1987). The strategy involves analysis of the first case and development of an analytical model. After that, researches move to the discovery of the model for the next case and examine comparatively the models. The matching of the patterns is looked for and, also, if new cases share the previous configurations.

In our study, each case was examined as a whole, as a total situation resulting from a combination of conditions, and cases were compared with each other as wholes. This strategy was chosen due to the small number of cases in order to meet the strategy of interpreting specific cases and pinpointing the combinations of conditions and causal complexes. Such combinations are expected to produce specific outcomes. Thus, the different parts or conditions that make up a case are understood in relation to each other. They are considered together as composing a single situation about different issues such as: perceived experience in JOBS program, educational and professional route, benefits of the program, meaning of learning and education about professions.

The *text working strategy* was the *coding of the material* with the purpose of creating categories and developing theories (Flick, 2009). To gain methodological triangulation *two procedures of the theoretical coding* were used – open coding and axial coding – (Strauss & Corbin, 1990) and also the *thematic coding procedure*, developed by Flick (2009). Thematic coding is suitable for comparative studies in which the groups under study are derived from the research aims and thus defined *a priori*. The underlying assumption is that, in different social groups, differing views about professional orientation can

be found. In order to assess this assumption and to develop a theory of such groups' specific ways of seeing and experiencing the world of professions, a multi-stage procedure, described hereunder, was applied.

In the first stage of analysis we have addressed the cases involved, becoming familiar with our data, and we have produced a description of each participant to better organize the data and to follow individual narratives; these case profiles were continuously re-checked and modified if necessary during the further interpretation of the case. We described a case after reading the whole transcript of that interview. A case description includes several elements with regard to the research aims (e.g., gender, age, class, school, profile, hobbies, extracurricular activities and the central topics mentioned by the interviewee concerning the research issue).

In the second phase of analysis, for elaborating the categories system, we used open coding actions to identify themes, categories and subcategories. The interviews transcripts were examined closely by a team of two researchers knowledgeable about vocational training. Open coding is the first procedure of the theoretical coding (Strauss & Corbin, 1990). We generated initial codes that were applied to the data set after reading line by line the transcript. These initial codes described what we were reading. Codes featuring similar contents were grouped together, yielding themes that described, for example: significant life experiences, plans for the future, learning situations about the world of professions, meaning of learning and work and so on. We have identified anchor examples from the text to reflect those themes, categories and subcategories. The next step involved individual reviewing and refining the main themes, categories and subcategories.

In the third phase of analysis, we systematically coded transcripts using the coding scheme established in the previous stage. Coders carefully reviewed all transcripts to capture any additional comments regarding the themes and categories identified.

The coders then met to discuss the themes, categories and subcategories, retaining those with high cross-reviewer overlap, and looking for agreement in revising and refining the themes with lower overlap; the two coders have sometimes named differently the codes emerged from the texts, because of their different theoretical background. During this process, repeated for each transcript, they discussed each alternative name and choose a name for the category that was closer to the words of participants. Because qualitative methodology is an ongoing "back-and-forth" process between theory and the data (Berg, 2007), changes or additions to the coding scheme were adopted as appropriate during this stage. This iterative process of induction and deduction was performed until all coders (two coders and two supervisors) have agreed on a set of themes.

A thematic structure results from this cross-check, which underlies the analysis of further cases in order to increase their comparability.

The process of theoretical coding of data continued with the axial coding procedure. "Axial coding is the process of relating subcategories to a category. It is a complex process of inductive and deductive thinking involving several steps. These are accomplished, as with open coding, by making comparisons and asking questions. However, in axial coding the use of these procedures is more focused, and geared toward discovering and relating categories in terms of the paradigm model" (Strauss & Corbin, 1990, p. 114). In this phase, we selected the categories most relevant to the research aims and we identified relations between the different axial categories using the parts of a coding paradigm: cause-effect, temporal, or local conditions, strategies, consequences. From the multitude of initial categories were selected those that seemed to be most promising for further elaboration. In axial coding, the researcher asks questions to discover relations. The coding paradigm suggested by Strauss (1987, pp. 27-28) was taken as a starting point for deriving the following key questions:

1. Conditions: What led to the situation? What aspects of the background contribute? What course of events?
2. Interaction among the actors: Who acted? What happened?

3. Strategies and tactics: What ways of handling situations were adopted, e.g., avoidance, adaptation?

4. Consequences: What changed? To what consequences, results? (Flick, 2009).

The next step was thematic coding procedure (Flick, 2009) consisting in identifying the comparative dimensions across cases, common aspects and differences between the participants. The developed thematic structure also served for comparing cases (e.g., for elaborating correspondences and differences between the various cases in the study). The dimensions chosen for comparison were: meanings of learning, meanings of work, roles of professions and future intentions. Based on these dimensions, all cases were analyzed and described using a narrating style. The resulting patterns were then analyzed and interpreted based on the research aims.

7.4 Results

7.4.1 Description of cases

Case 1

"We don't always do things to help us, but to help others."

The interviewee is a 16 years old boy, who attended the JOBS program. At the time of the interview, he was a 10th grade student in a National College. Both of his parents have university level education, his father being an entrepreneur and his mother a financial controller.

The boy plays handball as professional player in a local sport club, but merely mentions the activity.

As a significant life experience, the student discusses about the math contests he participated and, especially, about his highest achievement in such a contest *"when I was in the 7th grade, I won 100 points"* (I.1, L.11) *"it was the maximum score"* (I.1, L.12). The experience was motivating as currently he still participates in such contests and in math after-school classes. Alongside these contests, the student named his professors as a factor of influence in his professional route. The influence of teachers is described as directive *"during school, teachers have told us what to do"* (I.1, L.29).

His plans for the future include two professional alternatives, but the students gave little attention to the matter: *"there were some thought about which faculty to go to, but nothing definitively"* (I.1, L.20-21); *"I either go to informatics ... and, if not, medicine would be another alternative"* (I.1, L.23-24). The alternatives are still uncertain. His interest is based on pleasure and curiosity. In informatics, he mentions several experiences when he had the chance to prove his skills by solving other colleagues' problems related to use of computers.

Learning is seen by the student as a result of the learning situations he experienced, mostly based on memory. He emphasizes that remembering is the key to learning: *"learning is what is left after something happened, for example after reading a book one remembers what the character did, how he acted [...] the same is in school [...] they teach us a lesson and what is left after is what you have learned. If you forget it means that you haven't learn it properly."* (I.1, L.76-80). The student considers that learning in school was useful in his case for broadening his understanding of things.

For the interviewed student, the profession of individuals contributes greatly to the welfare of the community rather than the individual wealth *"for a person it does not have great importance, but, for example, for a bigger community [...] in a town, is very important to have a butcher, for example"* (I.1, L.116-117). The main function of getting a profession is for this student to help others.

Regarding the JOBS program, the student remembers the tasks he had to fulfill in the program, but also the emotions attached to those tasks. He remembers having to take on interview to an employee, an experience described as interesting but for which he felt fear as the situation is uncertain *"you don't know what [the employee] will answer and what else to ask him"* (I.1, L.42-43). Other remembered

tasks were: identifying personal strengths and weaknesses, drawing diagrams with personal interests. These tasks are now considered as being difficult but solvable.

The overall description of JOBS program is that it contributed in preparing students for the future. The benefits of the program are named as skills developed “[JOBS] *teach you how to take an interview, how to behave (...) what to do, to identify the good parts and the bad parts of a thing, to know your advantages*” (I.1, L32-34). Another mentioned benefit of the JOBS program in the opinion of this student is the gain in motivation for personal development, for planning the future, and for attempts to gain work experience. The program offered opportunities for the students to better know themselves and to plan their future, “*I still have classmates who don’t know what they will do and I cannot imagine how this is possible, but the answer is that they weren’t part in this project and didn’t have such an experience*” (I.1, L.58-59).

The JOBS experiences are very well delimited for this boy from any other form of learning situation about the world of profession, which are not clearly mentions. He stresses the need of a mentor in learning about professions. The role of the adult mentor, or the teacher playing this role, would be “*to help or to push forward*” (I.1, L.104-105), to answer questions and to lead the team of learning students.

For this interview pleasure and the opportunity to help others are key aspects in choosing and performing a profession. His perception of work is strongly connected with helping others while doing works task out of pleasure. JOBS programs contributed, as he stated, both to the development of pleasure, but also of self-knowledge and motivation. In this case, the attendance in the program is stated as significant in shaping the future as students gain insight into their own strengths and weaknesses and into the need to further develop.

Case 2

"Without well-defined team, without workforce, and without the necessary studies, you cannot do what you want."

The interviewee is a boy, aged 17, of Romanian ethnicity, who attended the JOBS program. At the time of the interview, he was studying in a technical highschool, at Technician in transportation profile, in the 11th grade. He comes from a two-parent family; his father had graduated a vocational school and works as an auto mechanic and his mother, with a university degree, is a housewife.

He likes: music, dance, extreme sports such as cycling and rollerblading. In his private life, he considers himself as “*...crazier type. The thunderstruck kind*” (I.2, L.24) and in the school area he describes himself in the following terms “*a calm nature. I sit, listen, I have no problems with anyone. If there's ever a problem to bother me, I say my point of view, look, I say my opinion*” (I.2, L.26-27). He has gained professional experience in various places (restaurant, car wash, car service), from each situation he declared having learned valuable lessons about the world of professions.

As a significant life experience, the student discusses about the practical placement in a car service: “*I’ve got what I like, mechanics. When I saw how many operations are, how to make [them], I realized that is not as easy as I thought*” (I.2, L.9-10). He had looked at this situation as a way to test if he has enough interests and abilities to continue on this path: “*And I said, let's have the patience to see it's for me or it's not for me.*” (I.2 L.10). He spent time with his father at work, opportunity which, together with curiosity and personal interest for car mechanics, has developed his knowledge and practical skills and marked his decisions about professional route. This passion had materialized in the present extracurricular activities: “*... I got to have some kind of car service with some friends [...], I work with two boys, among which is the one whose yard is. We work two, three, four cars a week, but we do moneys for us, and generally, I also teach them something about car, because they have just entered into the mechanics, they are passionate, but do not know ... not have so much knowledge*” (I.2, L.11-17).

In the case of this student we encounter well-defined plans for the future on the medium and long term. It all started with a passion, tested during an internship, and then continued through extracurricular activities in which he engaged his friends with the same interests. In the chosen professional field, he intends, as a first step, to deepen his knowledge and skills by employment in a car service from another country, to accumulate capital which, thereafter, he will invest in opening his own business: *"I want to go to England, I have a friend, the boss of my father, who is there in a car service... I want to go there, to work and to stay there ... for a while ... and after a year or two, as time passes, slowly I want to come home and open a small business to turn somewhere up.... "* (I.2, L.49-52).

Learning is regarded by the student as a process that begins when you do not have any knowledge/ you do not know how to do something and is characterized by the novelty of tasks that you have to perform, *"learning is ...to do things that we've never done before. I take everything from scratch...when I know nothing"* (I.2, L.139-140).

For the interviewed student, defining the profession is closely linked to achieve professionalism in a particular field *"for me, to have a profession means ...to be good at one thing and that one thing... to explore "* (I.2, L.208-209).

Regarding the factors that favor the fulfillment of the tasks at work, he focuses on those related to the employee, namely: the activism *"I have conquered all in the first three weeks. I was simply very active "* (I.2, L.150-151), teamwork, professionalism in performing the tasks, customer focus *"to do so to finish even faster, and customer to be satisfied and do everything by the book"* (I.2, L.178-179), curiosity *"let's find out, to see how it goes, why it goes, how can I make it look good, how can I change it, how can it be changed, what do I need to change"* (I.2, L.210-211).

The student presents JOBS program with respect to its objectives: *"We can actually learn what a job is, what means to immerse in the profession"* (I.2, L.65-66), demystifying the superficial perception that an outside party has about a particular profession: *"... through JOBS you can find what is happening behind the curtain, [...] what happens in the back, how things are really done things that we all seen so easy"* (I.2, L.66 -68). Beyond forming a realistic picture of the complex tasks involved by different occupations, JOBS program gave him the opportunity to discover the importance of a cohesive team in the success of any good work *"anywhere in a field there is a team. If you have a well-defined team... that area is going well"* (I.2, L.98-99). His professional experience, gained in different work contexts, has helped him reaching the same conclusion: *"if we work as a team and everything went well, each of us has an advantage"* (I.2, L.130-131), *"And that is why I decided to do my all studies, to develop a good team ... to be able to fulfill my dream, to be able to have come up somewhere"* (I.2, L.135-137).

For this student, teamwork is one of the most pleasant memories about the program: *"the more, and the more I liked in Jobs, is that we always were working in teams, we were always a good team"* (I.2 L.78-79). Also, the specific program activities are brought into the discussion, the task of conducting a professional interview being a significant experience for this boy. Overall evaluation of the program has been positive, with emphasis on its utility *"is a very interesting and very enjoyable project, because many of us do not know what, in fact, work means. [...] The thing we have learned is that not everything is that easy"* (I.2, L.87-92).

The types of tasks, received by students in the JOBS program, are appreciated by the student, too: *"to keep interviews, projects when students must go to the field...in a field of work, to actually learn what that work means"* (I.2, L.187-189). Suggestions for improving this type of learning experience refers rather to specific additions, such as an internship, *"I would really recommend to do JOBS kind of practice ... kind ... one-day practice "*(I.2, L.189-190)

Professional plans for the future that are clearly contoured and the attitude toward learning and working have been generated both by the experiences gained in various jobs and by participation in the JOBS program, but, above all, by certain personal characteristics of this young person such as: dynamism, initiative spirit, passion for a particular professional field, a proactive attitude and curiosity for novelty.

Case 3

“...in Romania one works for everyday living. Abroad one works out of pleasure and for building a family.”

The interviewed person, is an 18-year boy, former participant in the JOBS project. At the time of the interview he was a highschool student in a technical college, in the 11th grade. Previously he graduated from a professional school. He comes from an organized family, his father being a professional driver and his mother is working as a receptionist.

The significant life events that he mentioned are the moment when he obtained the driving licence and the working period in construction *“During the summer I’ve been with my uncle in Bucharest, we put metal roof [on houses]”* (I.3, L.8). This experience had had a powerful impact on his attitudes towards work.

Among the factors that contributed to his educational route, the student mentions his parents, especially the father, whom he follows on the professional track. He describes the parents’ role as a guiding one: *“my parents guided me mostly, my mother and, especially, my father through his words and what he is guiding me to do”* (I.3, L.38-39).

Regarding the future, the boy is uncertain. He takes into consideration multiple options (going to university, working in a car service, working in a foreign country, doing a bartender course), but none of these option is detailed or taken seriously. His plans for the future are vague and highly contextual: *“if I will pass the baccalaureate, I’m thinking of going to the university or to a college...if I have possibilities. If not, I will find myself a nice and favorable workplace”* (I.3, L.22-23), *“...multiple options but none too punctual. I also want to make a course as bartender and more [options]”* (I.3, L.31-32).

Learning is seen rather as an informal process, gained in interaction with other persons: *“One can learn from a person, what he/she is doing, what he/she is thinking”* (I.3, L. 61). He emphasizes the informal learning rather than formal education: *“learning is not necessarily reading from a book”* (I.3, L.61).

The student considers work and profession as a mean for earning financial gains necessary for satisfying personal needs: *“If we wouldn’t have a job, we could not make money, we would not have from what to live, to buy [...] food....”* (I.3, L.86-87). He differentiates between working in Romania and working abroad: *“...in Romania you work for living from one day to another. Abroad you work out of pleasure and for making a family. In Romania, you just sustain your family with an insufficient amount”* (I.3, L.70-72). This idea inflicts his future plans. The role of professions is also strongly related, for the student, with earning money: *“[...] what you do, do better so you can make a progress, promote. Earn more money.”* (I.3, L.81-82).

The general perception of JOBS program that the students holds is strongly based on the perceived utility of the program: *“[JOBS] showed us what is work and, at least, helped us to understand what is a job”* (I.3, L.43-44). Besides that, other benefits of participating in JOBS were related to interpersonal skill *“to be ok with persons you meet, not to be that type...egoist or aloof”* (I.3, L.50), *“to handle situations, wherever I go”* (I.3, L.57) and to job adjustment *“[JOBS] helped me to adjust to the workplace...”* (I.3, L.67). The boy remembers specific tasks in JOBS program: taking an interview and making posters to present a desired profession. He also mentions working in teams and involvement of more students as relevant aspects regarding JOBS program.

Learning about professional world in school is possible through practical placement: *“this thing [practical placement] helps. Because one can see what is happening at a specific job”* (I.3, L. 92). Also, he considers that learning about professions depends greatly on the students, mentioning ambition and behavioral problems as influencing factors in learning: *“Depends on the character of the student. If he is good, if he is ambitious, if he has or not problems in school...”* (I.3, L.95-96).

The student is highly uncertain about his future educational and professional route. His attitudes towards education and work are sometime contradictory, either highly contextual (dependent of situational and social factors), either highly dispositional (dependent of internal factors). Mainly, he emphasizes the role of opportunities in shaping the future. The benefits of JOBS program are presented in terms of knowledge about specific professions and social skills.

Case 4

"I found out that if I learn it's better, I can get a better job."

The interviewee is a 15-year-old girl, involved in JOBS program. At the time of the interview she was studying in a high school with economic specialization, in the 11th grade. She comes from an organized family, both her parents have medium education level, the father works as a machinist and the mother as a nurse.

She describes herself as enjoying singing, dancing, playing basketball, and spending time with friends. In the past, she was a member in the school choir and played basketball, a sport she is still practicing.

As significant life experiences, the student names basketball trainings and the felt joy at the beginning of trainings *"...when I start practicing basketball, I was the happiest [person] in the world"* (I.4, L.28), the talks with the coach who offered her useful information for her future plans *"I was at training and the teacher told us that he receives a high wage, works not very hard, that it's easier to stay few hours in the gym [...] rather than staying in a factory for twelve hours [...]. And that helped me a lot to think"* (I.4, L.68-71).

During her school years, in difficult or decisive moments, she received the social support from her teachers and friends *"The teachers helped me a lot, because they gave me special attention, they taught many things. I had really nice teachers. and friends very much, because they were next to me when needed"* (I.4, L.23-25).

Constant practice of a sport had an important role in planning the professional and educational route and in taking a definitive decision: *"In the future I would like to finish a faculty of sports and to become basketball coach ..."* (I.4, L.32-33), *"... I decided to become coach"* (I.4, L.66).

These plans are the result of learning situations about the world of professions. The student mentions about the context of extra-curricular sport activities, but also about involvement in the JOBS program as being significant in learning about the world of professions. She stated that in program *"...I learnt many things about jobs, about people working there, how they get along, about [...] team spirit"* (I.4, L.38-40). A different learning situation was the discussion with members of her social network *"they told me....my parents, my godmother told me that it's much easier to learn in these few years [of high-school], which are fundamental for life, rather than not learning and work in a very bad environment"* (I.4, L.76-78). The interviewee defines learning by its results *"...knowing many things about ... different situations"* (I.4, L.93).

When talking about work, the girl names the following factors as having a positive influence on job tasks fulfilment: work engagement *"to give everything that is possible"* (I.4, L.129), financial rewards *"a very important role also have the wages"* (I.4, L.126), teamwork *"...to work a lot in a team, I have something with teamwork"* (I.4, L.130-131), friendly attitude towards colleagues *"...not to fight with someone in the workplace, because it's no good at all....to be friendly [that is] very important..."* (I.4, L.129-130). On the other hand, arrogance is seen as a disruptive factor of work relationships.

The evaluative perception on JOBS program is rather a general positive image of JOBS: *"It is interesting.... we learn many things"* (I.4, L.42). She emphasizes the utility of the program *"...I think that every class in the school should learn do this..."* (I.4, L.156-157).

For her, the most significant memories about JOBS program are related to learning context: *“I remember that we played a lot with the teachers. We had a teacher that taught Romanian, she was also in charge [of JOBS] and we were always laughing and smiling, drawing, doing interesting project”* (I.4, L.45-46).

The JOBS tasks are, in the perception of the interviewee, very new and, despite obstacles in fulfilling them, interesting, funny, challenging: *“We had to draw the map of Braşov, the streets of Braşov, and the rout we had to follow. So that was...fun”* (I.4, L.48-49).

Regarding the personal benefits from this program, the student considers that she improved her team working skills *“I learnt a lot, firstly I learnt how to work in a team [...] I was like, single...I did not want to talk with someone and so...I’ve learnt”* (I.4, L.64). In her perspective, the most appreciated aspect of JOBS-program the one regarding students’ involvement in teamwork *“teamwork should be kept, not to allow people to work separately, teamwork is very important”* (I.4, L107-108).

For the described case, practicing sport, the social network and involvement in JOBS programs played the significant roles in making educational and professional plans and in forming attitude towards learning and work.

Case 5

„I learn only what I believe I will need in life.”

The interviewed student is a 16 years old Hungarian ethnic girl, member of JOBS group. She is a student in a Hungarian language thought college, in economics specialization, in 10th grade. She comes from a single-parent family, her mother graduating high school level studies and working as a sales person. At the time of the interview, the student was involved in a romantic relationship.

She likes to read and sing, and work with young children and to write. In the past, she took dance lessons. As a significant life experience, she brings into conversation her romantic relationship.

Regarding the factors that had an influence on her school course, she mentioned the social support offered by her teachers at different times, and her own effort to fulfill school’ tasks in the last period of time.

The student does not place much attention on her future education and professional path, revealing vague ideas about her professional outcome: *„something with young children. I don’t know, teacher.... Yes’, something like that”* (I.5, L.38-39).

In the case of this student, learning is seen as a tool in order to achieve a practical outcome. She learns only what she believes is useful in life in order to move ahead and what presents an interest to her: *„ I learn only what I believe I will need in life. So, in math I don’t learn everything, because I know that I won’t need it. I only learn to pass the exam [she’s laughing]. Only that much. And what interests me, I learn, but anything else, not much”* (I.5, L. 93-95). She defines learning focusing on the results of the process: *„To learn? Well, [means] to knows something.”* (I.5, L. 93)

Among the factors that favors the accomplishment of work tasks, she identifies: judiciousness, responsibility, patience, creativity and financial compensation: *“...in every work place we have to be careful in what and how we are doing things, because we have a responsibility. And we have to be very patient (...), hmm... and creative, if we are in a work place that requires creativity”* (I.5, L.82-84), *“...now in these times, also to earn money.”* (I.5, L.133).

Regarding the profession system, the student underlines the need of diversity: *“I need both, a policeman and a firefighter, we need an accountant very much, and many other professions.”* (I.5, L.127-128). Moreover, she mentions that professions have a role in the society.

For her, the JOBS program had the following objectives: *"JOBS helps us to know more about the working possibilities, about jobs, it helps us to write a CV and to go for an interview, and how the interview takes place"* (I.5, L.48-49). She emphasizes the need of students to receive vocational guidance: *"...we really need to know about jobs, because there are another two more years and we have to work, if it is possible."* (I.5, L.72-73).

The learning process in the JOBS program is presented as innovative, different from other experiences before, and the tasks were pleasant: *"We learn in a different way. They [teachers] do not teach us lessons, just to write in a notebook.... We learn but we also have fun and receive grades."* (I.5, L.153-155). The general perception over JOBS is summarized in a positive light *"...it is good, it really helps."* (I.5, L.71).

For the student, the most accessible memories about the program were those on specific activities, such as the projects, the diagrams, the interviews, and also the discussion themes: *"I know that we did diagrams, I'm not sure that we did CVs, but I know that we did interviews"* (I.5, L.51-52).

The significant and recalled situation was the task which required to complete a project presenting a job. Describing the project, the student is able to talk about the content of the task, the context in which she did the task, and the themes of the dialogue during the interviews she organized with employees.

Considering the positive effect of the program, the student highlights the important role of individualized feed-back received: *"...when we end a project, the teacher said to us what we did well and what not. And from these I learn."* (I.5, L.97-98). Another positive effect is the obtaining of complex information on many diverse professions: *"I learned a lot about jobs, because we were in teams and each of us went to a different work place. They made one [presented], others another one and we learned from each other."* (I.5, L.76-79). Also, the student declared that being part of JOBS contributed to training of transferable competences for other subjects (how to make a project, how to make a presentation): *"When we have to make a project in history or in other subject, we learned in JOBS how to do it and then I do it better."* (I.5, L.98-100).

In her perspective, the most appreciated activity is the one related with completing an interview with employees, recommending that the program to be kept as it is: *"Everything, absolutely everything to remain the same."* (I.5, L.110).

The student's attitudes on learning involves more the usefulness of the knowledge and not a cognitive curiosity. She chooses to pass certain subjects on the minimum levels of the requirements (such as math) and engage more in the learning activities that rise her the interest and brings her useful information for life. She has a few hobbies but do not display interest for extra-curricular activities organize in formal settings. These characteristics alongside with the lack of significant life experience that can develop the drive for challenge seem to be related with the lack of coherent plans for future academic and professional path. The involvement in JOBS program appear to be the only learning opportunities she encounters about professions world.

Case 6: Non-JOBS student

"It's better to learn first and then to start work."

The interviewee is a 15 years old boy, student in the 9th grade in Economics specialization in a theoretical highschool. He comes from an organized family, both his parents having medium level education. His father works as an engineer, while his mother is housewife.

The boy describes himself as being a people person, friendly, enjoying spending time with friends or colleagues. He mentions bicycling and going out with friends among his free time activities. A significant life event he mentions is a trip abroad, *"I like to discover what is in the world"* (I.6, L.31-32).

His educational option for the specialization he currently attends (Economics) was marked by the low grades: *"I had low admission grade and no other option. On one hand, I wanted [to attend the specialization], on the other I didn't."* (I.6, L.19-20). He considers this specialization to be difficult. For this boy, the teachers' support is a significant factor that impacts his educational path, *"...the teachers are nice and they always help us study"* (I.6, L.22).

The student does not place much attention on his future education and professional path, revealing undefined options: *"I thought of studying Management, since I'm here [at Economics specializations] I could open my own firm* [I.6, L.26-27].

Regarding learning, the interviewee ambiguously differentiates between the learning process and the learning outcomes. The learning process implies the "learning by error" strategy, *"one needs to learn by himself from mistakes. Not to do the same thing twice..."* (I. 6, L.74-75). The motivation for learning is pleasure, *"Even if we do not attend the specialization we want, we should still learn what we like"* (I.6, L. 79-80). The learning outcomes are personal benefits, *"to be a better person"* (I.6, L.76) and avoiding social disapproval *"not to be looked by people as being the 'don't know how' person, not to be talked behind"* (I.6, L.76-77).

Unlike learning which implies *"mental [effort]"* (I.6, L.84), work is seen by the boy as being mechanical *"let's say you are at work, and you have to do all the papers and everything"* (I.6, L.83). Work is based on learning to do something specific, *"We learn how to do a firm... We need to learn the basic steps"* (I.6, L.88), *"It's better to learn first and then to start work [...] It's better to know a basic thing"* (I.6, L.99-100).

Learning about professions world is possible, in the view of the boy, in school: *"I truly think that the lessons teachers give us are not for nothing. If we learn them, then we must use them"* (I.6, L.95-96), but also from discussion with adults, parents, friends, persons working in the same domain *"[one could learn by] going to certain persons who graduated and to ask. Through these questions I guess you can learn a lot"* (I.6, L.106-107).

The student perception on JOBS program is based on his interaction with students attending the program, whom he asked, *[JOBS] is a very interesting project. It really helps you to better know about professions. Some persons express their opinion about [that profession], what is good to do and what is not, what he likes and what he doesn't"* (I.6, L.51-53). Among the activities he mentions as part of JOBS are taking an interview with an employee and team work. The benefits of the program for the participants, in his view, are at professional and interpersonal level: *"How to adapt to a workplace. How to be in good relations with someone"* (I.6, L.57).

Even though he did not participate in JOBS, the student has several recommendations for the Program: *"[you should] not go to just a company, but to two or three and in each company to learn what is like. [...]. Not just on one line, you need more information. [...] From one company, you find out an opinion, from a different company another opinion, and this way you can understand better"* (I.6, L.129-132).

For this case, interactions and discussion with others seem to be the significant form of learning, both in academic context and about professions world. Teachers, parents and adults who graduated a similar specialization or work in a similar domain are social actors relevant for learning about professions. The boy has an unclear view of his educational and professional path and place little emphasis on this aspect, as well. Learning is the base for work, but learning involves mental effort while work involves rather routine and mechanical abilities. From his answers, it is obvious that students participating in JOBS program shared their experiences with other colleagues. The boy knows about specific activities performed in JOBS (like taking an interview to an employed person) and has pertinent opinions about the Program and the activities within.

Case 7

“The most important experience is friendship.”

The interviewee is a 17 years old boy, student in the 11th grade at the Economics specialization at a theoretical highschool. He comes from an organized family; both his parents having university degrees. His father works as cashier, and his mother as a masseur. During the interview, the boy answered in very short sentences and needed supplementary questions to approach a theme.

The educational path of the student was marked by different options in diverse domain. He wanted to study Biology as specialization in highschool but he was not admitted in that class (he does not mention the reason), so he attends Economics. For the future, he is considering Psychology as a professional option *“Because I love to talk with people, to understand their feeling and to help them.”* (I.7, L.24). The boy mentions friendship as the significant life experience for his. He names a friend as being his oldest and dearest friend.

He describes his school experience as *“very easy nice”* (I.7, L.18), having the opportunity to *“learn a lot about life”* (I.7, L.20). Giving his current studies in Economics, he considers that the main role of a profession is to make money and, sequent, to satisfy basic needs *“for example, you need aliments to live”* (I.7, L.98).

The interviewee defines the JOBS Program though its title, *“Firstly, what JOBS means: JOBS Orientation for Business and School”* (I.7, L.39). He remembers one specific task in the program, taking an interview to an employed person, namely, a woman working in a grocery store. He clearly remembers the questions he addressed and the answers *“I asked the woman about how she feels, if she is ok with the firm, if she wants another job”* (I.7, L.46-47). He also names team work, brainstorming, and diagrams as other activities performed in JOBS.

The benefits of the JOBS program are presented by the student in general terms, stating that the program *“helps you if you study economy...”* (I.7, L.40), it is useful *“for all those who study economics. And for life, especially for life”* (I.7, L.73), and teaches you that *“life is hard”* (I.7, L.61). Still, in reflective manner, the boy mentions more specific benefits of the program, related to his school learning: *“...the advantage of this firm is that is a non-stop store and they don’t have competitors”* (I.7, L.49), *“If I don’t enter Psychology, I thought that I could start working in sales and marketing, choosing a place without competitors and where are people, buyers”* (I.7, L.63-64). The perspective on the gains of JOBS program is rather pragmatic and contextual.

The personal benefits that he mentions are *“to trust myself when asking questions”* (I.7, L.66) and *“to be polite”* (I.7, L.111), *“to respect the decisions of others”* (I.7, L.87). Communication is considered to be a gain from the JOBS program that will help him in his future career. He remembers with pleasure about working in a team and about brainstorming. He recommends that students’ activity in JOBS should be graded because *“it is more interesting than all [school subject]”* (I.7, L.89).

Regarding the opportunities, a student has for learning about professions world, the boy emphasizes the necessity to attend the JOBS program. Other means for this are studying economics or *“reading something on the Internet and that will solve everything”* (I.7, L.102).

The boy representing case 7 has a clear and motivated perspective on his future professional path, his option being influenced solely by his interest in the domain and by the value he places in helping others and in friendship. Past or present school experiences don’t seem to have a significant impact in his decision about the future. Regarding the JOBS programs, the boy has very precise memories about the activities made in the program. He states the benefits of the program in general terms, stressing the utility of JOBS for future life, in general.

Case 8

“Working means being totally present in what you do ...”

The interviewee is a 14 years old boy. At the time of the interview he was a freshmen high school student, in 9th grade, at Mathematics and Informatics specialization. He comes from an organized family; both his parents have university degrees. His father works as engineer, no information about the profession of the mother were collected.

The boy practices sportive dance during his free time, an activity that marked his past significant life experiences and also his perspective over future career. One of the most important memories is related to this experience, in a national dance contest *“when we heard that we will be in the final among first six [competitors], and our teacher began to cry of happiness and everybody was sending ovations...”* (I.8, L.27-29). The experience of achieving a high performance after a hard investment is significant for the: *“we trained a lot just for the fun of training and we reached fifth place at national level”* (I.8, L.23-24).

The boy is strongly motivated in achieving performance also in school. He chose the best class to attend in high school and he mentions that the quality of teaching in this specialization was decisive for his decision to study Mathematics and Informatics.

The perspective of the future is clear and consistent articulated despite the young age of the interviewee, *“I would like to be a Math teacher”* (I.8, L.11). The professional route is built on the interest on the subject (*“in eight grade I started to like mathematics a lot”* (I.8, L.10)), on the pleasure in working with children (*“I like to teach kids, to give them what I know”* (I.8, L.31-32)), but also on the experience of a close family member (*“my brother also studies Mathematics and Informatics”* (I.8, L.13).

Regarding learning, the boy refers to the process of learning: *“Learning means to learn what is important, essential in the shortest possible time”* (I.8, L.132) and to the outcome of learning: *“to understand”* (I.8, L.137). Paying attention during classes is an effective strategy of learning, *“...if you are paying attention during class, you understand the lesson because the way of teaching is very good”*. (I.8, L.137-138).

Work is seen by the interviewee as a pleasure as long as a person works in a field he/she likes. Given this condition, working always implies reaching a purpose, a finality: *“Working means being totally present in what you do, and if you started something not to stop half-way even if [...] distractions are present, to move on and to take your idea to the end, to take your project to the end”* (I.8, L.140-143). Regarding the perception on the role of professions, the boy mentions that the nature of this role is to contribute to a common good: *“each profession has the role to do something in common. Each [person] does his job and then something, a unitary whole comes out. [...] if everybody does his job, everything comes perfect. If a piece is missing from this cycle then the project has no role, it won't be finished.”* (I.8, L.145-1438).

According to the interviewee, the best way for a student to learn about the world of professions is by practical placement, which could offer the possibility to apply knowledge.

The student refers to the JOBS Program mainly through the novelty of the type of learning implied by the program: *“It was something new, there were much more pictures, we were learning in a different way, we were more creative...”* (I.8, L.39-40). The memories related to JOBS are emotion-based for the boy: *“I remember how we were always joyful ...”* (I.8, L.43). His memories about JOBS activities and tasks are rich in details. For each presented activity, the student presents its finality: *“[They] told us that it was the best project”* (I.8, L.64).

The outcomes of the project are mentioned by the interviewee at different levels. One level is represented by the perceived gains in terms of personal skills: *“...I found out that I can communicate very well, I can present and I can plan, I can be, let's say, a boss, I have the quality to organize”* (I.8, L.71-72),

"...this year I developed a quality of mine [...] that I can have many relations and I can find out in no time something important" (I.8, L.88-89).

A second level at which the benefits are stated by the interview is the group level: *"...through JOBS, we, as class, became very cohesive. [...] we ended to understand each other" (I.8, L.47).*

The third level is represented by the motivational level: *"...I remember that at some point, we had to search who earns more, [...], which are the top professions..." (I.8, L.81-82), "[that] made us to want more, to reach higher" (I.8, L.95).* Competition is mentioned as also being motivating: *"...in the class there was such a competition, who does better..." (I.8, L.46-47).*

The last level at which are mentioned benefits is the teachers level: *"And the teachers evolved, it seem to me ... its noticeable, I notice that they progressed" (I.8, L.166).*

For this boy, the extracurricular activities he performs shape his attitude towards learning and working. The experiences in these activities are strongly significant and success in them is based on effort and training. From his perspective, making effort and being totally involved in the task is the key for success in the JOBS tasks, but also in work in general. Competition is also stimulating in developing new skills. Planning the future is based not only on the described experiences, but also on the experiences of significant others and on the support of teachers.

Case 9

"...[learning means] a thing I saw in someone else and I wanted to do it also, to progress, to do it as good as possible"

The interviewee is a 19 years old girl, participant in the JOBS program. At the time of the interview she was a freshman student at the University. She attended JOBS Program while studying in a technical highschool. No data about her family educational and professional background were available.

At the time of the interview, the student had already taken a decision about her professional route after graduating highschool. She is attending the Pedagogy of Primary and Preschool Education study program. She describes the practical placement at kindergarten as a significant life experience, *"it was something...wow! To stay and to work with the children, to see really what is like [to work there]. [...] it was very beautiful."* (I.9, L.14-15). The pleasure and interest for the chosen professional domain is strong for this case, *"Since I was small I had this tendency..."* (I.9, L.25), *"...I do what I like"* (I.9, L.7). The student also mentions the role of a significant adult in making her decision *"I had, indeed, a very young teacher and I liked her"* (I.9, L.31) and the role of her family background: *"I come from a family with many brothers and taking care of them..."* (I.9, L.26).

She has a clear vision about her future, intending to work as a teacher in primary school after graduating *"I want to teach. I want to be in the educational system. I'm thinking about teaching at primary level..."* (I.9, L.18-19).

For this interviewee, learning is based in observing others, practicing and reflecting on the observed aspects: *"A thing I saw in someone else and I wanted to do it also, to progress, to do it as good as possible"* (I.9, L.73-74), *"...to apply"* (I.9, L.76).

The experience in JOBS program is described as *"a very, very good experience"* (I.9, L.39), *"it was a new experience"* (I.9, L.64). She remembers specific activities she attended to in a program: drawing a poster with several possible jobs, doing presentations in front of colleagues.

The main benefit of the program is associated, for the girl, with the main objective of the program: *"I think that was the aim for us, to figure out what we want to do next, what we aspire at, what we want to become. [...] Maybe we weren't aware then."* (I.9, L.58-60). Working in teams, listening to colleagues, following a leader are other specific named gains after attending the program.

The student also identifies the benefits in personal development: *“The fact that we worked all the time in teams, that we had to listen to each other, to put in balance what was good, what was bad and to reach a consensus, helped me. [...] not necessarily to correct myself, but to stay and to analyze myself, to see that sometimes I have to stay and to listen.”* (I.9, L.86-89). Reflecting to her experiences in JOBS, the girl now considers herself as being more *“understanding”* (I.9, L.92). Team-work is an activity which contributes to self- and other-knowledge: *“...only through this activity we can help [them] ... to know each other.”* (I.9, L.96-97).

The general perception on JOBS Program is that *“everything had a purpose and it was appropriate [...] It was thought as it should, not too tiring... Everything was [meant] to keep you on...”* (I.9, L.103-105).

This case has a very clear and consistent future orientation. She already made a career decision which is strongly based on her interest in the domain. Family background and early school experiences also contributed in shaping her career choices. Current school experiences are also significant and strengthen the career decision she took. The perception on JOBS program is highly positive, due to the novelty of the project, the perceived utility of it and to the team-based tasks involved by the program.

7.4.2 Interpretation of results

In interpreting the results, three lines of interpretation are taken into account. First line is strongly related with the questions of the interview study, namely the perception on the experience and utility of the JOBS-program (1). The second line regards the attitude towards learning (2), while the third one focuses on attitude towards work (3).

1) All interviewed students identified the *benefits of attending the JOBS-program*. The main gains are related to the development of specific job-related skills: taking an interview, initiating a contact and interpersonal skills, making a presentation, team-working skills. When asked about their memories related to JOBS program, most students mentioned tasks-based learning situations (such as taking an interview or making a presentation). The type of learning implied by the JOBS program contribute greatly to the perception of the utility of the program. The perception on the utility of the program seems also to be related to how clear are the students' plans for future professional route. Students who named few specific professional alternatives and base their decision on personal interest or skills (e.g. Case 8), identified more long-term specific job-related skills of JOBS program, like those abovementioned. Students who are uncertain about their future (e.g. Case 3, Case 7), named more general skills without a specific context for exercising those skills (e.g. interpersonal skills).

2) The *attitude towards learning* of interviewed students is related to their background, namely to significant life experiences they mentioned and to relevant extra-curricular activities they were involved into. For example, the interviewee Case 5, a girl, has a pragmatic attitude towards learning in terms of outcomes and expected values of the outcome (learning is a tool). Among the relevant factors in her educational paths, she stresses the role of others, even significant life events are interpersonal experiences. We could assume that formation of attitudes towards learning have a strong social base, an idea sustained by the fact that this pragmatic attitude is more frequent among interviewees coming from families with medium education level. At a different perspective, are the students who view learning as a constant set of opportunities for personal and professional development (e.g. Case 8 and Case 2).

3) The *attitude towards work* of interview students differs, therefore, and does not seem to be related to attending the JOBS Program. Extracurricular activities and hobbies have also an impact on students' attitude towards work. Those students practicing a sport or any type of systematic activity perceive work as a source of pleasure and of benefits for the community. Other students have a more pragmatic view on work as a mean to gain money and to satisfy needs (e.g. Case 7). Work is also seen as a routine, implying less mental effort and more physical effort (e.g. Case 6). These different attitudes towards work shape students' plans for the future. For example, Case 3 who considers work and professions

merely a mean for making money, has vague and undifferentiated plans regarding his professional route, stating several different perspectives, but none being specific. A opposite example is Case 8, who has the experiences of obtaining success though effort, view work as a contribution to the social good. His plans for the future are more clearly stated, having two very well-articulated professional alternatives.

Regarding the learning situations about the world of professions, most students relate to the JOBS Program as the most significant learning opportunity. Some of them (e.g. Case 1 and Case 9) hardly identify similar learning situation, either in or outside the school. It may be that the only significant situation in which they were exposed to information about jobs and professions was JOBS Program. Other students mention practical placement and interaction with working adults as similar opportunities for gaining specific job- and career-related knowledge and awareness, but none names specific job-related skills developed through these means.

7.5 Conclusions

Few years after attending the JOBS-program, the students perceive their experiences in the program as beneficial, both for developing specific *job-related skills* and for developing *interpersonal skills*. The JOBS activity most frequently associated with gaining these benefits was taking an interview to an employed person. Team-work task, brainstorming, presentations and diagrams are also specific remembered activities. Overall, the perception on the JOBS-program is highly positive due to the type and the content of learning in the program.

Interviewed students do not have specific professional options for continuing their educational route. All participants in the interview study coming from a theoretical highschool intend to continue their study at university level, while those coming from technical college plan to start working after graduating.

The support of teachers and school experiences are somewhat significant in planning the future, but students' attitudes towards learning and working seem to be highly relevant in making a decision about educational and professional options.

Learning about professions world is possible and useful though JOBS Program. Beside targeted intervention such as JOBS, students consider that practical placement and social learning (observing or asking employees) as also effective ways of learning about professions world.

Unfortunately, due to the insignificant number of Non-JOBS-students included in the interview study, a comparative qualitative analysis between JOBS- and Non-JOBS-students in terms of their educational path could not be performed.

7.6 Annexes to the Interview Study: Interview guide

Objectives of the interviews:

- To understand the perception of students on their experience in JOBS classes
- To identify their professional and educational path after Jobs
- To identify what gains/ benefits do students considered to have obtained as a result of participating to JOBS program
- To identify the meaning of learning and the meaning of education about professions for students

Identifying information: Gender, age, class

Themes and Questions

Romanian language	English language
<p>Întrebări introductive</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Descrie-mi o experiență din viața ta pe care ți-ar plăcea să ți-o amintești, ceva ce consideri important în viața ta. 2. Spune-mi, te rog, câteva lucruri despre tine: ce faci în acest moment? care este situația ta actuală? cu ce te ocupi? 3. Cum ai ajuns în acest punct? Cum ai ajuns să faci ceea ce faci acum? Ce anume crezi că te-a ajutat să ajungi în acest punct? 4. Ce intenționezi să faci după ce termini școala? 	<p>Introductive questions</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Describe me a past or present experience you would like to remember, an aspect of your life that you consider to be important. 2. Please tell me a few things about yourself: what are you doing now? what is your current situation? 3. How did you reach at this point? How did you get to do what you do right now? What helped you reach this point? 4. What will you do after you have finished school?
<p>Percepția asupra JOBS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. <u>For JOBS-students (J):</u> Să presupunem că te întâlnești cu un prieten care îți spune "Am auzit că ai participat la proiectul JOBS. Ce este JOBS?" Ce i-ai spune? <u>For Non JOBS-students (NJ):</u> Să presupun că te întâlnești cu un prieten care a participat în proiectul Jobs. Ce ți-ar spune acest prieten despre Jobs? 6. J: Ce îți amintești despre Jobs? NJ: Ce îți amintești că ai auzit despre JOBS? 	<p>Perception of JOBS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. <u>For JOBS-students (J):</u> Let's assume that you meet a friend who tells you "I heard you participated in JOBS programs. What is JOBS?" What would you tell him? <u>For Non-JOBS-students (NJ):</u> "You heard from a friend, that he/she participated in the JOBS-program. What would this JOB-Student talk/explain to you?" 6. J: What do you remember about JOBS? NJ: What do you remember that you heard about JOBS program?
<p>Importanța programului JOBS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. J: Gândindu-te la experiențele tale din ultima perioadă și la situația ta actuală, ce crezi ACUM despre JOBS? NJ: Ce crezi acum despre programul educațional JOBS? 	<p>Importance of JOBS</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. J: Taking into consideration all your experiences from the past year and how you stand now, what do you think NOW about JOBS? NJ: What do you think now about this educational program JOBS?
<p>Rezultatele învățării (doar JOBS)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Ce ai învățat în cadrul Jobs? Ce înseamnă a învăța pentru tine? Îmi poți da exemple de alte situații în viață în care ai învățat lucruri similare cu cele învățate în JOBS? 	<p>Learning outcomes (only JOBS)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. What did you learn in JOBS? What does learning means to you? Can you tell me some other situations in life in which you learn the same as in JOBS?
<p>Beneficiile JOBS (doar JOBS)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 9. Din ceea ce ai învățat în JOBS, ce anume te-a ajutat? În ce fel te-au ajutat aceste lucruri? <p>Satisfacția față de JOBS (doar JOBS)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 10. Ce ai recomanda să păstrăm în programul JOBS? 11. Ce ai recomanda să schimbăm în programul JOBS? 	<p>Gained Benefits (only JOBS)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 9. From what you learned in Jobs, what did help you? In what way it helped you? <p>Satisfaction with JOBS (only JOBS)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 10. What would you recommend to further keep in JOBS? 11. What changes would you recommend to JOBS?
<p>Importance of learning about professions</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 12. Ce crezi despre profesii, în general? Ce rol au ele? 13. Ce rol crezi că au pentru societate? 14. Cum poate un elev să învețe în școală despre lumea profesiilor? 	<p>Importance of learning about professions</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 12. What do you think about professions? What are important functions of them? 13. What are important aspects of professions with regard to society? 14. How can one learn something about the world of jobs in schools?
<p>Încheiere</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 15. Ai dori să mai îmi spui ceva despre JOBS, în afara celor discutate? 	<p>Closing question (all: JOBS and NON-JOBS)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 15. Is there anything else you would like to tell me about JOBS?

8 Dissemination

8.1 Publications

- Keller-Schneider, M., David, L. T., Cazan, A. M., Truta, C. & Albisser, S. (2017). JOBS RESEARCH, Evaluation of the Educational Project 'JOBS'. Report Part II: Effects of individual and social resources on the learning output. Zürich: University of teacher Education.
- David, L.T., Truta, C., Cazan, A.M., Albisser, S. & Keller-Schneider, M. (2017). Efectele programului JOBS asupra elevilor și profesorilor – ce contribuie la eficientizarea învățării? Extras din rezultatele cercetării în cadrul Programului JOBS. Brașov: Transilvania University of Brașov.
- Keller-Schneider, M., Albisser, S., David, L. T., Truta, C. & Cazan, A. M. (2016) Gerüstet für die Berufswelt – JOBS, ein Vorbereitungsprogramm zur Unterstützung von Jugendlichen in Rumänien im Übergang in die Berufswelt. Berufs- und Wirtschaftspädagogik bwp Spezial 12, 1-20.
- David, L.T., Truta, C., Cazan, A.M., Albisser, S. & Keller-Schneider, M. (2016). Learning orientation, motivation and self-efficacy as a trigger for teachers to engage in a new teaching setting. Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brașov. Series VII: Social Sciences & Law, Vol. 9 (59) No. 2 – 2016.
- Truta, C., Cazan, A.M., David, -T., Albisser, S. & Keller-Schneider, M. (2016). Psychometric qualities of the scale for goal-oriented learning motivation on two Romanian samples. Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brașov. Series VII: Social Sciences & Law, Vol. 9 (58) No. 2 – 2016.
- Keller-Schneider, M. & Albisser, S. (2015). JOBS RESEARCH, Evaluation of the Educational Project JOBS. A project to evaluate the effects of the JOBS teaching and learning materials. Report Part I. Zürich: University of teacher Education.

8.2 Presentations

Events

- David, L.T., Truta, C. & Cazan, A.M. (2017). Presentation of JOBS-RESEARCH-study to schools, teachers and the inspectorate, involved in the JOBS-study. University of Brașov, 20. June 2017.
- Cazan, A.M., David, L.D. & Truta, C. (2016) Session of the Students' Scientific Papers, Brașov: Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences, Transilvania University of Brașov, May 2016.
- Truta, C., Cazan, A.M. & David, L.T. (2016). Schools' Pedagogical Circles. Brașov County

To the scientific community

2017

- Keller-Schneider, M., David, L.T., Cazan, A.M., Truta, C. & Albisser, S. (2017). Changes of teachers' beliefs on teaching and learning trough further education. ISNITE 2017, University of Gdansk (Danzig), Poland:29.-31. August 2017.
- Keller-Schneider, M., David, L.T., Truta, C., Cazan, A.M. & Albisser, S. (2017). Beliefs and motives of teachers attending JOBS-Project and its effects on teachers' and students' learning outcome. ECER 2017, University of Copenhagen: 22 to 25 August 2017.
- Cazan, A.M, David, L.T, Truta, C. (2017). Workshop Dezvoltarea abilităților de management al carierei la adolescenți - programul JOBS, The 19th International Conference „Scientific Research and Education in the Air Force – AFASES 2017“ Brașov.

2016

- Cazan, A., Keller-Schneider, M., David, L., Truta, C. & Albisser, S. (2016). Teachers' attitudes towards cooperation – do-es attending the JOBS program matters? Presentation an der EARLI SIG 11 Teacher and Teacher Education, 20.-22. June in Zürich.

Cazan, A.M., Truta, C., David, L.T., Albisser, S. & Keller-Schneider, M. (2016). Changes in students' motivations and learning orientation as a result of enrolment in a career counselling program. ECP European Conference on Personality, 19.-23. July in Timisoara, Romania.

Truta, C., David, L., Cazan, A. & Albisser, S. & Keller-Schneider, M. (2016). What drives teachers to engage in Jobs Program as a task-based and student-focused teaching and learning setting? Presentation an der EARLI SIG 11 Teacher and Teacher Education, 20.-22. June in Zürich.

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2015

Keller-Schneider, M., Albisser, S.; David, L.; Truta, C. & Cazan, A. (2015). Students Matter. The Effects of Motivation, Self-Concept and Self-Efficacy on Outcomes of Students' Learning in the JOBS Intervention-Program. Job Orientation Training in Businesses and Schools to Educate Romanian Students for Professional Life. Presentation at the Conference SELF, 21. August in Kiel, Germany.

Keller-Schneider, M., Albisser, S., David, L., Cazan, A. & Truta, C. (2015). Fostering Students' Career Decisions: Effects of the JOBS Program Job Orientation Training in Businesses and Schools to Educate Romanian Students for Professional Life. EARLI 2015, 26. August in Limassol, Cyprus.

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